

**TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE CHANGE MANAGEMENT IN HEALTH INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY: THE CASE OF THE NATIONAL ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD
SYSTEM IN NHS ENGLAND**

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ABSTRACT

The successful implementation of an integrated Electronic Health Record System (EHRS) in England has remained a persistent challenge. Implementing an EHR is a huge investment and a challenging endeavour for due to its complexity and need for integration. In the face of the significant advancements that occurred in the field of EHRs over the last two decades, implementation and adoption issues persist, and the advantages of EHR adoption fall short of expectations. Despite numerous efforts, there is a lack of sustainable change management frameworks for EHRS, particularly within the UK context. This research aims to address this gap by investigating the sustainability of EHRS change management in NHS England and developing an effective framework for a sustainable EHRS, complemented by practical implementation guidance for managers and practitioners. A qualitative research approach, specifically a case study design, will be employed to achieve these objectives. This methodology allows for an in-depth exploration of the complexities surrounding EHRS implementation and its management in the context of NHS England. The research will draw insights from key stakeholders, including healthcare professionals, policymakers, and IT experts, to gain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in sustaining EHRS initiatives. The primary contribution of this research lies in the development of a Strategic EHRS Implementation Sustainability Framework. This framework aims to provide a systematic approach to manage change effectively, enhance stakeholder engagement, and address the barriers that hinder sustainable EHRS implementation. Additionally, this research will offer Practical Implementation Guidance tailored to the specific context of NHS England. The guidance will empower managers and practitioners with actionable steps to foster long-term sustainability in EHRS projects. By bridging the literature gap and offering a comprehensive framework and practical guidance, this research seeks to

make a significant contribution to the field of health information technology and sustainable change management. It is anticipated that the findings of this study will not only benefit NHS England but also serve as a valuable reference for other healthcare organizations aiming to implement EHRs sustainably.

DECLARATION

I declare that the entirety of this thesis is my work, that the content has been properly referenced when applicable, and that it has never been submitted to any educational institution for any certification or degree.

DEDICATION

To the Glory of Lord God Almighty, I dedicate this thesis to my father, Mr. Taiwo Gabriel Oladiran, who strongly sponsored my academic pursuits since childhood, and my beloved wife, Temitope Esther Oladiran, who has stood by and supported me on the journey of conducting this research.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction

Essentially, in this opening chapter, the Researcher fundamentally examine and elucidate the background of this research, revealing the research problems and problem statement, the significance of the research and the research motivation. It also contains an introduction to the aim of the research, as well as its corresponding objectives alongside the research questions. It presents the contribution of this research, literature review summary and proposed methodology. It discloses and discusses the research limitations and shows the structure of the study.

The Researcher's current work within the arm of NHS that focuses on delivering excellent healthcare and health improvement to patients and the public of England proffers a profound and invaluable experience for this research. This department plays a crucial role in ensuring that the healthcare workforce of today and tomorrow possesses the right numbers, skills, values, and behaviours, and is in the right place at the right time. The relevance of the Researcher's NHS experience to Electronic Health Record Systems (EHRS) change management is reflected in involvement in the significance of health improvement and the impact it can have on patient outcomes. EHRS implementation is a strategic step towards enhancing health improvement efforts. Through Electronic Health Record System, patient data can be easily accessed, analysed, and shared, leading to more informed decision-making and personalized patient care. The Researcher's experience in supporting health improvement initiatives has impacted the understanding of the importance of an efficient EHRS change management strategy to achieve optimal patient outcomes as demonstrated in this research.

1.1 Background

HIT involves the use of digital advancement, information and technological innovation or even software models to optimise organisational performance and systems delivery in the healthcare sector (Creswell *et al.*, 2021). Patient expectations have been radicalised through the advent of disruptive digital transformation. This has grossly impacted the means by which and speed at which healthcare organisations must respond to this digital development. Hence, HIT thrives on agile transformation (Accenture, 2021). The agile method of operating is, therefore, the means by which organisations respond to changes, and it is specifically an exclusive approach used by leading and high-performing organisations in the current era of digitalization (Accenture, 2020). It aids organisations in honing profound knowledge of changing customer needs and how to meet them. It facilitates the quicker and perpetual improvement of patient and stakeholder engagement and interaction. It propels cheaper and smarter ways of working while increasing accountability and transparency within a healthcare organisation, which often impact organisational reputation. HIT can also result in effective organisational cultures with heightened satisfaction and consolidated team diversity. In HIT change management (Yusif *et al.*, 2019), the agile way of operational engagement is not restricted to information technology software development teams in healthcare organisations. Rather, it is tremendously relevant at all operational levels with all other departments within a trust, hospital or healthcare organisation, and it harmonises information technology and healthcare services and operations across all spheres in the sector (Sheikh *et al.*, 2021)

HIT changes the means of healthcare operation in its entirety across all levels of an organisation. It can be implemented by transforming hierarchical departments with assigned

managers into small teams with no designated or appointed managers (Laukka *et al.*, 2020). These small teams are comprised of staff members from across all the departments within an organisation. They are often handpicked from each department. The team is often led by a product owner and is ultimately responsible for its patient-driven purpose. A successful comprehensive implementation (Ko *et al.*, 2016) always starts with baby steps and a few pilot teams. Afterwards, the agile principles and techniques are further scaled and extended across the teams for a selected number of divisions. Finally, an all-encompassing measure of the degree of adoption of HIT through agile transformation across the entire scope of the organisation is executed. There are diverse models, schemes and frameworks that are fundamental and critical to its success, and they are not without the challenges and changes that accompany HIT (Choi and Ahn, 2021)

1.2 Problem Statement

Electronic health record system (EHRS) is not a new concept in the United Kingdom healthcare sector. It has been right at the centre of information technology development and implementation in the optimisation of healthcare performance. However, over the years, it has not ultimately lived up to the fulfilment of its potential, especially at the level of national implementation (Creswell *et al.*, 2021). It has often been riddled with challenges and compelling problems, which has undermined its purpose and inhibited its merits and has been a long-standing controversial concept in the healthcare sector (Tayefi, *et al.*, 2021). The systematic delivery of healthcare services has been a typical process of synergy that involves a continuous chain of communication and information exchange involving a wide array of practitioners across different specialities involving care (Kim *et al.*, 2019). EHRS is the system by which information dissemination and patient data interaction can be increased in

effectiveness and patient medical data and relevant information can be easily assessed with no time constraints and with no form of ambiguity (Kumar and Mostafa, 2020). However, it is still in its infancy because there is no national database in which patient information and medical history data are stored in detail and with precise accuracy that would make it effective for use in the delivery of healthcare services to patients (Madhavan *et al.*, 2021). Medical practitioners should be able to adequately attend to any patient without prior knowledge of that person's medical past and in situations in which the patient does not have the full capacity to respond or give the required information that is vital to their treatment. Through an effective, comprehensive and integrated national EHRS, in the United Kingdom, medical practitioners can quickly and easily access patient information to provide prompt and well-tailored healthcare services. However, this system is not currently in place for many healthcare providers. Hospitals within the National Health Service (NHS) have adopted EHRS with many concerns and bottlenecks in its change management, which has resulted in many emphases on structures and strategies geared towards the successful implementation and acceptance of the EHRS initiative (Wood *et al.*, 2021). The authors of existing literature (Mohammed *et al.*, 2021; Dahleez *et al.*, 2020; European Commission *et al.*, 2021; Hower *et al.*, 2019, Bloom *et al.*, 2021) have focused on the benefits, designs and implementation of EHRS. However, little attention has been drawn to the pursuit and provision of a sustainable EHRS change management framework in the UK healthcare sector (Cho *et al.*, 2021, Fennelly *et al.*, 2020; Leung *et al.*, 2021). There has been insignificant research into the means and strategic frameworks required for the development of the sustainable management of EHRS, especially in the UK (Beauvais *et al.*, 2021; Walker *et al.*, 2021; Birnbaum *et al.*, 2018; Miraldo *et al.*, 2019). Hence, this study is focused on addressing this gap to foster successful and sustainable EHRS change management in the UK healthcare sector.

1.3 Research Significance

This research provides a comprehensive approach to effective change management for an integrated EHRS and is essential to all healthcare managers, leaders, board of trustees, healthcare organisation chief executive officers, clinicians, medical practitioners, patients and major stakeholders. It is an important study for decision-makers in the healthcare sector, particularly in the area of the optimisation of healthcare services with the fast-growing possibilities of information technology for the quicker, smarter and safer delivery of qualitative healthcare services. This study is an addition to the knowledge of IT change management, particularly in a sector less researched for business excellence and introduces a practicable management framework for sustainable and consistent outputs in the management of organisational change in the NHS. Various research and studies (Kumar and Mostafa, 2020, Turulja *et al.*, 2020, Frigidis and Chatzoglou, 2018, Nguyen *et al.*, 2017) have been carried out on the subject, but the significance of the current study is encapsulated in its provision of a framework for the productive and sustainable change management of EHRS at all levels, whether locally or on a national scale. This is a comprehensive solution, as well as a profound response to the problems identified.

1.4 Research Aims

My primary aim in this research was to investigate the sustainability of EHRS change management in NHS England and develop an effective framework for a sustainable EHRS supported by implementation guidance for managers and practitioners.

1.5 Research Objectives

There are systematic and sequential procedures that need to be strictly followed to achieve the main aim of this study. The following are the objectives that had to be accomplished to fulfil the research aim:

1. Evaluate the current status of healthcare IT systems in general and specifically EHRs in the NHS
2. Analyse the factors (challenges and barriers) that affect the implementation of healthcare IT systems in general, particularly EHRs in the NHS
3. Evaluate the conditions necessary for the success of change of the sustainability of EHRs in the NHS.
4. Evaluate the effectiveness of existing frameworks in healthcare IT systems.

1.6 Research Questions

1. What is the current status of healthcare IT systems in general and the EHRs in the NHS in particular?
2. What are the factors (challenges and barriers) that affect the implementation of healthcare IT systems in general and the EHRs in the NHS in particular?
3. What are the necessary conditions for the successful change of the sustainability of the EHRs in the NHS?
4. What are the existing frameworks for the implementation and sustainability of healthcare IT systems?

1.7 Summary of Research Methodology

This section contains insight into the methodology used in this research. Detailed explanations and discussions are shown in Chapter Four. The most suitable research philosophy identified for this research is interpretivism (Duminda and Allen, 2020) due to the essence of the research subject, which is mainly EHRs in the healthcare sector. This philosophy helped to enlighten me, provided knowledge about HIT, especially the EHRs in the healthcare sector and fostered the design and formulation of an unprecedented framework for sustainable EHRs implementation and change management. This enabled the provision and recommendation of implementation guidance to leaders and managers in the healthcare sector, as well as scholars. According to Mattimoe *et al.* (2021), the choice of interpretivism philosophy is influenced by the researcher's experience and previous study experience in the field of business and management. The research approach utilized in this study was a combination of inductive and deductive reasoning because this combination is an efficient means of research (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). However, it is essential that there is no parity in engagement in this combination. Inductive reasoning is more predominant and minimally complemented by the deductive approach (Al-Ababneh, 2020). The researcher's business and management background, experience in the use of HIT in the NHS and understanding of the concept of change management forms the inductive basis for this study. However, to further broaden insight into EHRs change management and develop a sustainable HIT change management framework, the contribution of deductive reasoning cannot be undermined. The framework has been developed through deductive reasoning based on the literature review and the gaps in the literature. Hence, the deductive approach was used to control and guide the inductive reasoning, which is mainly observation-based. The research strategy used in this thesis is case study research (Yin, 2018). Case study research

was selected as the strategy for this research due to its flexibility provided the and possibility of providing an enormous amount of knowledge about achieving sustainable change management to both scholars and top management. This case study research was subjected to reliability, internal validity, external validity and construct validity tests (Sürücü and Maşlakçı, 2020). The design adopted in this research is qualitative research because the philosophy adopted in this study is interpretivism. Qualitative research was adopted because it enables in-depth analysis, knowledge enhancement, participant involvement and perspective-sharing and flexibility (Braun and Clarke, 2021). Data gathering for this qualitative research was achieved by means of conducting interviews.

1.8 Research Contribution

The actualisation of the aims and objectives of this research will yield the following theoretical and practical contributions:

1.8.1 Theoretical Contributions

1. Through an extensive analysis and evaluation of diverse ideas and EHRS subjects, immense contributions will be made to academic knowledge. This is catalysed by intensive evaluations and assessments of studies that are corporate and management-oriented with other literature that is purely academic and theoretical. The investigator's identification and acknowledgement of the effects of the factors that influence the implementation of EHRS change management also aid in the fulfilment of this knowledge contribution.
2. A qualitative research methodology was adopted for the critical evaluation and analysis of the case study. Hence, this research contains deep insights and broadens the knowledge of EHRS with comprehensive solutions to the challenges encountered

in its sustainability. It also provides a clear understanding of the peculiarity of the barriers involved in change management in the adoption and implementation of HIT.

1.8.2 Practical Contributions

1. This study makes a significant contribution to the related literature through the formulation of the Sustainable HIT Change Management Framework for the healthcare sector. This framework presents a concise and comprehensive change management process in the implementation of sustainable EHRs and includes critical factors that are important to successful change management at each phase of the process. This framework provides senior management in the healthcare sector with a blueprint for the implementation of a reliable and sustainable EHRs.
2. The research provides improved insight into the benefits and significance of EHRs in the healthcare sector. The investigator intends to present and describe the essentials required for EHRs implementation through the evaluation of the prevalent challenges hindering its sustainability in the healthcare sector, thereby providing a guideline that is both prescriptive and implementable. This will provide healthcare senior management and leadership with systematic guidelines for the implementation of a successful and long-lasting EHRs through the sustainable EHRs change management framework.

1.9 Thesis Outline

This thesis is comprised of seven comprehensive chapters that are outlined in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1.1: Thesis Structure

Source: Researcher

Chapter One: This is the introductory chapter, and it includes the research background, problem statement and significance of the research as it relates to its contribution to knowledge and its uniqueness in theory and practice. It also includes the research aims, objectives and research questions. Furthermore, Chapter 1 grants insight into the research methodology approach and the structure of the thesis.

Chapter Two: This is an extensive review of relevant literature, past and present.

Chapter Three: The third chapter presents the theoretical framework with essential models, tools, phenomena and theories that are interrelated and central to the subject of this research. It contains the evaluations of current frameworks and a description of the proposed framework.

Chapter Four: The methodology used in this study is detailed in Chapter Four, along with the approach and process of the research.

Chapter Five: In Chapter Five, the methods and techniques of data collection used in this study are presented along with the results of the data analysis.

Chapter Six: This chapter appraises the discussion section of the research with adept consideration of the findings of the data analysis.

Chapter Seven: This chapter contains the conclusion and recommendations of the research expatiating on the research contributions, strengths and limitations and areas for future research.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

EHRs are electronic or paper medical records about patients (Koh and Ahmed, 2021). EHRs are often referred to as electronic medical records (EMRs) (Gamage *et al.*, 2020). EHRs can also be defined as collections of information that pertain to a patient's previous, current or future physical or psychological health records that are stored electronically, used to take, transfer, gather, inventorise, recover, connect and exploit data, essentially for the provision of healthcare services through its featured usability (Bloom *et al.*, 2021). As stated earlier, EHRs are paper patient records that have been made electronic. They contain health-based information about a patient that can be accessed by approved and licensed clinicians and healthcare staff within an organisation (Lynn *et al.*, 2017). EHRs enable perpetual information sharing and can be updated, so they culminate as detailed health records of a patient's lifetime (Koh and Ahmed, 2021).

There are certain core fundamentals that characterise EHRs. An EHR must feature a longitudinal compilation of electronic health-related information about a patient and for the patient. It must grant readily available electronic admittance to authorised personnel and users alike. It is imperative for an EHR to provide support for decision-making and adequate knowledge that heightens the quality of healthcare, the safety of healthcare delivery and efficiency in productivity (Walker *et al.*, 2021). It must also underpin and impact the processes of the delivery of healthcare services. EHRs provide platforms of engagement for patients to participate in their healthcare because they are designed with interactive interfaces that accommodate patient access (Tai-Seale *et al.*, 2021).

The documentation of health-related records was around long before recent civilization. In medieval times, medical records were majorly aimed towards knowledge dissemination and transfer through teaching to impart knowledge to medical apprentices (Dalianis, 2018). It was often in the form of short, comprehensive written documents and case reports. Over the span of several decades, these case reports were used as patient records by physicians at various intervals. A discovery of 48 Egyptian case reports with an archaeological date of 1600 BC was discovered in 1862. These reports contain documentation of dislocation, fractures, tumours and wounds (Metwaly *et al.*, 2021).

2.2 Overview of Electronic Health Record System

Catching and adequately utilising clinical data and information to guarantee high-quality, protected and manageable medical care administration is generally perceived as significant (Gartner, 2019), and the information in EHRs was imperative to decision-production in general wellbeing approaches during the coronavirus pandemic (Williamson *et al.*, 2020). An EHR is a longitudinal record of data regarding the wellbeing status of a person in PC processible structure across practices and trained professionals and continuously empowers approved admittance to clinical records. Just as growing the ability to use clinical information for checking patient results and leading reviews and examinations (Kouroubali and Katehakis, 2019), the EHR grants admittance to patient data without wasting any time, empowering medical care experts to invest more energy with patients, lessening the duplication of testing and other work, and working on the wellbeing and nature of the care given (Warraich *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, the coordination of different capacities and programming, such as clinical choice, help, and scanner tag prescription organisation further extends its potential advantages.

Electronic patient records (EPRs) or EMRs offer many of these advantages. However, some ERPs and EHRs exclusively contain the records from a singular association. Shared or outlined care records and patient entrances separately store and work with admittance to explicit patient data needed by healthcare professionals and patients (Health Information Quality Authority, 2019). Despite the many advantages of using these frameworks, challenges have been met in executing a completely interoperable EHR among essential and optional considerations (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2018), regularly credited to the execution cycle rather than the item provided by the EHR seller. Accordingly, the execution cycle is basic (Fragidis and Chatzoglou, 2018) and should be considered as a continuous interaction that starts during acquisition and proceeds throughout each period of planning, advancement, testing, 'going live' and enhancement. Although HIT was present in the United Kingdom and United States since the 1960s (Collen and Miller, 2015), their optimisation and extensive application were later peculiarities in countries such as France, Italy and especially the Republic of Ireland, where public medical care is overseen by the Wellbeing Administration Chief, who uses with a private wellbeing framework (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). The Workplace of the Main Data Official (CIO) has, by and large, liability regarding implanting innovation inside the wellbeing framework, and until now, EPRs have been executed in some singular private and public medical clinics and most general professional (GP) workplaces, but none has patient interaction or engagement (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). Notwithstanding this, numerous different clinics and NHS trusts remain, to a great extent, paper-based and do not operate exclusively on EHRs. The implementation of EHRs, as seen in the case of eHealth Ireland, should be people-driven, visionary-led and strategically executed. Consequently, the preliminary period of an EHR project is a helpful time for strategy creators and other key partners to survey the lessons from the executions of HIT, both locally and universally.

Regardless, an immense measure of writing is extended on themes like EHRs, which renders it difficult for strategy producers to stay exceptional, maybe enhancing technical or practical knowledge gap (Bloom *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, medical care is a perplexing and versatile framework that should be perceived and recognised when endeavouring to repeat triumphs in another setting (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). The initiation and implementation of EHR projects in any climate should generate relevant insight into the improvement of healthcare. It is important for produced information to give significant and pertinent key contemplations that are promptly lined up with the strategy and decision-making process (She *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, the point of this survey is to distinguish between and investigate the key variables that advance fruitful EHR executions across medical services settings with dynamic cooperation from key partners in the Irish setting.

The world situation, described by incessant changes in social, technological, financial, political and political systems, guides companies to continually assess their goals and processes. Besides in special cases, organisations related to general wellbeing end up being profoundly impacted by the climate and see themselves obliged to refresh their board approaches and practices. The points of view of such organisations changed. They used to be dedicated to helping others and lacked the commitment to introduce proof to the board. They are also presently heading in an enterprising direction, directed by execution, results and straightforwardness (Botega *et al.*, 2020).

The intricacy of these associations requests the age, handling and accessibility of an expressive volume of data, which is fundamental for their cycles. These associations also settle on endowments for decision-production in general wellbeing approaches (Cresswell *et al.*, 2020). These data include patients' EHRs, clinical and nursing rehearsals, clinical

conditions, information and learning about the executives and the association of regulatory practices in the climate where the medical services happen, among others (Gatner, 2019). By acquiring, handling and making them accessible for quite a long time, a successful evaluation is empowered as managerial and functional proficiency, as well as the prosperity of society (Cresswell *et al.*, 2020). In such a setting, government attempts to execute healthcare data frameworks through innovative technology have been occurring globally in nations with various advancement levels to work on patient wellbeing and the quality and productivity of medical care administrations (Haried *et al.*, 2019).

These drives are usually portrayed as complicated projects or megaprojects (Value *et al.*, 2018) because they happen on a territorial or public scale (largescale) and include the coordination of various partners who generally have unmistakable interests and viewpoints (Klecun *et al.*, 2019). Given the expanding recurrence of the execution of huge scope HIT, specialists have announced the need to augment information and comprehension of the points of view used in such executions (Cresswell *et al.*, 2020). A few researchers have contended (Ross *et al.*, 2016; Sligo *et al.*, 2017; Klecun *et al.*, 2019) that there is expansive literature on the prompt execution of HIT and localised and integrated HIT systems. Research on the execution of a highly extensive and holistic integrated system, on a national scale, for example, is scarce (Luz *et al.*, 2021), particularly concerning the sustainability of the system, which is the focus of this present research. Hence, this research aims to address this literature gap, thereby adding to the related knowledge in both academia and professional practice in the healthcare sector.

According to Carvalho *et al.* (2020), the determination of applicable literature through an organised process is a basic advance in the improvement of precise reviews. The past reviews

of the literature on programs for the execution and evaluation of largescale HISs generally depict the program zeroing in on at least one explicit nation (Price *et al.*, 2018) and explicit wellbeing data innovations. However, this literature will review EHRs generally across different settings to deduce significant factors and process management strategies that may impact the peculiarity of the sustainable change management of the EHRs in the UK. This review might help and direct current and future examination processes that are similar in nature. The exploration, interaction and fundamental discoveries might be utilised by various scientists expecting to foster examinations on the issue or to aid specialists, including those engaged in the execution of largescale national integrated EHRs. In the forthcoming area, HITs and the qualities of their enormous scopes will be depicted.

2.3 Application of the Electronic Health Record System as HIT

Lately, there has been a developing interest in EHR reception in numerous nations. This is because of an expanding acknowledgement that a grounded HIT is critical to accomplishing better consideration at lower costs. EHR has been recognised to be a vital piece of an effective medical services data framework that ensures positive wellbeing results (Tsai *et al.*, 2020). As indicated by ISO, an EHR is characterised as a storehouse of patient information in a computerised structure. This data is put away and traded safely and available to different approved clients. It contains review, simultaneous and imminent data, and its main role is to help effective and quality-coordinated wellbeing (Odekunle, 2016). It plays a critical role in the medical care framework, and it has been applied in different ways in the medical care framework. Many examinations led in various medical care settings have demonstrated that the expansive and proper utilisation of EHRs in the medical services framework will help wellbeing experts decrease clinical blunders, accomplish successful consideration

coordination, work on understanding security and care quality and reduce medical care costs (Vehko *et al.*, 2019). For instance, by making a critical patient’s data electronically accessible, medical care data frameworks can serve to forestall requests for copy tests and methodologies, diminishing patient consumption of medical care administration. Moreover, the accessibility of patient data in advanced structures will diminish the consumption of capacity, recovery and transportation of patient outlines in the wellbeing record division (Tubaishat, 2019). Medical services frameworks are data-concentrated undertakings. Medical services labourers need satisfactory information to oversee data and make choices while overseeing and running the endeavour and focusing on the patient to archive and convey plans and exercises to meet the administrative prerequisites of the certifying association (Alami *et al.*, 2020). The application of EHRs as a HIT is significant because it generates important data that can bolster the understanding of the various utilization, roles and functionalities of EHRs in the medical services framework. This can help decision-makers make educated choices about the most proficient ways to achieve the significant utilisation of EHR functionalities in various parts of the medical care sector.

According to Kim *et al.* (2019), the National Academy of Medicine (previously known as the Institute of Medicine) initiated a study of paper records and EHRs and published findings that argued for greater EHR adoption in the U.S. healthcare system. These findings also include the eight EHR key functionalities shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: EHRs Core Functionalities/Applications

Core Functions	Details
Data and information about health	Diagnoses, allergies, prescriptions, lab results, and other pertinent information about patients. As new clinical

	knowledge becomes available and users' needs change, requirements will change.
Result management	Manage all types of results, such as lab test results, radiology procedure results, and so on. Increases efficiency, improves patient safety, reduces duplicated testing, and enhances communication between doctors and patients.
Order management/entry	Eliminates lost orders and ambiguities caused by illegible handwriting, automates the development of related orders, monitors for duplicate orders, decreases the time it takes to fill orders and boosts clinician productivity.
Decision-making assistance	Assist providers in the diagnosis and management of diseases. Improve adherence to consensus norms and processes based on evidence.
Connectivity and electronic communication	Improve patient safety and quality of treatment by facilitating communication across care partners (e.g., lab, pharmacy, radiology). Improve the monitoring of public health.
Patient assistance	Patient education will be given more attention. It is possible that this will expand to telemedicine.
Reporting and administrative procedures	Improve efficiency by eliminating patient delays and confusion, improve access to treatments by confirming insurance eligibility immediately, more timely payments and less paperwork, faster drug recall communication and identify candidates for chronic illness management programs.
Population health management and reporting	Reduce costs associated with reporting important quality indicators by presenting clinical data in a standardized and manipulatable data format.

Source: Kim *et al.*, (2019)

2.3.1 EHR Applicability in Emergency Care

The huge volume of patients, quick staff turnover and high work pressure imply that the ease of use of all frameworks in the ED is significant. The progress of EHRS has brought numerous advantages to emergency care yet puts pressure on staff to enter the information. Helpless

convenience has a direct outcome and opportunity cost in staff time and assets that could be utilised in quiet care. Ease of use is a measure of the proportion of how viably an item can be utilised to play out its planned function (Bloom *et al.*, 2021). In a medical care association, there are various innovation frameworks that professionals use for successful medical care conveyance, and EDs have been slowly carrying out EHR frameworks since the 1970s. There are around 30 million ED attendances in the UK every year. In a solitary payer medical services framework like the NHS, which works across every one of the four nations in the UK, the enormous volume of patients getting pressing and crisis care implies that the advantages or misfortunes brought about by convenience are generous. Data frameworks that are difficult to utilise endanger patient security, are wasteful and add to burnout and an unfulfilling working life (Lee and Mylod, 2019). On the contrary, a framework that is not difficult to utilise is a positive advantage for staff, can expand proficiency and further develop wellbeing in crisis care (Ashton, 2018). Although applicability or ease of use may appear to be an undefined idea, it permits producers and clients to distinguish frameworks that have been suitably tested and found to help in clinical consideration through great usability. Applicability envelops numerous parts of client plans, like the reliable utilisation of elements and screen space, so an administrator does not need to consume a ton of mental energy to work out how to use a framework. A decent emergency department IT system can fundamentally benefit clinical, functional and monetary capacity and may effectively forestall patient damage through implementing clinical security frameworks.

In the UK, an enormous level of the NHS emergency service administration is conveyed by junior specialists, the majority of whom are simply connected to the emergency care for four months. This incessant turnover combined with the poor applicability establishes a climate with extremely high preparation requirements (Adams *et al.*, 2019). Dissimilar to some in

different nations, in the UK, there is no direct monetary tension on clinicians to enter information precisely. To address this, in certain destinations in Australia, recorders have been used to diminish the weight of administrative obligations, for example, recording conferences, organising tests and arrangements and finishing electronic clinical record tasks (Walker *et al.*, 2019). A framework with helpless ease of use is additionally unequivocally connected with doctor burnout while an exceptionally usable framework, especially one that is adequately adaptable to be versatile to criticism, can add to the sense of being esteemed at work (Melnick *et al.*, 2020). Poor ease of use can represent a danger to patient wellbeing. Divided presentations can forestall rational perspectives on patients' drugs and lead to solution blunders. Mortalities have been related to HIT failures, and in Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, United States, an ascent in paediatric mortality was incidental with an EHR framework execution (Bloom *et al.*, 2021).

Poor EHR applicability causes numerous issues for end clients and, subsequently, their associations and the patients they care for. One of the more significant issues identified with poor ease of use is the weakening usefulness of EM. For each electronic task that is requested of clinicians, time is detracted from their main responsibilities (Walker *et al.*, 2021). This amounts to an extremely enormous extent of medical care specialist time being spent on administrative work. An underlying way to advance towards progress, in this case, is to recognise main emergency physician duties and other undertakings. Main assignments for emergency specialists identify with extricating and incorporating data, imparting choices, data and necessities to patients, families and wellbeing groups and, once in a, embracing methodology (Vehko *et al.*, 2019).

2.3.2 Impact of EHRs on the Delivery of Qualitative Healthcare

EHRs are kept in medical clinics with a perspective on working on the nature of medical services administrations. They give a critical opportunity to improve wellbeing observation and evaluate administration conveyance, which can bring about advancement and the board of general wellbeing and better clinical choice (Dornan *et al.*, 2019). The use of EHRs in medical clinics has improved in quality because it vows to further develop the combination and availability of patient information and productivity and the cost-viability of medical care administrations. Furthermore, it can be used to change doctor–patient relationships to relationships in which medical care is shared by a group of medical care providers. The quickly changing climate also requires the reception of EHRs (Gatiti *et al.*, 2021). Electronic wellbeing records are considered essential to improving medical services administrations concerning medical service quality, as characterised by the Organisation of Medication (IOM), including, adequacy, effectiveness, security, idealness, patient-centredness and value. The IOM perceives the EHRs as a basic instrument for working on understanding security and medical service quality and a significant apparatus in lessening the expenses of short-term care (Abdulai and Adam, 2020). Furthermore, the reception of data innovation in medical care has decreased medical service administration costs and expanded efficiencies. EHRs impact medical care quality through documentation, clinical administration, practice the board and correspondence (Ayaad *et al.*, 2019). EHRs lead to effectiveness in medical care administrations by decreasing superfluous test orders and reducing medical care work time and the work done on documentation or other non-patient wellbeing related work. According to Mayer (2020), EHRs hold critical and delicate individual data for treatment, so they are a rich wellspring of insight for medical service providers. The scattering of this information is important to making a highly intelligent medical care framework and further developing the quality of medical service administrations. Electronic

wellbeing records face a great deal of difficulties in post-execution. A portion of these difficulties are normal in PC frameworks and incorporate interoperability, convenience and information security (Hamherra *et al.*, 2017). There is vulnerability concerning whether the execution of EHRs impacts the nature of wellbeing administrations in emergency clinics. There have been a few endeavours to comprehend the functionalities of EHRs that impact the nature of medical services. For example, researchers concentrated on automating clinical records frameworks to help medical clinics convey secure, understanding-focused and effective considerations, as well as support examination, quality improvement drives, general wellbeing, wellbeing administration arrangement, and exploration (Cherswell, *et al.*, 2021). EHR execution is associated with patient fulfilment gauges, specifically release data, care progress, the responsiveness of medical care labourers, the proposal of the emergency clinic and, by and large, medical clinic rating (Hu *et al.*, 2020). EHR further develops specialist–patient correspondence concerning the giving of input to patients, appropriate doctor presentation, advice for patients, time to be taken and the impact it will have on the patient, tuning in and reacting to patient concerns immediately. Doctors exert valiant efforts to ensure patients get the best medical care possible, are conscious and thoughtful to patients and are touchy to patient requirements, both physical and enthusiastic. Nonetheless, the impact of EHR use on specialist–patient correspondence was addressed by Taylor *et al.* (2014), who did not write about any measurably critical distinction after the execution of doctor–patient correspondence before and after EHR execution.

2.3.3 EHRs and Blockchain Technology

Much attention is being paid to improving health information as a result of improvements in digital technology and communication networks with the help of EHRs (Abouelmehdi *et al.*, 2018). Technological equipment is becoming increasingly prevalent in hospitals with

specialised services in every corner of the world. As a result, patients are eager to attend healthcare facilities. Healthcare providers, and patients on occasion, are forced to undergo specialist examinations. Doctors seek more effective therapies as a result, the patient's personal, clinical, pharmacy and accounting information is all kept on file in several locations in a fragmented manner. This data grows rapidly over time, making updating and accessing activities more difficult. Apart from security concerns, it is inconvenient (Mettler, 2016). Information on health is also exchanged among healthcare providers. When patients must go to several hospitals for treatment, it is necessary. It becomes increasingly difficult to achieve your goals. In addition, there is a need for integrated healthcare data management among hospitals, doctors, patients, medical labs, pharmaceutical manufacturers and insurance companies in different geographic locations (Dimiter, 2019). To overcome these challenges, new systems must be created with secure electronic health data, efficient storage and a proper and authenticated retrieval mechanism. In addition to the patient-provider relationship and access sharing (Shan *et al.*, 2018) with more relevance to patient-centric health data management, such a provision must protect patient privacy. Meanwhile, blockchain technology, which allows for secure transactions between network participants, has been used in EHRs in recent years. Blockchain technology, which is commonly associated with Bitcoin, involves the use of digital ledger systems with public-key cryptography to create unchangeable, time-stamped chains of health data (Chelladurai *et al.*, 2021).

This innovation brings unchanging nature and interoperability to every other established order for clinical offering frameworks and works with decentralization (Yue *et al.*, 2020). Blockchain, characterised as information in the form of blocks in a series of chains, is a duration-stepped collection of facts that can be permanent. Blockchain technology is a data storage structure that stores blocks of records and is often referred to as electronic ledger

technology. This information is thoroughly secured and far too difficult to alter (Chelladurai *et al.*, 2021). The block information is transparent because it may be accessed by other members of the network. The blockchain is made up of three different techniques: the use of cryptographic keys, a peer-to-peer network with a shared ledger and capabilities for storing block transaction records (Jin *et al.*, 2020).

The application of blockchain technology in the delivery of healthcare services has recently been a subject of intense research (Chelladurai *et al.*, 2021). One of the adopted blockchain technologies in healthcare is MIT's MedRec (Azaria and Lippman, 2016), which is considered to be a first-rate hospital treatment framework. MedRec is a blockchain primarily based on decentralized appropriated document innovation for sharing and keeping up with the sufferers' wellness facts. MedRec was created to address troubles involving community interoperability, admittance to medical records, affected person office, fractures and so on. It makes use of settlement calculation to test the proof of action. This shape supplies a stable approach for buying and selling the clinical offering records over a blockchain community. The MedRec software effectively maintains clinical offering records and offers accessibility, privacy and interoperability. A blockchain-designed healthcare platform used to secure the management of an EHRS was created by Do-Hyeun *et al.* (2019). It gave patients a complete, unchanging log and easy admittance to their medical records throughout diverse clinical settings. To test the framework, the creators conducted contextual research on a permissioned community.

2.3.4 Application of EHRS for Healthcare Research

International interest in the possibility of repurposing routinely gathered electronic hospital patient health records for clinical research is growing. This prospect is particularly appealing

in the pharmaceutical industry, which invests heavily in clinical trials and realises the potential for efficiency improvements and, as a result, a faster time-to-market for new drugs (Shah and Khan, 2020). The use of EHRs for research has become commonplace. The capacity to analyse real-world, real-patient outcomes in near-real-time is an apparent and unique benefit (Hammack-Aviran *et al.*, 2020). Analysing existing data, whether prospectively or retrospectively, is also less expensive and more convenient than developing a human-curated dataset. Future applications of EHRs in research appear to have almost limitless potential, especially as the types of data collected and the capacity to extract information from records are improved. In the burgeoning subject of radiomics, for example, technological advancements are allowing for the creation of new MRI sequences as well as the calculation of new quantitative features from images. Observational studies on drug consumption, natural history, risk factors, safety monitoring (i.e., post-marketing safety surveillance), regulatory work involving safety surveillance, pharmacovigilance (Cowie, *et al.*, 2017) and clinical research are all examples of current applications that include hypothesis generation, performance improvement, and comparative effectiveness (Kim *et al.*, 2019).

EHRs are gradually being changed and redesigned to increase the ease of research as the usage of EHR for research becomes increasingly common. The North American Association of Central Cancer's *Registries and Standards for Oncology* and *Registry Entry Standards*, which are used by national cancer registries, are being worked on, as are terminologies for semantic tagging and annotation, such as evidenced by *Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine: Clinical Terms*, *Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes*, and RxNorm. However, the lack of financial incentives for EHR suppliers and consumers has hampered the adoption of standards besides ICD-9/10 and CPT codes (Hernandez-Boussard *et al.*, 2018).

The main goal of clinical research is to use EHRs to plan and execute clinical trials for novel drugs (Coorevits *et al.*, 2013). The population has a direct correlation with health conditions. Healthcare institutions, hospitals and laboratories are now experiencing a lack of skilled medical personnel for a variety of reasons (Shah and Khan, 2020). Discovering new pharmaceuticals with improved results, as well as new procedures and robust strategies, is one feasible way to solve various medical problems. Clinical research is required for all these tasks. As a result, clinical research is critical in addressing some of the most pressing medical challenges.

2.4 Benefits of Electronic Health Record System Use

The four significant advantages of taking on EHRs over paper-based clinical records are cost savings, stockpiling, and improved security and ease of access (Yi, 2018). To begin with, overseeing EHRs requires less staff, and huge physical spaces are no longer required for record-keeping. Accordingly, it costs less to oversee and keep up with records with this strategy. Second, as the quantity of patients increases, the protection of records becomes an issue. Paper clinical records are printed on paper and regularly occupy enormous physical environments to be put away (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). They can also rot and be obliterated. EHRs, on the contrary, are not printed on paper and do not require enormous extra rooms. Third, EHRs can be put away in safe places like the cloud and can be observed for any dubious access while paper records are essentially put away in file organisers with relatively little security. The documents can be taken or harmed in catastrophic events such as fires and floods (Monegain, 2017). To be ready for any misfortune, we want to have reinforcements. With EHRs, we can easily make duplicates while paper records require copy reinforcements and the arrangement of the duplicates. At long last, to get to paper clinical records, they

should be sent or checked. Furthermore, email is occupying loads of time (Yi, 2018). In any case, the utilisation of EHRs permits clinical experts to get to the data they need immediately with the press of a button. Because time is basic in clinical settings, EHR use is more proficient when contrasted with paper record use. As of now, EHRs are utilised within individual healthcare organisations, and in their best integrated form in the UK, they are used within the NHS Trust, a network of hospitals and healthcare settings (Walker *et al.*, 2021). On the off chance that this electronic clinical data is shared, we cannot just use this clinical data to fix patients' sicknesses yet in addition for research or factual purposes (Tubaishat, 2019). With cutting-edge organisation and portable innovation, we can access EHRs and other clinical benefits from any place. The present organisations permit us to see superior-grade pictures of lab results and other wellbeing data and any time and place. Assets for the transmission of EHRs are promptly accessible (Alami *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, cell phones are generally utilised to make and share delicate healthcare information over remote connections.

Although hospitals and ambulatory care centres are rapidly embracing EHRs, the majority of user-level usage is still focused on billing. In the United States, the bulk of EHRs were built to assist in billing, with clinical workflow and research as secondary functions. In one single-centre study, most physicians accessed the EHR to enter data that was important for billing purposes (such as clinical documentation), but only a tiny minority altered issue lists, allergy lists or suggested modifications to the system (Kim *et al.*, 2019). Another researcher found that, despite significant heterogeneity in the number of providers that use EHR capabilities, such as clinical decision support tools, practically all clinical encounters meet meaningful use objective metrics, which are crucial for achieving optimal compensation. According to Tseng *et al.*, (2018) billing accounts for a large fraction of the entire time and financial cost of EHR-based encounters (up to 25% for emergency department contacts, for example). Because

diagnosis and procedure billing codes are frequently available for clinical encounters, they are reliable sources of data that may be extracted from EHRs.

The use of personal health information for purposes besides direct healthcare delivery, such as research and teaching, is referred to as the secondary use of EHRs (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). Ironically, the primary reason medical records were originally preserved was for didactic purposes, but this is now a so-called secondary use (Tsai *et al.*, 2020). Researchers can face medical, ethical, political, technological and social difficulties because the data was not intended for research uses and EHRs contain sensitive information. For example, we recently showed that private patient–provider and provider–provider communications in EHRs can be used to predict early treatment termination (Yin *et al.*, 2018). It is becoming increasingly important to address these challenges as the volume of and access to health data grows in both the public and private sectors. The American Medical Informatics Association (AMIA) released a white paper outlining the need for a framework for the secondary use of EHR data, as well as a data quality ontology based on Weiskopf’s elements of data quality (Kim *et al.*, 2019).

The number of secondary EHR applications is increasing at the same rate as the amount of data being collected. The first, and possibly most obvious, applications are automating routine clinical tasks. The usage of EHRs has made it easier than ever to collect and transfer a wide range of patient data, and it may even increase the ease of prospective data collection. Collection data in retrospect can be time-consuming and error-prone, and thus, may not be appropriate for clinical research. To better track outcomes, such as patient toxicity, EHRs can be linked to EHR tools (Alami *et al.*, 2020). Continuous heart rate monitoring, for example, could be used to track and diagnose dehydration caused by poor oral intake in head and neck

cancer patients receiving chemoradiation therapy, allowing for fast interventions and a reduction in the number of hospitalisations. The recent news that Fitbit data will be included in the data stream for the *all of us* initiative exemplifies the growth of such data “mash-ups” (National Institute of Health, 2019). Early initiatives to gather serial patient-reported outcomes and automatically record them in the EHRs have also been made (Kim *et al.*, 2019).

2.5 Challenges and Barriers to EHRs Implementation

The deployment of EHRs in healthcare facilities includes a number of hurdles. The key obstacles to the successful adoption of EHRs are provider engagement, administrative and policy support with commitment, and a lack of infrastructure (Endalew, 2020). Other hurdles to implementing EHRs include privacy, security, legal, and digital divide concerns. Because of the personal nature, importance and possible consequences of the malicious use of EHRs, health information privacy and security are receiving much attention. The unauthorized acquisition, disclosure, and/or secondary use of a person’s personally identifiable information, such as health information, violate that person’s privacy. Securing patients’ EHRs is a difficult issue in today’s interconnected digital environment. The security of EHRs is critical to providing patients and service providers confidence in their utilisation. Security flaws in healthcare companies can cause severe harm to both organisations and patients. In the worst-case scenario, an infiltrator’s unlawful access and purposeful modifications to patient medical records can result in death. Organisations must extensively assess the procedural and technological components of EHR security due to the substantial ramifications associated with EHR security breaches (Endalew, 2020). Concerning physical controls, the security plan for the company must meet the physical security demands of the whole network, from central data storage to the different desktop and mobile devices used by employees throughout the

firm. Access to work areas must be restricted to authorised workers, visitor access must be logged and data visibility on communication devices must be secured. Other essential issues include protecting mobile devices from theft, using secure virtual private networking from remote locations, and only allowing authorised workers to handle hardware and software. Healthcare facilities employ vendor-supplied gadgets and keep personal health information on them. As a result, organisations must implement controls to ensure vendor compliance, testing and an accurate record of device installation and removal on the facility network (Endalew, 2020). Figure 3 depicts some of the challenges associated with EHR adoption and utilisation reported in the research. Figure 2.1 depicts some of the challenges associated with EHR adoption and utilisation reported by Tsai *et al.* (2020).

Figure 2.1: Barriers to EHR uptake and utilisation on a mind map

Source: Tsai *et al.*, (2020)

End-user support: Poor and insufficient training, as well as a lack of technical and educational assistance for users have been mentioned as impediments to EHR and PHR adoption/use (Vehko *et al.*, 2019). One of the obstacles faced while using EHRs, according to clinicians and

staff, is a lack of awareness about EHR functions (Tsai *et al.*, 2020). The lack of user involvement during the design, development and deployment phases of the EHR and PHR system lifecycle (Priestman *et al.*, 2018) was also addressed. Users' literacy and technological and computing skills, such as typing and internet use skills, were reported to affect EHR and PHR adoption (O'Donnell, 2018).

EHRs: There were complaints about poor system compatibility and integration, which hampered both the deployment and adoption of EHRs (Al-Rawajfah and Tubaishat, 2019). Clinician resistance and lack of trust in EHRs regarding data privacy and the danger of data loss were identified as important hurdles to the full utilisation of EHRs. This was underlined in a study in which the author found that a lack of faith in the dependability of EHRs and a lack of belief in their benefit for patient care were viewed as impediments to EHRs implementation (Tsai *et al.*, 2020). Other EHRs complaints included system quality, system compatibility, system inefficiency (slow response), system failures, server crashes and difficulty locating EHRs that meet demands (Raglan *et al.*, 2017). Functionality difficulties with EHRs were cited as impediments to their utilisation, including too many complex capabilities and too few needed functions. Usability elements, such as user interface design and navigation, were all acknowledged to be important.

Information and Data: Clinicians and patients have expressed concerns about the privacy and security of data and information in EHRs (Keshta and Odeh, 2021). In a survey, one-third of physicians expressed concern regarding the privacy of patient data in EHRs in the event of illegal leakages. Providers have expressed concerns regarding improper and illegal access to the sensitive information contained in PHRs, such as mental health information (Kariotis and Harris, 2019). Patients/consumers were also concerned about the privacy, security and

confidentiality issues associated with the use of EHRs while physicians were concerned about the quality of patient-generated data in EHRs. There have been reports of data and information in PHRs generating anxiety in patients when misconstrued (Tsai *et al.*, 2020). Clinicians also stated that allowing patients with psychiatric problems access to their medical records in EHRs would be problematic (Kariotis and Harris, 2019).

Other challenges and barriers to the implementation and adoption of EHRs were reported, including the high cost of system upgrades and maintenance, inadequate funding, time constraints, limited access to computers, limited networks (internet) and an insufficient number of user licences (Greysen *et al.*, 2020). Concerns about the legal liabilities involved in the storage of medical records in EHRs/PHRs have also been expressed. There was mention of a lack of administrative and policy support, as well as a lack of understanding that could stymie the successful adoption and usage of PHRs (Khan *et al.*, 2018).

According to Scheibner *et al.*, (2021), EHRs obstacles are classified into five categories: implementation, legal and ethical issues, data-related issues, engagement issues and software-related issues, as shown in Figure 2.2 below.

Figure 2.2: Sunburst diagram depicting EHRS problems and subcategories based on the number of segments.

Source: Scheibner *et al.*, 2021 Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Conflicting stakeholder requirements (Klecun *et al.*, 2019), difficulty establishing benefits (Severinsen *et al.*, 2019), financial issues, government, policy, and political issues and larger implementation challenges were the most common implementation challenges. There were also many legal and ethical issues to deal with. Concerns regarding privacy and research ethics were the most often expressed (Keshta and Odeh, 2021). Concerning the latter, Keshta and Odeh (2021) alluded to issues like ethical committee approvals, assuring representative samples, disclosing results, preserving patients' rights and consent/re-consent processes, among others.

Patient autonomy, or the right of patients to make decisions about their medical care and general health, is another key concern. Patient autonomy, in this context, alludes to patients' ability to regulate access to their EHRs, as well as whether an opt-in or opt-out consent was

preferable (Moats and McFall, 2019). Aside from that, three types of medical responsibility have been recognised. These included physician and healthcare organisation liability for providing proper medical care, eHealth system equipment or product liability and patients' responsibility for their health records (Mitchell and Ploem, 2018). First, there were issues with assuring data availability, which included being able or ready to exchange data with other hospitals, healthcare organisations or research institutions (Kariotis and Harris, 2019). The challenge of transferring data across national or international borders, for example, was a jurisdictional issue. Issues with the availability of various data types, such as metadata and data linking, occurred. The second data difficulty was information quality, which refers to records and information that are of poor quality, missing or lost. The third data barrier was interoperability, which was limited to the use of disparate standards (Fragidis and Chatzoglou, 2018). Similarly, the adoption of "silo" or free-text systems was argued to stifle the free exchange of data (Severinsen *et al.*, 2019).

Another significant problem is stakeholder engagement. The first problem is a lack of interest. There is a dearth of patient participation, which jeopardised the utilisation of patient data for secondary research (shah and khan, 2020). Physicians would also refuse to utilise the systems because they do not trust them or had bad experiences with them, and software was widely blamed for physician burnout. As a result, the potential benefits of these technologies would be limited (Scheibner *et al.*, 2021). The lack of access to the benefits of the use of eHealth systems, such as from geographically remote places and underdeveloped countries, as well as communication challenges, impacted involvement.

Finally, technological difficulties with the systems themselves have been recognised. Security issues were the most common, and they included issues with security measures, such as role-

based access control and information security (Keshta and Odeh, 2021). Furthermore, these difficulties were linked to broader ethical and legal considerations concerning patient autonomy and privacy and found to affect physician–patient interactions (Ballantyne and Stewart, 2019).

2.6 Sustainable (i.e. Continuously Maintained) EHR Implementation.

Sustainable Electronic Health Records System (EHR) implementation refers to the continuous maintenance and improvement of the system throughout its lifecycle to ensure its long-term success and effectiveness. It involves a well-planned and ongoing process that focuses on various key aspects to maximize the benefits of EHR and address challenges that may arise during and after implementation. Elements of sustainable EHR implementation are thus discussed:

Comprehensive Planning: Sustainable EHR implementation begins with thorough planning. This includes conducting a comprehensive needs assessment, defining clear objectives, and engaging stakeholders from different departments within the healthcare organization. (Ge, et al., 2022). A well-designed implementation plan considers the organization's existing workflows and processes, ensuring a seamless integration of the EHR into daily operations.

User Training and Support: Effective training and support for end-users are crucial for successful EHR implementation and sustained adoption. Continuous training ensures that healthcare professionals are proficient in using the system and can leverage its full capabilities. Ongoing support mechanisms, such as help desks or dedicated support teams, assist users in resolving issues and answering questions, fostering user confidence and acceptance (Woldemariam and Jimma, 2023).

Continuous System Updates: Technology and healthcare practices are constantly evolving. Sustainable EHR implementation requires a commitment to continuous system updates and enhancements. Regular software updates address bugs, security vulnerabilities, and optimize system performance. Additionally, updates should reflect changes in regulatory requirements and industry standards.

Performance Monitoring and Evaluation: Monitoring the EHR performance is crucial for sustainable implementation. Data analytics and user feedback can provide valuable insights into system usage patterns and areas for improvement. Regular evaluations help identify bottlenecks, inefficiencies, and usability issues, enabling organizations to make informed decisions for system optimization.

Scalability and Flexibility: As healthcare organizations grow and evolve, the EHR must be scalable and flexible to accommodate changing needs. A sustainable EHR implementation considers future requirements and ensures the system can adapt and grow with the organization. (Sterrett et al., 2022).

Sustainable EHR implementation is a dynamic and ongoing process that requires careful planning, continuous training, robust security measures, and a commitment to continuous improvement. By addressing these key elements, healthcare organizations can maximize the benefits of EHR, deliver better patient care, and foster a culture of innovation and efficiency in healthcare delivery.

2.7 Evolution of Electronic Health Records in the United Kingdom

In 1968, the use of computers became generally adopted in the NHS as an aftermath of the introduction of an initiative called the NHS Experimental Computer Program. This further gave rise to a pioneering database system and a preceding methodology (i.e., a prototype) used in

one of the hospitals in the capital (Wienroth *et al.*, 2019). Between 1980 and 1990, there was a significant increase in the formation, development and adaptation of relevant policies for NHS information technology systems. This was initiated by the insightful and cutting-edge publications of the Resource Management Initiative (RMI) in 1986, the 1982 Korner Report and the Griffiths Report of 1984. The RMI was aimed at availing hospital management and health practitioners' access to information through state-of-the-art technology, which in turn, required them to provide enormous data on hospital performance and cost to appropriate authorities and governments (Lampon and McKeivitt, 2020). Due to the cumbersome and hectic mode of RMI operation, a scheme was put in place that permitted each hospital to create a suitable computerised information system customised to meet its needs. This scheme helped each hospital adequately compile patients activity data from an existing patient administration system (PAS). Through the PAS, much other relevant information was readily accessible for proper and meaningful use. Following this development, the Hospital Episode Statistics database used by the Department of Health specifically for the analysis of inpatients was created in 1987 (Glaser, 2020). The RMI was grossly unsuccessful in furnishing a holistic system. Hence, the Hospital Information Support System was initiated to achieve an entire consolidation of the PAS and make seamless information sharing and interaction between IT applications possible by the end of the millennium (i.e., by 2000).

The information management and technology (IM&T) guidelines to be adopted and implemented by the Department of Health were rolled out in 1992 and recommended that information should be individual-oriented, highly confidential and safe and obtained from fully functional and integrated operational systems to communicate and transfer data and information across and within the length and breadth of the NHS. The IM&T guideline was introduced because the RMI was assumed to have achieved its goal even before the

publication of a comprehensive review. There was also criticism about embarking on such a massive and financially enormous project due to the unproductivity caused by former and foregoing policies. Six years after launching, the IM&T policy was amended and improved with a stressed significance and priority on integrated systems. Furthermore, Information for Health (IFH) set out goals to ensure the EHRs of patients are adequately kept throughout their lifespans and easily accessible and transferrable around the clock among NHS General Practitioners and Hospitals by 2005. This decision led to the investment of about 500 million in triune key aspects that include local or national applications, electronic health libraries and other information services and, lastly, intra-organisational and inter-organisational electronic records. In 2002, the National Program for IT was published. It was acclaimed to be the most expensive IT project to be embarked upon by the government of the UK (Arabella *et al.*, 2016). This was a result of the insignificant achievement of the IFH in the implementation of EHRs locally (Department of Health and Social Care, 2018). The initiative for a national IT program was solely focused on achieving one EHR suited for all patients through a strategic central system pitched and controlled at the national level. This system was envisioned to take effect by 2010. With this system in place, a high degree of independence and self-government in the implementation and operation of EHRs was attained by NHS hospitals, but there was a drastic impact on the system because there was insufficient system delivery (Cresswell *et al.*, 2020). The shortcomings of past policies, concerning the ambiguity of timelines, which often seem to be unrealistic, the Department of Health developed a framework that is to be implemented over 10 years. This framework is targeted at transforming the face of information use throughout the entire scope of social care and healthcare in the country. It was meant to be achieved through countrywide measures, including leadership resolution and localised means of funding, implementation, responsibility, planning, prioritisation and

market-based solutions (Department of Health, 2012). Following an evaluation by the Major Project Authority (MJA) in 2013, which showed that the National Program for Information Technology (NPfIT), it was found that the framework was not fit for its purpose and had failed to achieve the goal for which it was created. Hence, it was dissolved (Major Project Authority, 2011). The NHS was later poised to be a paperless organisation by 2018 by the then Secretary of State for Health (Illman and Hunt, 2013). As a result of this proposition, NHS England proposed a policy to lead the campaign for an Integrated Digital Care Record (IDCR) with a systematic structure of planning for gradual transformation from a full and heavy paper form of operation to light paper use and eventually a paperless system of keeping records. A sum of 500 million was earmarked to drive and fund this vision (NHS England, 2013). In 2014, a publication was released that highlighted and focused on a vision of attaining personalised healthcare by 2020. It made a strategic framework available to help NHS personnel explore and maximise the advantages of the benefits that digital revolution has to offer. The detailed step-by-step process was not the focus of this publication. The publication reiterates the emphasis. The Secretary for the State for Health stated that by 2020, all NHS must have gone paperless. This policy was geared towards real-time access to electronic records by NHS staff by 2020 (Department of Health, 2014). National standard and security, NHS number, confidentiality frameworks, Hospital Episode Statistics (HES), NHSnet and PAS were all frameworks, databases and infrastructures initiated and implemented by the NHS at different points over a period of 24 years, starting from 1968. The policies, however, faced criticism for their unrealistic optimism, ambiguity of vision, limited guidelines and prioritising and focusing on the technological and technical area of implementation at the expense of ignoring equally important change management aspects in the implementation strategy (Wainwright and Waring, 2000). Contrary to the vision of actualising an electronic record system that is

integrated and at the national level, the deficiency of guidance, inadequacies of frameworks and isolated or individualistic systems of approach were recommended in the IM&T policy of 1992. This resulted in a series of disintegrated systems in the NHS because each organisation embarked on developing self-customised EHRs.

The IFH has no procedure or methodology that dictates or guides the execution of EHRs. This is because the NHS is new to this initiative, and this has never been done within its organisation. The resolve and conclusion of the NPfIT to facilitate the use of a centralized system were because some industries have adopted such stratagem with undeniable success and effectiveness. Also, many other IT projects in the NHS that involved the use of local methods led to isolated systems of operation with an inability to communicate, transfer and disperse information to others and, hence, made achievements below the desired and expected results. Notwithstanding all these factors, the review of the National Project for Information Technology and the IFH has condemned and disapproved of the centralized method of EHR implementation for being a major contributor to its unsuccessful quest. The NPfIT and IFH assessment rendered insufficient recommendations and regulations on future strategies and approaches to the implementation of EHRs. This is evident in the policy presently adopted because it has unelaborated guidance. The suppliers of EHRs and contract management also contributed to the compounding effect that led to unproductivity and the frustration of the vision set out by NPfIT. While the NPfIT program was being implemented, there were severe delays in effecting the EHRs as a result of technical faults in the system of operation, coupled with the limitations of NHS hospitals to customise, modify and localise central systems that were already in place. Hence, the initial strategy for implementing a centralized national process was reviewed and discontinued to give accommodation localised processes. This enabled the local trust to have a system of self-governance concerning the

cost implication, performance and operation of electronic records. The inability to meet the targeted deadline in actualising the EHR program and a major setback resulted in the re-bargaining of the terms of engagement between the Department of Health and the contractors for the EHRs. The renegotiation affected the initial number of EHRs that was planned to be delivered because it was cut back. However, it had no impact on cost implications. The cost of delivering the system remained unchanged. The resolution to drive the project through three major electronic record contractors was further applauded and reinforced due to the merits of fostering competition, cost-effectiveness and increased chances of yielding immense productivity. Despite the recognised advantages, the analyses and evaluations carried out by the NPfIT indicated a series of demerits, such as impediments to the development and evolution of future systems, the restraint of the contractor market and unprecedented cost hikes. The HER projects issued by the Npfit to contractors were largely faulted and maligned to involve high degrees of risk. This was gross because, at the time of signing off on the project and reaching a mutual agreement with contractors, the EHRs had not yet taken full shape because it was still an idea in its infancy. To mitigate the imminent and associated risks, certain measures were formulated and implemented to ensure the contractors were thorough and diligent. These measures included the requirement that contractors will pay a sum between £50 million and £500 million to the government if they fail to deliver as expected. Also, payment for services will be rendered after the project is fully delivered and set in motion. Another measure was ensuring contractors were to incur any additional costs if the project exceeded the established targets and deadlines. In addition, a systematic change measure was installed to ensure the Department of Health did not bear the burden of any form of payment or expenditure should the project change hands. The NPfIT aimed to pay back the sum paid by contractors with interest if they failed in the project,

as long as the failure was fully ameliorated within three months of the initial end date. This, however, seems counterproductive because contractors could exploit this avenue as a means of gain and could result in deliberate negligence, seeing that it is rewardable.

2.7.1 Failure of the National Programme for IT on Electronic Record Systems

In 2002, the NPfIT in the NHS was inaugurated with a financial estimate of approximately £6 billion by the UK government. This funding is geared towards achieving centralized and holistic digital transformation in NHS England. NPfIT's fundamental goal was to optimise the operability and applicability of IT in the NHS through the development of a unified EHRS for patients and by improving the systems of information use in the NHS, thereby fostering service enhancement and refining the quality of care received by patients. The programme was not well received by medical practitioners and seems to have no effect on the safety of healthcare recipients. There was intense resistance to the programme because of lack of adequate and the uninformed decision-making processes of top management affected the organisations at the lowest levels of the management structure (Cresswell *et al.*, 2020). After nine years of a tumultuous adventure, the National Program for IT was finally dissolved. Acclaimed to be the most prodigious information technology programme in the world, its grand failure could not go unnoticed and never without concerns that raised pertinent and curious questions about the root cause of its fatal debacle. In this thesis, a detailed examination of the root causes of NPfIT failure will be outlined. These causes include the misjudgement and undervaluation of the project scope, the lack of a change management strategy and inadequacy in the involvement of end-users (Arabella *et al.*, 2016).

The implementation of information technology initiatives in the healthcare sector is often carried out on a small scale at a level that can be easily controlled (i.e., execution is usually

first pioneered in one NHS Trust or organisation before it is reproduced on a wide scale). Regardless of this measure, the difficulties encountered are usually enormous. Hence executing the same project on an extensive or comprehensive scale certainly usually leads to the escalation of inherent setbacks. Considering the intricacies of operations in NHS organisations, the complications become overbearing. Numerous, IT projects in the NHS are carried out on a large scale, always wide-ranging at the regional or even national levels (NHS England, 2019). These projects are often flawed and ruined, despite the huge amounts of money often invested in them. Despite the lack of comprehensive knowledge on the root causes of the failure that keeps undermining the desired progress, huge amounts of money are still being pumped into these projects (Kaipio *et al.*, 2020). Each passing year of the implementation of these large-scale schemes results in excess overrunning estimate at a rate of 15% rise. However, there is still limited insight into and understanding of how to achieve an organisational change of such magnitude in the NHS. Additionally, along with project delays, an overriding information technology that is highly sophisticated due to continual and ongoing research and development in the technology industry is developed. It is noteworthy that accomplishing an IT task of such enormous magnitude in the health sector is more about the people than the technology. Sparingly, just 1/3 of IT-related NHS projects have successful outcomes (Department of Health and Social Care, 2018). Also, to achieve the goals of information technology projects in healthcare, an organisational culture that imbibes change management must be strongly upheld. There have been speculations that social, behavioural and cultural factors in the administration and execution of NHS information technology projects are crucial and technological and engineering-related factors and can be even more paramount. Unarguably, the introduction of a digitized system of healthcare will, evidently, impact the operations and processes of service delivery, as well as radically change the *modus*

operandi of traditional standards of procedure. Hence, the ability to alter the organisational culture within the trust where it is being implemented is inherent in EHRs.

Table 2.2: NPfIT number of delivered systems with their corresponding values.

Region	Supplier	System Delivered	Contract value
North, Midlands and East	CSC	56/90 community care trusts 10/97 acute trusts 0/35 mental health trusts 80 interim systems delivered but not replaced	£105million for interim systems original contract £3.1billion for delivery of care record systems to 220 trusts Expected to cost £2.2billion despite issues
South	Fujitsu, BT replaced Fujitsu after contract termination	23/25 community and mental health trusts 7 acute trusts BT to deliver 35 original systems	Fujitsu terminated the BT London contract extended £454million (£214million BT £151million to Fujitsu)
London	BT	All 37 community and mental health trusts received the system. Half acute trusts (number not specified)	£444million Original cost increase from £65 to £85million Contract extended at cost of £546million

Source: Arabella *et al.*, (2016)

At the inception of the NPfIT, the government flagged eight substantially stupendous and state-of-the-art information technology projects. A whopping amount of funding was allotted to the projects to transform the NHS England, which is deemed to be the largest government-

controlled organisation in all of Europe. In the public sector of the United Kingdom, an undertaking of this size and magnitude was clearly unprecedented (Watchter, 2016).

Figure 2.3: Regional Divisions and their respective suppliers

Source: Watchter, 2016

2.7.2 HIT Development in the UK Over Time

Takian *et al.* (2012) observed how policy context can be altered during the course of a single long-term transformation initiative. As a result of these circumstances, many stakeholders may end themselves pursuing moving targets and scope creep. The economic recession of 2008–2013, for example, had a significant impact on the English NPfIT, resulting in a shortage of long-term funding (Cresswell *et al.*, 2020). Shifting socio-political situations are crucial, but they are only one part of the story. A long-term perspective on nurturing developing infrastructures reveals that best practices inevitably shift over time (Aanestad *et al.*, 2017). They also frequently lack a clear endpoint, and there is not always agreement on strategic direction. We discussed this before in the context of digital maturity, which is a hotly debated

topic (Cresswell *et al.*, 2019). Different types of program management and evaluation tools that take this type of evolution into account may be required. These could include a focus on flexibility and reflexivity, thus enabling decision-makers to change plans and roadmaps in response to changing demands and surroundings. This strategy will also necessitate learning from history and drawing on the vast knowledge of people who have first-hand experience with comparable initiatives. Available technologies are affected by changes in medical procedures and diagnostics, care delivery models and vendor offerings (and vice versa). Because the market may not be able to rapidly adapt to new policy-driven models, these characteristics must be considered in evaluations and policies (Mozaffar *et al.*, 2015). This could entail looking into changing vendor-user relationships, user group emergence and mobilisation, procurement frameworks and market diversity (Mozaffar, 2016). Our research, for example, demonstrates that, as a result of the English NPfIT, international mega-suite solutions centred on core EHR technologies are progressively dominating the UK market. These solutions provide a rather well-established and trustworthy path to digital maturity and interoperability. The alternate option entails stitching together EHRs with a variety of additional vendor-provided features. This may have the advantage of allowing an adopter to create a best-of-breed (BoB) solution that is unique to each local environment and, hence, better suited to local organisations (Cresswell *et al.*, 2020). Vendors that provide modular solutions for BoB, on the contrary, face challenges entering the market and developing interfaces. Existing EHR providers are struggling to update their systems into mega-packages. Interoperability problems and innovation potential provided by disparate systems must be carefully considered by implementers. Programs must guarantee that procurement practices promote (or at the very least, do not stifle) a thriving marketplace.

CHAPTER THREE—THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Introduction

This chapter contains a comprehensive description of the theoretical framework of this study. The framework formulated in this chapter was developed through a detailed examination, review and evaluation of vital concepts and phenomena. Hence, this chapter contains the results of an evaluation of relevant theories, such as the TAM, organisational performance management, organisational culture theories and change management theories. The frameworks currently used in the implementation of EHRs and HIT in general are critically evaluated in this chapter. Furthermore, this chapter contains a description of how the proposed framework was derived. The contents of the proposed framework are carefully highlighted and explained in the chapter, along with the validation of the rationale behind them. This chapter ends with the conclusion of the whole study.

3.2 Relevant Theories

There are important studies on theories and models that are relevant to this study and were carefully considered and analysed and comprehensively presented. I analysed Rogers' (2003) Innovation Diffusion Theory. The major models examined include change management theories, such as Lewin's (1947) change model, Kotter's (1996) change management model and the TAM. Change management can be referred to as a method of guiding personnel, departments or organisations to change from an existing condition or situation to a desired condition for the achievement of a goal. It is the definition and adaptation of plans, design, technology and methodologies to combat the change caused by internal and external factors (Change Management Survey Report, 2007). The need for the achievement of successful change management, especially to weather the storm of a depressive economy, is crucial for

many organisations (Ashurst and Hodges, 2010). Information Technology has become extremely invaluable to business operations in all organisations. It is central to driving and fostering business creativity and innovation and has formed one of the bases upon which strategy formulation and decision-making processes are pitched. The constant evolution of information technology encourages organisations to adopt survival mechanisms to survive and remain relevant in their respective industries, hence the need for change and a system of management for change. Organisational change has become inherently inevitable and highly crucial to the goals and objectives of organisations. According to the Information Technology Infrastructure Library, change is the act of transferring from one set form to another (Hussein *et al.*, 2013). To achieve the successful adoption and implementation of change, diverse change management models have been developed.

3.2.1 Innovation Diffusion Theory

Rogers *et al.*'s (2019) Innovation Diffusion Theory focuses on the acceptance and adoption of a new technology in any field and comprehending the proliferation of such technology within a given populace. This theory describes innovation as a concept, procedure or technology that is considered to be foreign or unknown by a group of people in a social setting. However, according to Roger *et al.* (2019), *innovation* is synonymous with *technology*, and in his work and research, *innovation* is often used interchangeably with *technology*. Hence, innovation diffusion theory can be understood as technology diffusion theory. The most suitable theory for the examination of technological adoption is innovation diffusion theory (Breaugh *et al.*, 2021). Diffusion can be defined as the process involved in the dissemination or spreading of the knowledge about an innovation to a group of individuals over a period in a system of communal structure (Zhang *et al.*, 2015). In healthcare settings, diffusion can be referred to

as a social process of conveyance, teaching and sensitizing clinicians concerning the HIT for improved service delivery (Dearing and Cox, 2018).

In innovation diffusion theory, there are four major elements critical to the success of technology adoption. They include innovation attributes, channels of communication, time and social system.

- **Innovation Attributes:** A concept or information technology may be considered new not as a result of time but as a result of the awareness of its existence. A technology may have been innovated for a long time, but that does not mean it is not new. However, to an individual or a group of people who are being introduced to or encountering the technology for the first time, it is new; it is an innovation. There are five important attributes of innovation: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). Compatibility refers to the extent to which a technological innovation aligns with the values, culture, experiences and end-users' needs in the existing social system. An innovation that strongly aligns with existing values peculiar to a social system can be easily and smoothly adopted (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). Complexity encapsulates the extent to which an innovation is considered herculean or complicated to comprehend, execute or engage. A technology that is well understood and user-friendly will be more readily adopted than one with many complexities. Trialability is the extent to which a technological innovation can be tested or examined with little, or no risk involved. Observability is a measure of the degree to which the advantage of an innovation is noticeable, especially by the intended users.

- **Communication channels:** This is one of the diffusion elements that involve the transmission of messages for common understanding. A means of communication is referred to as diffusion when the message being transmitted concerns a new concept or technological innovation (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). *Communication channel* can, therefore, be defined as the medium or means through which certain individuals or groups of people acquire knowledge regarding a technological innovation and its perceived usefulness. The main communication channels in innovation diffusion theory are interpersonal communication and mass media communication channels (Pinho *et al.*, 2021). Interpersonal communication channels are mediums of communication between two or more individuals. They are the channels for personal means of communication that entails one-on-one contact or face-to-face engagement (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). Mass media communication channels involve the use of general and widespread communication channels, such as newspapers, magazines, television, radio and even social media platforms.
- **Time:** This is an extremely important element in innovation diffusion theory. Little emphasis has been placed on the time factor in behavioural science studies, and little research has been carried out on its impact and significance in technological innovation and adoption (Breugh *et al.*, 2021). However, in innovation diffusion theory, the impact of time is examined and detailed in the rate of adoption of technology and the decision-making of an innovation process. The variable of time has been recognised as a strength of innovation diffusion (Horn, 2021).
- **Social System:** This is described as a set of interconnected contingents embarking on a solution-oriented task to accomplish a unanimous objective (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). Diffusion of innovation takes place in a social system. This may be a university, a

church, a hospital or the healthcare sector in general, which is the main domain of this study. A social system consists of groups of individuals, teams or units with diverse attributes but bound together by a common goal. A social system often has a built-in structure, and this structure influences the attitudes of members of the social system towards a new concept of technology and further affects the adoption rate of such innovations (Kaan, 2021).

According to Rogers *et al.* (2019), there are five different types of adopters. This classification is based on the level of the measure of how quickly or early an individual or group of people adopts an innovation compared to other members in a social system in which an innovation is introduced. The adopters can be classified as venturesome, respectable, deliberate, sceptical and traditional.

- **Venturesome–Innovator:** These are adopters who constitute a few percentages of the population of a social system (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). They are enthusiastic and eagerly embrace new ideas, concepts or technologies. They are often in contact with the external environment of the social system to which they belong and are often antagonized by other members of the social system for their external alliance (Diamond, 2019). They are driven towards trying out new things. They are quite adventurous, and their risk appetite is high. Innovators are often the brains behind an innovation (Wang *et al.*, 2020). Other members of the social system are usually introduced to an innovation by innovators. They spearhead change and are major change agents considered to be major catalysts in diffusion processes (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). Innovators must be ready to embrace the failure of innovations they initiate and must be self-motivated to drive an innovation towards a desired change. They are

often equipped with the ability to interpret and engage technical and complex knowledge that other members of the social system lack.

- **Respectable–Early Adopters:** These are members of the social system who are well respected and esteemed by others. They have keen insight and the ability to recognise the benefits of innovations initiated by the venturesome beyond that of other members of the social system (Palm, 2020). Early adopters quickly gravitate towards innovators to take maximum advantage of their innovations and be the first partakers in the initiative. They are often economically fit to bear the financial burden of an innovation (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). They also have the right connections to make resources abound towards an innovation. They have reputable statuses and are recognised as leaders with capabilities to influence other members of the social system (Graziano *et al.*, 2019). They are responsible for eliminating doubts and fears regarding an innovation by adopting, evaluating and communicating the consequence of their adoption to others within the social system.
- **Deliberate–Early majority:** These are members of the social system that are result-oriented. They will not embrace an innovation until it has been proven to deliver on its promises. They often wait for the early adopters to endorse an innovation before they adopt it (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). They are recognised and well-integrated into the social system. However, they are not leaders. They will not be among the first set of individuals to adopt an innovation or among the last group of people to embrace it (Overby and Ransbotham, 2019). They wait a bit before making a decision regarding an innovation. They follow trends and engage an innovation when it has become generally acclaimed and widely accepted.

- **Sceptical–Late Majority:** These are the members of the social system who approach an innovation with extreme caution. They often lack self-motivation or natural interest in an innovation. They are usually sceptical and have a great deal of doubt and uncertainty regarding new concepts or technologies (Rogers *et al.*, 2019). Hence, they stand aloof and observe innovations from afar. They have little or no appetite for risk. They cannot accommodate the idea that an innovation has a risk involved, regardless of how much the advantage outweighs the demerits (Kumar and Alok, 2020). They will rather fixate on the insignificant risk than focus on the enormous advantage an innovation offers (Moon *et al.*, 2021). They often adopt a technology due to pressure, fear of being excluded from the use of an innovation and external motivation from other members of the social system.
- **Laggard–Traditional:** These are members of the social system with a high degree of criticism for an innovation. Their resistance to change is rigid and difficult to influence. While other members of the social system are looking ahead and focusing on possibilities the future holds, laggards strongly fixate on experience and remain attached to existing systems or old methods and approaches (Blythe, 2020). They are critical of innovations, especially disruptive ones, and often uphold the past as their point of reference and paradigm for decision-making. They may never adopt an innovation or eventually adopt a change when it has already outlived its course and been succeeded by a new idea or technology (Mallison, 2020).

Figure 3.1: Adopter categories in a social system

Source: Rogers et al. 2019 Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

According to Rogers *et al.* (2019), innovation diffusion theory, though detailed, comprehensive and uncomplicated to apply, has been criticised by many authors as having major limitations. In its original ideology at inception, innovation diffusion theory was considered to be obsolete and unfit for use in innovative technology in recent times which are highly disruptive and characterised by a high degree of sophistication (Sima *et al.*, 2020). The adopter category has been criticised as no longer relevant in recent times. Hence, there are calls for the redefinition and recategorization of diffusion adopters. The categorisation of adopters was based on agricultural technological innovations, hence the need for a new categorisation that is holistic and more relevant to 21st-century technological innovations (Zohuri, 2020). The rapid development and advancement of technology in recent times made innovation diffusion more complex and heterogeneous. This intricate convolution and matrix systems have not been captured in the innovation diffusion theory (Wang *et al.*, 2020). According to Wood (2017), innovation diffusion theory has failed to consider the fluctuating dynamics and market segment variation that occur over a given period. Greater emphasis is placed on the technology rather than the stakeholders who will engage the innovation and whose needs change with time.

3.2.2 Lewin's (1947) Change Theory

Lewin's (1947) change model has been widely accepted, adopted and implemented across all spheres of the business environment and organisations. It has been used by researchers to study and scrutinize organisational change management across different industries and climes (Santhidran *et al.*, 2013). It has further been used to drive change management, even in the education sector (Azni, 2015). In his theory, Kurt Lewin stated that employee perspectives, beliefs and inclinations can be hugely impacted and influenced by changes within an organisation (Norhayati *et al.*, 2017). This change model presents vital phases for the smooth and systematic implementation of a desired change. It describes the crucial factors necessary to sustaining the existing conditions and promoting change. To facilitate change in an existing condition, it is important that factors for driving change be optimised or factors that contribute to the sustenance of existing situations be minimised. Also, both forces could be amalgamated for a response and pre-emptive change within an organisation through effective leadership that fosters knowledge sharing (Syed *et al.*, 2016). The stages involved in Kurt Lewin's model are unfreezing, transition and freezing.

Figure 3.2: Lewin's (1947) Change Model

Source: Researcher

The unfreezing stage, which is the first step in Lewin's (1947) model can be described as the phase that involves dissolving all forms of existing structures or conditions. It is the process of gradually and systematically disintegrating the status quo with careful consideration of the

sentiments that might have been long attached to the current ways of doing things (Hassan, 2018). This is because the existing systems of operations currently engaged within an organisation form the basis upon which actions are carried out, decisions are made, and strategies are formed (Hussain *et al.*, 2018). It is, therefore, important to weaken the forces and factors that drive the sustenance of the status quo. Employee beliefs, attitudes and behaviours that have been profoundly influenced by the organisational culture need to be subjected to a paradigm shift, and the organisation will need to appeal to the perspectives of the employees to ensure the productive unlearning of existing processes (Memon *et al.*, 2021). The lack of adequate and proper planning for the implementation of the unfreezing phase will ultimately frustrate the goal of the change process. This is because many stakeholders within the organisation will pose major resistance to the desired change intended by the organisation. The unfreezing phase will help prepare stakeholders, especially employees, willingly embrace the change and motivate them by involving and engaging them in the process of the planned change (Saleem *et al.*, 2019).

The second phase is the transition or movement phase. This is the stage in which actual change implementation takes place, strategies are executed, and restructurings are carried out with required tools and techniques (Akkaya *et al.*, 2021). Knowledge sharing and effective leadership are critical at this stage. Knowledge sharing is pivotal to the relationships among employees within an organisation (Lindorfer, 2021). The training and development of staff within an organisation should not be the only means of improving organisational performance and facilitating change. Knowledge sharing is a major means of achieving this (Dege, 2019). Knowledge sharing among staff on tasks and projects, technological innovation and creativity, standard operation procedures, performance improvement, idea generation and expertise and skills will help people achieve successful feats in the transition phase of change

management (Crosby 2020). It is fundamentally a learning process that helps employees develop whether from an experienced individual to an apprentice or among groups and teams within an organisation, the knowledge being shared among employees to facilitate change could either be tacit (i.e., skills, expertise and experience) or explicit (i.e., written forms in documents, manuals and even training materials) (Memon *et al.*, 2020). In the transition phase of Lewin's model, this knowledge can be codified (i.e., it can be archived in a database that can be accessed by authorised individuals). It is often explicit in nature. The knowledge can also be personalised (i.e., conveyed from one employee to another), and it is usually in tacit form.

The third stage of Lewin's (1947) change model is called the refreezing stage. This is the stage of stabilizing the newly implemented reformation, rendering it congruent and as fool-proof as possible from disintegration and retrogressing into the previous state of things before the introduction of change (Saleem *et al.*, 2019). It is often initiated after the new change has been fully saturated and engaged by all stakeholders to a certain desired level, at a point where employee beliefs, behaviours, perspectives and paradigm have been fully shifted to accommodate the desired change (Memon *et al.*, 2021). This often results in redefining organisational culture and, in some instances, the implementation of new measures for employees and organisational performance management. The third phase of Lewin's (1947) model often takes a considerable time before being introduced. It can, therefore, be noticed that Lewin's (1947) change model follows a sequence of transitions from a fixed state to a process of metamorphosis and then again to a coherent fixed state (Archer *et al.*, 2019).

This model has been strongly criticised as only being applicable to organisations that are mechanical, fixed and facile in their operations. It makes change management seem more

simplistic than it is (Hussein *et al.*, 2013). Lewin's (1947) change model is practicable and simple in theoretical terms. However, in practice, it lacks the element of realism. This model considers change to be sequential and linearly progressive, which is often not the situation in many change management efforts, especially in more complex organizational systems (Bartunek and Woodman, 2015). It has also been criticised for the phenomenon of freezing because organisational changes are rather continuous and unceasing (Ratana *et al.*, 2020)

3.2.3 Kotter's (1996) Change Model

Kotter's (1996) change model is one of the most reputable change management models. It is generally and popularly acknowledged. In the mobilisation and implementation of organisational transformation, Kotter's (1996) change model has proven to be efficient and effective (Caulfield and Brenner, 2020). It is renowned as the most convincing and captivating change management technique with a high success rate (Odiaga *et al.*, 2021). It has gained a reputation as a major conventional and astute means for leading sustainable change management (Carpenter *et al.*, 2021). Top management and leaders in organisations have held Kotter's (1996) model in high esteem and engaged and adopted it in their change management projects (Purnell *et al.*, 2020). Although this model has been heavily criticised for lacking a scientific and empirical basis, it has proven to be business inclined and suitable for change implementation in organisations. It has further seen enormous success in academic environments, even though its formulation and postulation lacked an academic background (i.e., could not be academically substantiated) (Mohteshamuddin and Mohiuddin, 2020). Kotter's (1996) model contains eight steps of organisational transformation, as shown in Figure 3.3 below.

Figure 3.3: Kotter's (1996) Change Model

Source: Kotter and Rathgeber, (2006) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

It essentially projects leadership as a fundamental factor in successful change management (Onia *et al.*, 2021). It is noteworthy that these eight steps strongly project a top-led approach to change management (Evans, 2020). According to Odiaga *et al.* (2021), Kotter's (1996) change model places much emphasis on the significance of organisational culture and how it relates to organisational change management. The eight major steps of Kotter's (1996) model are hereby highlighted:

Step 1: Create Urgency

Establishing a sense of urgency is the first important step to initiating any change in an organisation. It is primarily the act of consciously creating change and promoting awareness of the need for change. The inability to foster the need for change by establishing a sense of urgency can prove fatal to change initiatives (Isaksson, 2019). The status quo must be challenged by establishing an understanding that a current system is no longer fit for its purpose or less efficient than desired, thereby escalating or amplifying the need for an imminent redesign, reconstruction, transformation or a comprehensive and holistic change. The cooperation of all stakeholders involved is of paramount importance. Hence, communicating the need for a change is crucial in change management (Kormann and

Suberg, 2021). The leadership must ensure the message about the need for change is constantly and effectively communicated through the ranks and that all stakeholders comprehend the sense of urgency. Immense, consolidated and deliberation action needs to be taken to encourage, stimulate and convince employers to embrace the incoming change, even though it may be accompanied by some degree of distress at first (Reeves *et al.*, 2021). The introduction of external sources, such as consultants, at this stage to establish and communicate the need for change can prove productive because it can add validity to the message of change and make employees believe in it (Matama and Mkwizu, 2021).

Step 2: Form a powerful coalition: The second step in Kotter's (1996) change model emphasises the need for the formulation of a group that is well-equipped and thorough enough to successfully lead the organisation through its desired change. Such a group is referred to as a guiding coalition. Kotter (1996), wrote that to successfully lead and implement a change through an effective management process, it is important that it is not solely saddled on one individual, hence the need for a guiding coalition (Haas *et al.*, 2019). These individuals that are assigned to make up the coalition group represent sponsors for the change initiative. Individuals in such coalition groups must have specific traits (Weiss and Li, 2020). They include positions of power. These sets of individuals must be major stakeholders on the management board and have strong enough influence to undermine the resistance of the remaining few that oppose intended change. These individuals must also have expertise in their respective fields. It is important that all pertinent fields are represented in the group to make a holistic decision and strategy (Sittrop and Crosthwaite, 2021). The group members must be credible and reputable individuals who are well respected and esteemed by employees within the organisation. This trait will help endear and incline employees to the change initiative.

Leadership is a key trait in this coalition group. The group must be comprised of leaders with proven track records who can spearhead and facilitate the intended change (Lambert, 2019).

Step 3: Create a vision for change: In the management of change, as designed by Kotter, the next step after the creation of a guiding coalition is the development of a vision and strategy. The pioneering duty of the coalition group is to draw up a change vision and strong strategy with which to accomplish the vision. The vision must be simple, measurable, achievable, realistic and time-bound (SMART). The vision set out by the coalition group must be characterised by clarity so that it is easily comprehensible for all stakeholders. The absence of a clear and precise vision will lead to complication, misunderstanding and deviation from the intended goal, which will frustrate the essence of the change initiative (Kotter, 1996). In the management of change, the vision of change is unarguably crucial to the whole process of the change initiative (Venus *et al.*, 2019). A clear vision and strategic planning have been identified to be of high importance in broadening the perspective of the management beyond the immediate enhancement of performance and accommodation of the need to tackle persisting change in the dynamics of business operations and its environment (Lewis and Jones, 2019). According to Kotter (1996), the vision of change is required to be attractive enough to appeal to the interest of all stakeholders involved.

Step 4: Communicate the vision: The sequel to the formulation of change vision and strategic planning is the communication of the intended change vision. It has been identified as one of the two most paramount steps in Kotter's (1996) change model (Koukku, 2019). Communication is a crucial factor in the processes of organisational change management. Effective communication can help to mitigate doubt, de-escalate confusion and immensely influence employee reactions to the proposed change (Tao, 2021). Management can become negligent and undermine the level of persistence and frequency required in communicating

with stakeholders to foster proper understandings of the change initiative. This could ultimately result in sabotaging change within the organisation. Communication is important, and it is a key factor that must be present throughout the lifetime of the change process and beyond (Yue *et al.*, 2019). Progress and milestones in the process of change management should be communicated to encourage stakeholders, foster credibility and appraise the process and commend achievements. The employees and other stakeholders should not be left bewildered or marginalized at any point due to a lack of communication (Schramm, 2020). It is also imperative for communication to be effective and for avenues for feedback to be given to motivate stakeholders to actively participate in the process and adequately examine and review the alignment of the process with the change vision.

Step 5: Empower action: Through the effective communication of a change vision within the organisation, staff members are encouraged and motivated to take on new initiatives, creativity, innovations and ideas. Employees need support beyond communication to tackle and surmount barriers that are presented against the vision of change. At this stage, employees should be well-equipped to combat barriers, such as skills, supervisors, structures and systems (Neves *et al.*, 2021). Existing structures within the organisation can pose a serious hindrance to the implementation of the desired change. The stereotypical approaches of supervisors who are always keen on maintaining the status quo and have become rigid in the manner of carrying out their operations often threaten the survival of a change vision. The systems of operation within the organisation that have formed the basis of business or operational engagement and have helped maintain the status quo could also be an obstacle to change initiatives (Laig and Abocejo, 2021). Hence, it is essential for systems and structures that endanger the change vision to be eliminated and for opportunities and enabling environments for idea generation to be made available. To promote empowerment, the

significance of training cannot be overemphasized. The training of employees through effective communication and qualitative coaching has proven to be successful in empowering staff members (Asirifi *et al.*, 2022).

Step 6: Create quick wins: Short-term wins show the possibilities and realism embedded in change initiatives. There are different sequences and phases designed in the implementation of change projects that are often geared towards the actualisation of the desired change vision (Toor, 2021). The success of each step or phase helps motivate employees and further garners enthusiasm towards change. It is important to track the progress of change projects, recognising transformations and acknowledging every step in the right direction. It is also significant to applaud and reward employees for their contributions and innovations that impact the change process and furnish the goal of the change vision (Mannie, 2019). Change projects could span a long time, and some last several years. Without short-term wins, many people could be discouraged and lose commitment to the change process. Hence short-term wins help sustain a sense of direction and satisfaction towards drawing closer to achieving the desired goal (Asirifi *et al.*, 2022). This process of short-term wins helps show that the change process is rewarding aside from the main benefit of the change initiative itself. The guiding coalition can use short-term wins to evaluate the change vision in comparison to present surrounding factors and modify it accordingly.

Step 7: Build on the change: The visibility of initial successes and enhancement of performance may be a limitation for the management should they become complacent and negligent in their attentiveness to the change vision (Galli, 2019). Due to the possibility of relapse in the newly initiated procedures, it is essential for leaders and managers to engage the benefits of short-term gains to challenge the structures and systems that are in misalignment with executed change efforts (Kroll *et al.*, 2019). The successes attained so far

in the project must be continually put in perspective towards the change vision. Balance must be maintained by the management, especially the guiding coalition, to ensure that while short-term wins are celebrated and acknowledged, stakeholders do not lose sight of the main initiative (Wentworth, 2020). The achievement of objectives must be consolidated to engineer further ease of change implementations. Gains should not be an end to a change vision by subtly substituting change. Rather they should help integrate and foster change implementation.

Step 8: Make it stick: The ease from the persistent and relentless drive for change after barriers to change have been subdued can result in dissipation in the newly subscribed ideology if these new beliefs and ideologies are not ingrained in the value systems of an organisation (Laig and Abocejo, 2021). The aftermath of change implementation should be an immediate strategy for sustaining the new mindsets and ideals by anchoring them in the organisational culture. This can be done by enlightening employees on the positive impacts of the new perspectives, methodologies and values on the performance of the organisation and ensuring the adoption of this new strategy by new managerial intakes. To make change sustainable, it must be ensured that the values and paradigm of the new change become the norm and form the basis for internal operations within the organisation (Townesley and Knight, 2020). Structures should be in place to support the people leading the change to attain effective training, coaching, mentoring and shadowing. Effective means of communication of various means can also be engaged. These means of communication can involve pictures and audio-visual material and enhance the entrenchment of newly implemented changes in the culture of an organisation (Szymanska, 2021).

Kotter (1996) recommends and emphasises that the eight steps must be observed in succession. None should be omitted, and none of the steps should be executed randomly. It

also discourages the simultaneous implementation of the steps because it will hinder the success of the model in the management of the desired change (Townasley and Knight, 2020). It can, therefore, be surmised that the model, though detailed and comprehensive, is too rigid in approach and implementation. Hence, it is difficult to modify or adjust the model for use in organisations with cultures that do not entirely align with the fundamentals of each step of the model (Berry and Noller, 2020). Furthermore, some of the steps in the model might not be relevant in certain change projects. For instance, Stage 1 and Stage 4 will be irrelevant in the implementation of a change project with a high degree of confidentiality. Understudying and observing the impact of a change process requires a great deal of time. Therefore, considering a model with eight steps could take years to implement, hence rendering the evaluation of Step 7 and Step 8 more challenging (Andrade, 2020)

3.2.4 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The TAM is a model that relays the intentions of use and usefulness that have been perceived through the perspectives of cognitive instrumental processes and social influence (Zaineldeen *et al.*, 2020). Two major concepts have been found to be fundamental to the viability of the TAM, and it is upon these two concepts that this model has been postulated. They are perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. These two highly important concepts are central to the essence and significance of the adoption of any new technological innovation in any sector. It is imperative that before any group of people embrace and accept a new technology, it must appeal to their reasoning regarding the importance of its usefulness and how user-friendly it is (Sprenger and Schwaninger, 2021). There is a vital interrelation between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. It has been gathered that with a high degree of ease of use comes a corresponding increase in the degree of perception of the usefulness of a technology (Muhammad *et al.*, 2019). In other words, the more user-friendly

a new technology is, the more it is perceived to be useful. Perceived usefulness is, therefore, largely dependent on perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness influences attitudes and behavioural intention towards a new technology (Sagnier *et al.*, 2020). This behavioural intention further has an immense impact on the use of the newly introduced technological innovation. Perceived usefulness can be described as the extent to which a person thinks a new technological innovation would improve their effectiveness and efficiency. However, perceived ease of use can be described as the extent to which a person thinks a new technological innovation would be void of ambiguity and technicality (Al-Rahmi *et al.*, 2019). Figure 3.4 below shows the relationships among these concepts. The two major cores of the TAMs are perceived ease of use (PEU) and perceived usefulness (PU). However, there are other important external variables that are considerable factors that facilitate the TAM theory.

Figure 3.4: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Source: Zaineldeen et al., (2020) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

The application of the TAM has cut across different technological innovations of information systems in diverse industries with varieties of cultures and at different times. It has also weathered many considerable factors as well as varieties of fields of studies and all walks of life (Vahdat *et al.*, 2021). In all these critically distinctive nomenclatures, it has proven to be

productive, resulting in its wide acceptance and the belief in its comprehensive approach. In recent times, it is becoming increasingly pertinent to recognise the underlying factors responsible for the acceptance of or resistance to newly introduced technological innovations by end-users (Sukendro *et al.*, 2020). The research and study thereof have, therefore, gained prominence and critical attention. This is because end-users and the engagement and adoption of new information technology and systems have proven to be germane to the application and understanding of new technology (Granić and Marangunić, 2019). According to Jimenez *et al.* (2021), the TAM can be defined as the adoption of technological software and hardware in an organisation to enhance effectiveness and efficiency, speed up the operational pace, increase its strength and offer ease of access to information. The purpose of TAMs and theories is to relay, in detailed terms, the phenomena of the user assimilation, reception and engagement of newly introduced technology.

3.3 Evaluation of EHRS Implementation Frameworks

According to Gebre-Mariam and Bygstad (2019), the implementation of an EHRS comprises different important conditions. All these conditions must be present to facilitate the successful execution of an electronic record system:

- Casual conditions: These are conditions that have direct impacts on EMR implementations. Such conditions include restricted access to comprehensive patient details, confidentiality issues (Keshta and Odeh, 2021), drug interactions, errors in medication, communication issues among clinicians, the lack of a robust decision support system and the lack of efficient follow-up processes.
- Contextual conditions consist of infrastructural, economical and organisational factors. Energy and information and telecommunication systems are basic

infrastructures that are critical to the implementation of EHRs (Afolalu *et al.*, 2021). Organisational factors include human resource strengths, operational procedures, the task at hand and patient capacity. The economic conditions are essentially the funding and financial requirements for such a project involved in the implementation of a system of such magnitude.

- The intervening conditions are individual and organisational factors, cost and technological factors. Individual and organisational factors are reflected in the attitudes of end-users towards the system, the computer skills and literacy of staff members, especially clinicians that will be using the EHRs, and the relentless support of management in facilitating training and essential support is critical to the successful implementation of EHRs (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). The cost a factor here covers the financial implications of training staff, procuring equipment, recruiting personnel and the provision of maintenance at scheduled intervals. Technological factors encapsulate the quality of systems and services, as well as the software and hardware required in EHRs implementation.

Actions and interaction strategies are the carefully formulated activities and objectives that enhance projects geared towards the implementation of EHRs and driving intervening conditions. As shown in Figure 3.5, it is grouped into users and organisations. *Users* simply refers to stakeholders that are directly involved in the use of EHRs, and they are also involved in the pre-implementation and essential training. The role of organisations in action and interaction strategy development and implementation is to control and manage the project and provide task flexibility, support and damage control. The direct consequences of EHRs implementation and corresponding actions and interaction strategies are shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: EMR Implementation Framework

Source: Gebre-Mariam and Bygstad (2019) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

3.3.1 TAM-Based EHRS Framework

The effervescent and effective application of an EHRS in the robust delivery of effective healthcare services is premised on a profound understanding of the intentions and attitudes of primary stakeholders in engaging its use (Setia *et al.*, 2020). This insight is quite fundamental to the general success of the implementation and sustainability of an EHRS in any medical organisation and the healthcare sector in general (Poddar and Tripathi, 2021). The engagement of the TAM will help provide a better perceptive overview geared towards the enhanced comprehension of the attitudes of healthcare personnel to the acceptance of EHRS. As discussed earlier, the TAM was generically designed for the business-oriented environment. This is due to the critical role of creativity and innovation in business operation advancement through technological disruption. Hence, much more research and many additional studies have been carried out on TAM because it relates to commercial industries

and business (Granić, and Marangunić, 2019; Kamal *et al.*, 2020). However, scanty consideration has been given to the application of the TAM for EHRs and HIT generally (Ammenwerth, 2019; Kamal *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, the limited research and studies carried out so far provide a germane basis and comprehensive discussion on the TAM as it relates to healthcare. To achieve success in the application of the TAM in the healthcare sector, the peculiar characteristics of the healthcare industry must be considered, and several factors or attributes must be contemplated to design a TAM that is more suitable and relevant (Sukendro *et al.*, 2020). The distinctiveness in the healthcare industry is identifiable in the close engagement of all personnel (e.g., clinicians, physicians and nurses) with the service recipient and the resultant effect of the service provided. Also, the complexity of the nature of service, multiplicity and diversity of all specialities involved in service delivery and desired results distinguish the healthcare sector from other sectors. Hence, there is much information sharing across the board of this wide array of specialities. Patient information is transferred among relevant and authorised professionals to provide tailored services to each patient. This information sharing and data transferring has been found to be impacted by the degree of trust the staff has in the data (Ganiga, *et al.*, 2020). Studies have shown that the TAM anticipates an enormous degree of discrepancy in the acceptance of technology in the healthcare sector. This has further broadened the need for the design and development of a TAM that is well customised to fit the exclusive attributes of the healthcare sector to arrive at a more relevant model (Holden and Karsh, 2010). In his study of TAM's PU and PEOU of HER among nurses. Computer skill was included in the model as part of the attributes (i.e., user characteristics) to know if it will impact nurses' PU and PEOU of EHRs (Tubaishat, 2017). Also, it has been proposed that certain user characteristics, such as occupational hierarchy, gender and EHR experience can help enhance the utilisation of TAMs by adding them to TAM

design (Gagnon *et al.*, 2014). The study reveals that user experiences of EHRs greatly impacted PEOU, hence fostering user acceptance of the technology. As they advanced in the use of technological EHRs applications, their EOU significantly improved (Carayon *et al.*, 2011). Upon the careful study of computer skills as a user attribute, it was discovered that it influences EHRs through the TAM's PU and PEU. The skilful users find the system easy to use and find it more useful while the least skilful users find the system the most difficult to engage and, hence, less useful than others find it (Steininger *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, according to Mohamamad and Yunus (2017), the technology acceptance of EMRs is largely dependent on the influence of the attributes of the system (i.e., EMR on the PU and PEOU) and not the attributes or characteristics of the users. The EMR attributes included in their study are usability, functionality, security and privacy and confidentiality. Their research framework is shown below.

Figure 3.6: Framework of Technology Acceptance Model for EMR

Source: Mohamamad and Yunus, 2017

The implementation of EHRs is dependent on a range of important factors. Among these factors are leadership, management and organisational performance, as it relates to the sustainability of EHRs. Any attempt to implement an integrated IT system on an extensive or

national scale in any sector it is often accompanied by attendant cumbersome obstacles that pose hindrances to successful implementation (Hansen *et al.*, 2019). This has always been true in the HIT and in the implementation of an integrated EHR. To drive a successful EHR implementation, it is expedient for research and knowledge development around critical factors to be carried out intensively and comprehensively (Goldfinch, 2007; Maillet *et al.*, 2014). One of the crucial factors is leadership. Studies have shown that effective management, exceptional leadership, personnel development, operability and usability and infrastructural support are crucial to the successful implementation of EHRs (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2015). The general concept of leadership and leadership theories have been ingrained in organisational management and implementation of innovations and the facilitation of change in the public and private sectors alike. However, the applicability of these leadership concepts in the implementation of technological innovations in the healthcare sector is required for the consideration of the unique nature and peculiarity of this sector to achieve optimisation and high performance. According to Laukka *et al.* (2020), leadership and management have been significantly impactful in the successful implementation of IT innovations. Therefore, leadership plays a fundamental role in EHR performance. In leading and implementing change for organisational performance, there are two leadership styles that must be considered. They are situational and transformational leadership styles. These two are further subdivided into four important theories, namely mobilise, involve, adapt and guide (Hansen and Norup, 2019):

- Transformational leadership—Mobilise and Involve
- Situational Leadership—Guide and Adapt

According to Hansen and Norup (2019), there are four styles of leadership that translate into four hypotheses:

The first theory states that there is a leadership style that involves deploying or organising initial support prior to implementation and fostering organisational performance after implementation—mobilise.

The second theory states that there is a leadership style that involves rigorously training, preparing and equipping personnel before the implementation of an IT system and fostering system performance after implementation—guide.

The third theory postulates that there is a leadership style that involves promoting the engagement of end-users (i.e., personnel) in integrating and adopting the new technology in the standard operating procedure and fostering performance after the implementation phase—involve.

The fourth theory states that there is a leadership style that involves modifying the implementation of an IT system to the unique attributes of the immediate environment in which the system will be used, thereby promoting positive performance after the implementation phase—adapt.

Hansen and Norup formulated a performance model for EHRS, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 3.7: Model explaining variations in perceived performance.

Source: Hansen and Norup, (2019) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

In the above Figure 3.7, 'initial support' represents the first theory —mobilise. The second theory (i.e., guide) is depicted as 'directive leadership'. The third theory (i.e., involve) is represented as 'participative leadership' while the fourth theory is shown in Figure 3.7 as 'implementation strategy'. In their study, Hansen and Norup (2019), discovered that the theory has the greatest influence on perceived performance, then is the first theory after that is the fourth theory. Finally, the second theory has the least impact on perceived performance.

In the quest to understand the magnitude of the impact of the implementation of EHRS on the quality of healthcare services (output) and the performance of personnel (process quality), Yang *et al.* (2005) developed a framework. Their framework was a modification of the novel information system success model (Delone and McLean, 2003). They streamlined and based their framework on two of the fundamental dimensions of information system success formulated from existing models. Yang and colleagues only used information quality

and system quality. Adulkarim *et al.* (2011) adopted Yang *et al.*'s (2005) model in their studies to determine the impact of the EHR implementation process in the case of two hospitals in Malaysia. Hence, they proposed a framework for further use by others (Sabeh *et al.*, 2021). The framework is largely based on an assumption that quality service is a direct product of a successfully executed implementation strategy that results in the increased performance of employees and impacts overall organisational performance.

Figure 3.8: EHR Implementation process impact framework

Source: Adulkarim et al. 2011 Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

According to Adulkarim *et al.* (2011), the possible outcome of a successful implementation of an EHRS is system service quality improvement (i.e., service and information quality improvements). These are referred to as success dimensions. The former comprises usability, accessibility and interaction while the latter includes the adequacy of information and usefulness of the content, as shown in Figure 3.8. Adulkarim *et al.* (2011) compared two different implementation processes in two healthcare organisations (see Figure 3.8, Model A

and Model B). The impacts of both implementations were carefully studied, and the differences were reviewed. Ultimately, according to the study, Model A and Model B, as shown in Figure 3.8, proved that successful implementation fosters both system service quality and organisational performance improvement. R1, R2 and R3 represent the nature of EHRS implementation models, the effect of model variation on system service quality outcome and the impact of system service quality on individual performance, respectively.

Table 3.1: Summary of Model Gaps

Model	Gaps
Lewin (1947)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is mechanical in its operation. • It projects false simplicity of change management (Burnes, 2020). • It is more theoretical in approach and less practicable. • It is unsuitable for more complex organisations (Bartunek and Woodman, 2015). • It lacks implementation guidelines in each stage. It is not detailed enough.
Kotter (1996)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is too rigid in approach and implementation (Kang <i>et al.</i>, 2020) • Resistance to modification and adjustment to fit for use in organisations with differing cultures from the fundamentals of each step • Not all steps are relevant and practicable in all change projects (Thi, 2021) • It is more process-focused than people-focused.
TAM Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is only suitable for individual use not for adoption on an organisational scale (Ajibade, 2018) • Lack of detailed explanation of the behaviour of end-users (Lim <i>et al.</i>, 2016) • Inadequate explanation of the use of new technology and adoption by end-users (Chandio <i>et al.</i>, 2017)

Lewin's (1947) change theory is adopted in this thesis. Its relevance to the formulation of the EHRS implementation framework lies in its practicality, systematic approach, and emphasis on driving successful and sustained change in organizations. The unfreezing involves preparing the organization for change by creating awareness of the need for change and breaking down existing resistance to change. The changing stage involves implementing the new EHRS system, while the refreezing stage focuses on solidifying the change and ensuring it becomes the new norm. This structured approach helps guide the EHRS implementation process from initial preparation to sustainable integration into organizational practices.

It recognizes that resistance to change is a natural response within organizations. By identifying sources of resistance during the unfreezing stage, the EHRS implementation framework can proactively address concerns and build support among stakeholders. Understanding and managing resistance is crucial for the successful adoption and continuous use of the EHRS system. It also aligns with the notion of continuous improvement and learning cycles. After the initial EHRS implementation, the refreezing stage emphasizes the need for reinforcement and continuous monitoring to ensure that the new system becomes the accepted norm. This iterative approach allows organizations to adapt to challenges, collect feedback, and refine the implementation process for long-term success.

Lewin's (1947) theory acknowledges the importance of considering the human element in change processes. EHRS implementation involves significant changes in daily workflows and practices for healthcare professionals. By focusing on understanding the needs and concerns of end-users, the framework can prioritize user training, support, and engagement, leading to higher adoption rates and sustained system usage.

Furthermore, it has been widely researched and validated over the years, making it a well-established and evidence-based approach to change management. By adopting a theory with a strong empirical foundation, the EHRS implementation framework can benefit from proven strategies and best practices, increasing the likelihood of successful outcomes.

Lewin's (1947) change theory is highly relevant in the formulation of an EHRS implementation framework due to its structured, human-centric, and evidence-based approach. By leveraging the three-step change process, understanding and managing resistance, and prioritizing user needs, healthcare organizations can navigate the complex process of EHRS implementation and foster sustained change that positively impacts patient care and healthcare delivery.

3.4 Derivation of the Proposed Framework

The derivation of the proposed framework for a sustainable EHR implementation was achieved by identifying the gaps in existing literature, as shown in Table 3.2 below, a review of relevant theoretical models and an evaluation of the current frameworks. Various academic contributions and industrial research and developments in HIT over the past decades have made tremendous resources available for critical evaluation and review. The framework was derived from several existing studies with evaluations of relevant theories. The impacts and essences of these studies are categorised into the four-quadrant framework shown below in Table 3.2. This table helps distinctively group research studies and gaps in the related literature. The perspective upheld in the healthcare industry concerning comprehensively integrated EHRS implementation is that it is often a herculean task and egregiously daunting to sustain in the long-term, as so desired. As discussed earlier in this chapter and Chapter 2, some of the requirements for the implementation of a structured EHRS are often met. However, negligence and inadequacies in other required factors have often led to failures of entire initiatives. The proposed sustainable EHRS Implementation Framework involves the consideration of factors that were previously given little or no attention in existing frameworks and literature. It further consolidates them into a realistic and holistic implementation approach.

The key limitations of current EHRS practices were identified, and gaps in the related literature were discussed and fundamentally developed as the basis for the structuring and formulation of the proposed framework. The major tool used in this research to identify literature gaps was the four-quadrant framework, which involves grouping research based on outcome and purpose. The outcome could either be descriptive or prescriptive while the purpose can be either visionary or implementational (Althonayan, 2003). Visionary research is often theoretical and emphasises the goals and objectives of EHRs over the sequential processes of its execution. However, studies that are implementation-based are often practical-oriented and focused on procedures of execution. It is important to note that the outcome of either purpose can be either prescriptive or descriptive. Hence, this framework is rendered in four major quadrants, namely, visionary and descriptive, visionary and prescriptive, implementation and descriptive and implementation and prescriptive. This framework developed by Althonayan (2003) helps to give a comprehensive categorisation of the contributions of each study and existing EHRS frameworks.

Table 3.2: Research Literature Evaluation

		Research Philosophy	
		Visionary	Implementation
Research Outcomes	Prescriptive	Quadrant II	Quadrant IV
	Descriptive	Kuruppuarachchi <i>et al.</i> (2002) Menachemi and Collum (2011) Reina <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Mekanontchai (2009) Robertson <i>et al.</i> (2010) Stanberry (2011)

Prescriptive	Savage and Reis (2012)	Cresswell <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	Zhang (2012)	Takian <i>et al.</i> (2012)
	Devkota and Devkota (2013)	Alnassar (2012)
	Bozan (2014); Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Otto and Nevo (2013)
	Hawthorne and Richards (2016)	Lewis <i>et al.</i> (2013)
	Justinia (2016)	Boonstra <i>et al.</i> (2014)
	Razmak and Belanger (2017)	Balgrosky (2015)
	Sarabdeen and Moonesar (2017)	Baird and Boak (2015)
	Waithera <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Huang and Gramopadhye (2016)
	Yusof and Sahroni (2018)	Richardson (2016)
	Rigby <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Barrett (2017)
	Dahleez <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Tough and Lihoma (2018)
	Kumar and Mostafa (2020)	Fragidis and Chatzoglou (2018)
	Nwagwu and Areo (2020)	Hower <i>et al.</i> (2019)
	Patricio <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Yusif <i>et al.</i> (2019)
	Turulja <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Esmaeilzadeh (2020)
		Quadrant II
	Currie and Finnegan (2011)	Primer (2016)
	Sana <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Birnbaum <i>et al.</i> (2018)

Source: Adopted from Althonayan (2003)

All research efforts categorised into the first quadrant involve examining HIT and change management extensively but only in theory and not in practice. They are mainly visionary and descriptive. Savage and Reis (2012) examined research perspectives on HIT, the inherent advantages of HIT and HIT's application in enhancing the quality of healthcare and increasing the affordability of healthcare services. Sarabdeen and Moonesar (2017) focused on investigating the provision of laws and policies that govern and ensure the protection of patient data and privacy in electronic healthcare services from the perspective of end-users. Dahleez *et al.* (2020) investigated the contribution of HIT to the augmentation of the performance of healthcare professionals, the improvement of services and the strengthening of the relationship between clinicians and patients. Rigby *et al.* (2019) examined the transformation of child primary care services by EHRS while Kumar and Mostafa (2020) investigated the use of EHRS for research and development to improve and optimise the healthcare system and service delivery. Turulja *et al.* (2020) examined knowledge sharing among clinicians in the healthcare sector using information technology to improve healthcare

services. Yusof and Sahroni (2018) investigated one of the demerits of engaging information technology in healthcare—medical errors that occur as a result of HIT and how they can be reduced and effectively managed. Kurupparachchi *et al.* (2002) critically reviewed and examined strategies for the implementation of IT-related change management for the purpose of achieving a successful and sustainable change. Reina *et al.* (2012) focused on the application of EHRs in the management of knowledge integration and information of operational procedures through strategic interoperability and interconnectivity. Furthermore, Nwagwu and Areo (2020) examined the impact of economic and technical factors on the adoption of mobile a HIT facility in patient care within a hospital setting in the south-western part of Nigeria. Hawthorne and Richards (2016) focused on examinations of the literature on the direct patient engagement and use of EHRs, facilitating their active participation in their own care. They further examined barriers to adoption by patients and means of overcoming them. Razmak and Belanger (2017) examined statistical tools to examine the measure of the use of EHRs for personal healthcare management by patients in Canada and as a means of intensifying awareness and boosting patient confidence in participating in their own healthcare through the use of information technology. Patricio *et al.* (2020) explored how service design can impact and transform healthcare service through an integrated and patient-centric HIT. Wu *et al.* (2015) described the development and creation of HIT systems in healthcare organisations for the optimisation of performance and quality healthcare for patients. All the aforementioned research works are mainly descriptive and visionary. They all lack a prescriptive implementation in their approach, and none present a guideline or practicable framework for the implementation of a successful and sustainable IT change management in healthcare service.

The studies classified in the second quadrant are visionary-prescriptive studies. Currie and Finnegan (2011) reported on the analysis carried out on the NHS and its implementation of EHRs. They examined the relationship between theoretical recommendation and actual practice in the execution of an integrated EHRs in the UK. Nguyen *et al.* (2017) explored and investigated the perceptions, reactions and attitudes of healthcare professionals toward healthcare information system technology while Nach (2015) examined patient responses and reactions to the use of personal information in the application of HIT. The author also recommended mechanisms that give insight into patients' reactions when they feel their identities and primary data are being challenged or attacked. Parkin (2016) wrote a report on NHS England's implementation of an integrated EHRs and patients' access to their own EHRs. The author also described the need for a pathfinder exercise before the implementation of a national EHRs. Narattharaska *et al.* (2016) investigated the elements that healthcare professionals recommend for a successful EHRs implementation. The author established vital dimensions that are both managerial and technical, but the need for managerial proficiency was emphasised. Clarity of EHRs goal, allocation of budget, clinician involvement and communication were prescribed for the successful implementation of an EHRs. McLeod and Childs (2013) examined EHRs challenges through the analysis of clinicians' fears and worries and provided a tool (i.e., a framework) for understanding and managing EHRs challenges.

The research works categorised in the third quarter are descriptive-implementation. Hower *et al.* (2019) evaluated the measurement and usability of the change attitude scale in an organisation that offers healthcare services. In their study, Yusif *et al.* (2019) identified factors that affect the successful implementation of HIT change management in healthcare settings and recommended these factors as guides for HIT implementation. The factors they identified are stakeholder participation, experience, strategy, change agents and improvement with

training. Otto and Nevo (2013) studied and examined the role and effect of policy guidelines on EHRs adoption in hospitals. They provided the results of a theoretical application of a simulation model for the implementation of policies for HIT. Lewis *et al.* (2013) examined the impact of strategy on the capability of an organisation towards the successful development and implementation of EHRs in the U.S. healthcare sector. Stanberry (2011) analysed the design, development and formulation of the enhanced methods applied in the management of EHRs to determine and maximise the inherent benefits for all stakeholders involved. Huang and Gramopadhye (2016) provided recommendations for HIT implementation in rural healthcare organisations. They also investigated breaches in compliance with the policies and regulations recommended for the use of HIT. Barrett (2017) described and recommended means by which EHRs can be implemented so they appeal to employees and, therefore, yield increased performance and high productivity for EHRs. Baird and Boak (2015) identified EHRs implementation challenges in healthcare companies. They examined an EHRs introduction and analysed factors that enhanced the adoption of technological innovation in a small healthcare company. Tough and Lihoma (2018) identified means for implementing successful and sustainable integrated EHRs for the improvement of data and service quality while Esmaeilzadeh (2020) analysed the impact of privacy and confidentiality on patient care by examining the trust and willingness of patients in disclosing and giving consent for data access to healthcare professionals.

The fourth quarter contains research that is categorised as prescriptive-implementation. Miraldo *et al.* (2019) presented a strategic approach for implementing HIT to optimise productivity, monitor the quality of healthcare services and ensure thorough adherence to information and data compliance in technologically innovative healthcare systems. The authors designed a problem-solving technique for healthcare organisations to guarantee an

itch-free process of service delivery. They recommended the practical application of their strategy in any healthcare organisation in pursuit of quality enhancement, improved performance and technological innovation. However, there is no implementation guidance provided in their research or any framework in their study. Birnbaum *et al.* (2018) examined the perspectives of stakeholders and developed a framework for implementing an enhanced data privacy and protection system in the use of EHRs. They provided a framework with which to systematically execute the process and guide healthcare organisations. However, their study has no actual framework, and in their study, they focus solely on one aspect of HIT, data privacy protection. Very few researchers present a framework and practicable implementation guidance for the successful and sustainable implementation of HIT change management.

3.5 EHRs Implementation Sustainability Framework

In this study, extensive reviews were conducted on many varieties of literature on EHRs, investigating relevant EHRs subjects influencing the healthcare sector and recognising diverse robust operations, strategies and applications of EHRs with its strengths and limitations. In recent times, the application of EHRs has evolved and improved with advancements in technology and has helped reduce risks and enhance health service delivery to end-users (i.e., patients). Many EHRs theoretical frameworks and structural concepts have been devised and introduced. Upon the careful and in-depth analysis of the related literature, these theoretical and conceptual frameworks have been discovered to be deficient for practical and realistic implementation because it lacks implementation guidance.

The proposed framework in Figure 3.9 was derived from the literature reviewed in Chapter 2, subsections 2.5 and 2.6.1, the literature gaps identified in Chapter 3 and detailed in Table 3.2

and the relevant theories evaluated in Chapter 3, Subsection 3.2.2, majorly Lewin's (1947) change theory, and the evaluation of current frameworks that were discussed in Chapter 3, Subsection 3.3. Figure 3.9 is a three-phased change management framework for the implementation of EHRs, bearing great emphasis on the people (essentially all stakeholders) rather than the technology itself.

Figure 3.9: Theoretical EHR Implementation Sustainability Framework

Source: Researcher

3.5.1 Initiation

The initiation phase is the preliminary stage that precipitates the implementation of HIT change management. There are certain important phenomena and fundamental factors that must be established to achieve successful implementation. A robust initiation phase involves setting up a change initiative for effective and sustainable change management. A compromised initiation poses an enormous risk to an IT change project in the healthcare sector. It often results in a frustration of efforts and makes non and void subsequent tasks and engagement, which can be fatal and damaging to a change project. Other phases involved, as indicated in the framework, are largely dependent on a well-furnished initiation

phase. Hence, it is critical for the initiation phase to not be hastily executed. Rather it requires enough time for productivity and efficiency. This phase should not be rushed or unnecessarily stalled and delayed. The initiation phase involves the change vision, need for change, strategy, budget, end-user involvement, software design and stakeholder endorsement. These are, thus, analysed.

Vision: This is simply the core goal. It is a set ideology proposed for achievement by an individual or a group of people. Sustainable change management in HIT requires a vision to be set out at the initial stage for corporate achievement (Jalagat, 2016). It is essential for a change vision to be clear and concise. The clarity of vision enables ease of engagement. The ambiguity of a vision can greatly hinder the advancement and actualisation of a change project because stakeholders have different understandings of the change ideology due to its ambiguity. This difference in knowledge often results in differences in approach and the furtherance of other things besides the intended goal (Eryilmaz and Eryilmaz, 2016). The change vision gives a clear sense of direction for all tasks and engagements within the organisation. The change vision must be simple, measurable, achievable realistic and time-bound. The vision must be simple enough for ease of comprehension. As much effort as possible should be exerted to ensure the vision is communicable in just one sentence to promote sustainability (Katutura, 2020). This often guarantees the simplicity of vision. When a vision is well understood, it often fosters concerted efforts. Essentially, a change vision must also be measurable. There must be indicators that will help to track and monitor the change process to ensure it leads in the direction of the vision and values of the organisation (Baumgartner, 2014). This is often achievable through objectives. The achievement of these objectives serves as means to measure change vision.

Need for Change: Establishing the need for change serves as a major catalyst in communicating a change vision and helps people overcome barriers to change. It is imperative to convincingly establish the rationale behind an intended change, especially as it relates to information technology in the healthcare sector. Change initiatives are prone to limitations when they are embarked upon without a viable and established need for doing so in sight. The board of directors within an organisation must make concerted efforts in the deliberation of the needs for change and establish this beyond a reasonable doubt. Barriers to change often stem from disagreements on the need for change (i.e., employers are not convinced about a change and, hence, they resist it). The need for change can be strategically established by examining existing operations and systems and through the detailed analysis of their major challenges, weakness, threats and impacts on the output and productivity of an organisation. The need for the introduction of sophisticated IT systems in the management and delivery of healthcare services must be established by examining the challenges presented by the incapacities of existing systems and conveying how these challenges can be overcome through the new change initiative.

Strategy: Critical to successful and sustainable change management of information technology is the detailed and formulated plan for the overall achievement of the change vision. A holistic strategy serves as the blueprint for the change project. The formulation of a firm strategy will help establish the requirements, resources and alliances pertinent to the process of the change management of HIT to improve the delivery of healthcare. Planning for each task and every step of each phase will help to drastically reduce or eliminate surprises that might hinder the implementation or sustenance of the desired change. The design and formulation of the change strategy must be carried out by employees or staff members who are visionary and critical thinkers with applaudable problem-solving skills. Strategies for

sustainable change management should be detailed enough and include descriptions of required tasks and actions, which personnel should undertake such actions and the time required for such tasks to be concluded. It should also include performance and project management at each step, as well as serious accountability and a budget for the change project. Strategic planning is a critical success factor in the sustainable change management of information technology in the healthcare sector. A lack of strategy makes it extremely difficult to track the progress of a change and results in the haphazard implementation of change initiatives. The lack of a proper strategy sets up a change project for fatal failure, but an effective strategy gives direction and drives all stakeholders towards the actualisation of the ultimate goal.

Software Design: Software design is vital to the initiation phase in the change management of information technology in the healthcare sector. The technology must be furnished with large storage capabilities, efficient data transmission systems and tested and trusted hardware infrastructures. In the design of the software, thorough consideration must be given to the means of data acquisition, the organisation of data and data processing. When designing software in the healthcare sector, it is crucial to engage the end-users (i.e., clinicians, doctors, nurses, paramedics and other healthcare professionals). The input of the end-users will help guide the design towards ease of use and user-friendliness. The software sophistication, skills and dexterity of the supplier or designer are not guarantees of efficient and effective software. The processes of design must include the input, deliberation and consultation of major stakeholders, especially end-users. The change vision is also an important feature that must be included in the software design. The functions and operations of the software must be geared towards driving the vision for change. The organisational culture in the healthcare sector. A poor software design can result in incessant disruptions to

clinical operations and delays in patient care. This inefficiency may result in an incorrect diagnosis, which may be fatal for patients.

Stakeholder Involvement: In the initial phase, stakeholder engagement plays a pivotal role in ensuring the healthcare change initiative stands a chance of success. It is important for all major stakeholders to be carried along and engaged in the strategic planning of change management in HIT (McCarthy, 2014). Barriers to change initiatives often stem from top management negligence in recognising and consulting other stakeholders, especially the staff members and employees who will be majorly affected by the change or required to engage in the change program. Trust must be built with stakeholders to reduce or eliminate barriers to change (Rafferty and Restubog, 2017). This should be achieved by showing consistencies in actions and ideologies, being empathetic with stakeholders, ensuring transparency and accountability and acknowledging errors and misjudgements when appropriate. The stakeholders should be involved in the thinking and brainstorming process. Their honest opinions should also be earnestly sought after.

3.5.2 Executions

The execution phase follows the initiation phase. This is the stage at which the implementation of the change initiative is commenced. After the vision for change has been communicated at all management levels within the organisation and the need for change has been well received and understood. With a proper and robust strategic plan in place for the execution of a change and getting all stakeholders on board and moving in the same direction, the execution phase can be kicked off. In the execution phase, suppliers assigned with different tasks and targets are mobilised and strategies are implemented. Discussions, deliberations, meetings and all theoretical analyses are hereby turned into practical

engagements. It is important to stick to and align with the plan and strategy designed for the change project to achieve timely and fulfilling execution. However, consideration must be given to internal and external factors capable of influencing execution. A change in the dynamics of these factors will warrant a reasonable strategy change and adjustment to achieve the set goals. Each personnel, team, group and body assigned with tasks at each stage in the execution phase must be held highly accountable in this phase. In the change management of HIT, and EHRs in particular, the following are critical to the success of the execution phase: data privacy and confidentiality, interoperability, leadership, training and technology.

Data Privacy and Confidentiality: One of the main causes of failure in the implementation and execution of EHRs is the issue of patient data security and confidentiality. The national programme for IT in the NHS that was initiated over a decade failed woefully. Data privacy and confidentiality were discovered to be fundamental issues that were not factored into the execution of the programme, and there was no concrete evidence of any plan for managing patient data without compromising its security (Justina, 2017). The tendencies of risk to confidentiality and privacy of patient data are perilous to the success and sustenance of IT change management in the health sector (Norris, 2002, Kierkegaard, 2011). This has been a prevalent hindrance to the implementation of EHRs in the UK and other countries like the United States, Australia and Canada (Cripps and Standing, 2011). The principal challenge faced by the National Programme for IT (NPfIT) was personal information security. There were allegations that the patient data in the NHS can be transferred to certain incredible IT programs that could endanger the identities of citizens and residents alike. There must be a robust infrastructure in place that will strongly limit access to patient data, and policies and protocols must be established for authorised personnel to gain access to patient information

and data. Maintaining the security and confidentiality of patient data is the key to successful health information change management because patients must be assured that their data will not fall into the wrong hands and that they will be protected and shielded from unscrupulous individuals who might use their data for criminal activities. The rapid evolution and advancement of information technology have made diverse innovations with many possibilities available. However, the positives that technological creativity provides come with the challenges of cyber-crime. Hackers and malicious groups of people hunt for big data, such as that found in the NHS, for personal gains by using patient data for fraudulent endeavours. EHRs present huge opportunities for research and development. They are enormous resources for research purposes. However, the use of patient data for research or monitoring purposes should be subjected to stringent policies and regulations (Perera *et al.*, 2011), which will preserve patient data confidentiality and guarantee patient data security.

Interoperability: The implementation of an integrated health IT system is often maligned with the issue of interoperability. The implementation of a sustainable EHRs is attainable if the IT systems provided by the suppliers are interoperable (i.e., able to communicate with other systems), thereby resulting in system integration. EHR systems need to be able to communicate and transfer information from different databases established across various geographical locations in the country for a working and productive integrated system. In the adoption and implementation of EHRs in the United States, interoperability was one of the biggest challenges encountered because the healthcare sector lacked the standardization and compliance of interoperability. There was no established policy that guaranteed itch-free interaction among EHRs systems designed by various IT suppliers. This resulted in a bottleneck (Devkota and Devkota, 2013) in the smooth operations of an integrated EHRs, thereby threatening the sustainability and survival of the HIT change initiative. HIT regulators

should formulate unifying specifications and requirements that all vendors must strictly adhere to, which should be subjected to frequent auditing and monitoring.

Technology: The technology of the system is the bedrock of the entire change initiative and is mainly about the transformation and enhancement of healthcare delivery using technology (Lynch and Wainwright, 2020). Hence, technology is extremely significant. The technology involved includes software and hardware systems (Rogers, 2003), which must be synergized by skilled professionals for optimum delivery. In the execution phase, the appropriate operating systems, system files and computer applications should go live on the certified hardware platforms recommended by IT consultants in the healthcare organisation. The software can be designed and rendered to run on different forms of portable computer systems, such as tablets, mobile phones, laptops and personal computers, to support an integrated system (Wallis *et al.*, 2017). The system configurations required to ensure that the HIT system or EHRS run smoothly must be determined and specified for itch-free execution. A pilot system for the technology must be implemented before going live with the system in the execution phase. The pilot system is a trial session that gives the opportunity for the technology to be tested and understudied for a period. This ensures necessary modifications and adjustments are made before launching the HIT system. An untested or unproven technology will lead to the failure of HIT change management.

Training: Numerous HIT projects have ended in abrupt failure due to the incompetency of the end-users. However, the root cause of this ineptitude is mainly poor training. Training can be described as the process of improving employee expertise and competencies to equip them to efficiently execute their duties (Bashmakh, 2019). The facilitation and execution of HIT initiatives require the thorough and robust training of employees. This training is fundamental

to the success of HIT change management and sustenance. Training is a means of empowering employees to use the new system and adapt accordingly. It is a program that must be put in place to ensure that employees are well-equipped and thoroughly furnished (Rajasekar and Khan 2013) to acclimatize to the use of and use the new HIT system efficiently. The HIT system cannot offer the full capacity of the provision it offers without the adequate engagement of well-trained end-users. Poor or inadequate training can render a HIT system hazardous because the system can be made to serve the wrong purpose or malfunction when engaged by an untrained or incompetent end-user (Abbas, 2014). The lack of proper training can result in data breaches in which the security and confidentiality of patient data can be grossly compromised. Placing great emphasis only on the technology involved in HIT without a corresponding focus on the people (i.e., the end-users of such technology) often defeats the goal of any change effort, thus resulting in failure (Baus, 2004). Proper training will help the end-users understand the system holistically and give them a better understanding of the benefit of the adoption of the new IT system, thereby refreshing their minds while instilling the need for change in them. Training gives them first-hand experience with the system and encourages them to buy further into the change initiative. The training process (Karim *et al.*, 2019) provides further opportunity to indoctrinate end-users because it presents an avenue along which to instil the new value required for the actualisation and sustainability of the change project. The adequate training of healthcare personnel to engage the new HIT system is critical to the success and sustainability of HIT change management (Mozael, 2015). With proper training, the benefits presented by the HIT system can be fully maximised and contribute to the ultimate goal. Training provides the opportunity for end-user satisfaction in the use of the HIT system. Many employees may not be technologically inclined, especially the long-standing older generation (Elnaga and Imran, 2013). Therefore, without adequate

training, they may not derive satisfaction in the continual engagement of the HIT system, thereby impeding the sustenance of such a change initiative. The lack of satisfaction with a HIT system change can hinder smooth workflows and result in employee frustration on the job, which will lead to a decline in employee performance and inhibit healthcare service delivery, but with proper training, these employees can derive satisfaction in the use of the system, which often leads to encouragement for further engagement. This continual use will eventually lead to high competence and expertise in the use of the HIT system, thereby resulting in an improved, safe and timely healthcare service delivery (Naveed, 2014).

3.5.3 Monitoring

The final phase of the proposed framework is the monitoring phase. This phase consolidates the whole HIT system change management initiative. This phase is the key to the sustainability of the implemented change. Change initiatives are short-lived, even after successful implementation because of inadequacies in the monitoring of the newly adopted change. The monitoring phase will help prolong the life span of the executed change and ensure its evolution when required. Mismanagement and negligence at this phase can result in the total failure of the change effort, hence the need for a robust monitoring system. The successful completion of the execution phase could threaten the success of holistic change management. This is because the achievement and applaudable milestone of the execution phase may be mistaken for the success of the change project, thereby resulting in complacency and the dereliction of duty. This false sense of success could trigger some degree of negligence in subsequent tasks and phases. Therefore, it is important for the monitoring phase to be approached with a renewed form of energy and resolute commitment. This phase is fundamental to the sustainability of HIT system change management. The monitoring phase involves the observation of some important phenomena, such as system improvement,

feedback, organisation culture, technical support, performance evaluation and motivation and recognition.

System Improvement: The change management of an integrated HIT system requires a high degree of sustainability to achieve the desired change. This sustainability is dependent on certain measures and processes strategically designed to monitor the system. System improvement is significant in maintaining and ensuring an implemented change is long-lasting and nurtured to maturity to the fulfilment of its vision. Information technology is not static. It often evolves due to the continuous research and development in the field. Its innovation and creativity are often rapid in transformation. The failure to catch up with this transformation can lead to the existing system becoming obsolete and redundant and, thereby, regarded as no longer fit for its purpose. This will sabotage the longevity and sustenance of the change vision, hence the need for system improvement. The HIT system must be continually monitored and updated to ensure its functionality. The infrastructure used, both software and hardware, must often be optimised to meet healthcare demands and upgraded to the latest and best version available. System improvement also involves the engagement of skilled and well-trained IT professionals to continually monitor the systems and fix bugs that may hinder the ease of use of the system. This will help ensure the safety of the system and secure it against malware and sudden interruption or breaks in system workflow which may lead to delays in care for patients. System improvement helps to provide a refined and robust infrastructure that enhances patient data safety and confidentiality. It will help adjust the system according to the change in the dynamics of the influencing factors that are critical to the success and sustenance of HIT change management. The failure to improve HIT systems can lead to complete failures of the change initiative, regardless of the milestones or successes achieved in the initiation and execution phases.

Feedback: A effective feedback system is crucial to the monitoring phase of the HIT change management. It is important for the leadership and management within the healthcare system to provide opportunities for end-users to give feedback on the system. Feedback is a major catalyst for the improvement of the system. It gives insight into the specific aspect of the system that requires prompt enhancement, and this helps make the change effort highly productive. The feedback system will immensely contribute to the sustenance of the HIT change initiative because it will help provide direction, necessary corrections and required adjustments, which will lead to the optimisation of the HIT system. The feedback system provides a true representation of the opinions and thoughts of end-users on the HIT system. Its use is a means of continued engagement with employees on the management of the change project. As specified in the initiation phase, end-user engagement is important and critical to the success and sustenance of HIT change management. Hence, the feedback system in the monitoring phase is the developmental form of end-user engagement. The opinions and perspectives of employees should not be undermined, and their importance cannot be overemphasised. It would be counterproductive for the management and leadership to ignore or pay little or no attention to clinician feedback. The inspiration and motivation provided by the leadership that influenced employees to embrace the change initiative should not be deflated by the assumption that employees can no longer abandon the change. Failure to regard or recognise end-user recommendations and feedback can result in disinterest and a lack of motivation for the continued use and engagement of the HIT system by employees, which is a major bane to the sustenance of HIT change management.

Technical Support: It is important for the leadership of the healthcare organisation to put a robust technical support system in place after the implementation and execution of a HIT system. This will immensely contribute to successful change management because it will

promote the sustainability of the newly introduced system of HIT. There is a need for ongoing technical support in the monitoring phase to help end-users take maximum advantage of the ease of use of the new HIT system. The training and development rendered to staff members on engaging the technology at the execution phase should extend into the monitoring phase. Hence, technical support will further enhance the skills of healthcare professionals concerning the use and application of the system, thereby fostering sustainable HIT change management. An easily accessible technical support team of information technology professionals with the required expertise in the HIT system deployed must be available around the clock. This team will offer help to healthcare professionals at any point in time when there is a bottleneck in the technology. An easily accessible technical support team equipped with smooth and effective means of communication has great impacts on the longevity and sustainability of any HIT system. The lack of adequate skills and ineptitude of the technical support team can frustrate the engagement of the newly introduced technology. This is because the clinicians using the system will eventually revert to previous ways of doing things if the challenges encountered in the new system cannot be readily resolved due to a lack of effective technical support. The success and sustainability of HIT change management depend on the provision of robust technical support in the monitoring phase and beyond.

Motivation and Recognition: Motivation can be described as the process that drives and gears personnel dedication, direction and tenacity towards the achievement of a set vision (Robbins and Judge, 2018). In the pursuit of successful and sustainable HIT change management, the leadership and top management must establish a functioning and credible system of motivating employees and duly recognising them. Organisations that make effort to continuously motivate their staff members are often effective and productive (Nguyen, 2017). In the monitoring phase, the system of recognition and motivation will help spur

employees to engage the system with a sense of responsibility and encourage them to improve their skills to get the best possible outcome for the system, thereby increasing performance (Hussain *et al.*, 2019). All employees should be appreciated for their acceptance of change and readiness to use the new HIT system. They should all be rewarded for this and for using the technology. Afterwards, the giving of rewards and recognition for outstanding individual performance can then be initiated. This will ensure that no employee feels ignored, neglected or unappreciated (Jensen, 2018). The initial recognition and reward for all is a catalyst for success and sustainability because all employees will be motivated and geared towards upholding and using the new HIT system without diversion from the change initiative. The common goal set out by the organisation. Rewards should be attached to the effective use of the system (Saad, 2018). These rewards must be proportionate to the required effort. This will make the rewards attractive. An attractive reward motivates employees to use the system efficiently and as they were trained. Increases in the dedication to effectively use the system leads to the desired sustainability (Singh *et al.*, 2013). Employees who use the HIT system effectively should be recognised and praised within the organisation for all to see. They should be motivated with rewards that correspond to their levels in the organisation (Barkley, 2017). This will encourage others to follow suit. When most or all employees follow due processes in the use of HIT systems due to regular recognition and appropriate rewards, the HIT change management becomes sustainable within the healthcare organisation.

3.5.4 Influencing Factors

The successful attainment of a sustainable HIT system is dependent on certain factors that impact all three phases of the process (i.e., the initiation phase, execution phase and monitoring phase). These factors are categorised as internal and external. The internal factors

include communication, leadership, organisational structure and organisational culture. The external factors are governance, socioeconomic factors, finances and vendors.

Communication: Communication is a key factor that is critical to the success of change management in all industries (Neill, 2018) and it is an important internal factor in the successful implementation and sustenance of HIT change management. Without effective communication, a change initiative is bound to fail. Hence, great attention needs to be paid to building a strong and effective means of communication internally and across all departments or units within an organisation to achieve the desired change (Neill and Jiang, 2017). Members of management in the healthcare sector must ensure that the goals and objectives of the change project in implementing an integrated EHRS are effectively communicated to all stakeholders, especially the end-users of the system (Karanges *et al.*, 2014). Communication is said to be effective when the recipients can decode the message being passed (i.e., the stakeholders to whom the message is directed must understand the message as the sender intends). The successful and sustainable implementation of HIT change management in the healthcare sector stands a great chance when the communication system is well-structured and effective. Change management is often impeded by barriers such as employee resistance. In the healthcare sector, healthcare professionals' resistance to information technology adoption can frustrate the advancement of change within the sector. However, with excellence in communication (Men and Bowen, 2017), this resistance can be easily diffused and overcome, thereby dissolving the doubts of employees and allaying their fears and worries. Effective communication gives proper insight to healthcare professionals regarding what is expected of them in the execution of the change project and the application of a newly-introduced technological change. Effective communication often drives employee engagement (Verčič and Vokić, 2017). The need for the continual training and development

of employees in engaging the technology cannot be overemphasized. However, the training will fail if there is no effective communication in the training processes. To successfully make a change, a visionary leader must be equipped with effective communication skills to influence all employees, especially healthcare professionals who are the end-users of the technology being adopted (Kraft *et al.*, 2018). Effective communication is an internal factor that affects HIT change management in the healthcare sector. When it is effective, it is a huge influencer of change and potent enough to drive change management towards the change vision. Poor communication, however, will lead to the fatal failure of HIT change management, regardless of how small the project may be.

Leadership: The limitations encountered in EHR adoption for NPfIT are poor leadership and ineffective management. There were gross unaccountability and negligence in tasks and project management due to a lack of due diligence on the part of the leadership (Hansen, 2018). Change project initiatives with weak leadership and poor management efforts are bound to fail. To implement sustainable change management in HIT, the vision of change must be led by a change agent (Gerwing, 2016) who is a visionary and transformational leader. Employees, staff members and healthcare professionals may find it difficult to accept the proposed change due to sentiments and expertise in the use and operation of existing systems. This resistance often poses a major threat to the execution and sustainability of the desired change. However, if the change is spearheaded and controlled (Ganta and Manukond, 2017) by a visionary leader, then this impediment can be diffused through skilful communication. Successfully leading change entails skilful communication such that all stakeholders, especially end-users, are thoroughly convinced that the development and introduction of a new HIT system will be more beneficial than the existing system and justify the timing of such change management (Mansaray, 2019). Employees are often fearful of the

introduction of information technology systems because many of them sustain the ideology that the introduction of sophisticated and innovative technologies with diverse possibilities of advancement and growth into an organisation threatens their job security. Hence, they become barriers to the proposed change. This legitimate concern needs to be addressed with utmost transparency by a visionary leader (Mahomed, 2016) who holds integrity in high esteem. The healthcare professionals who will be engaging the new system need to be assured, hence the need for a leader who has gained the trust and loyalty of employees. The implementation of change management in HIT requires a transformational and visionary leader with a track record of success in change management, especially as it relates to information technology (Alqatawenh, 2018). The success of the execution phase and the whole change initiative requires proven leadership. Although the change involves IT, its sustainability largely depends on the end-users. Therefore, it is important for such change management to be led by an individual or group of people with a deep understanding of people and who can empathize with employees (Zen, 2016) and often assure them that their interests are well-acknowledged, and their opinions are well-respected (Edmondson, 2019). The change management of HIT must be led by a leadership team that is charismatic and well-equipped to inspire the people and motivate all teams within the organisation to focus on achieving the ultimate goal (Jackson and Parry, 2008). Such influence is highly invaluable in any change effort.

Organisational/System Structure: This is one of the most significant internal factors that affect successful and sustainable HIT change management. A positive organisational structure can be a huge catalyst in the successful adoption of a technological innovation. It can also sabotage the sustainability of an IT innovation being adopted in an organisation or sector (Dekoulou and Trivellas, 2017). The introduction of HIT change management to the healthcare

setting can be thoroughly stifled and hindered if the structure within the system is too rigid (Jensen *et al.*, 2007) and such that hampers the flow of communication within the organisation. A complex organisation structure in which employees have no readily-available communication channels or means of contacting the top management will contribute to the failure of technological innovation and adoption. However, the ease of communication with the leadership and top management of an organisation leads to effective communication, which is potent enough to pull down barriers to technological change. According to Teece *et al.* (2016), a favourable organisational structure provides an enabling environment that encourages employees to be creative and innovative, which will enhance HIT systems and contribute to their sustainability. This will also contribute to a solution-oriented mindset among employees, motivating them to come up with new ways to solve HIT problems, hence leading to a sustainable HIT system (Joseph *et al.*, 2016). When the structure of a healthcare organisation is innovation-friendly, it will greatly boost the chance of successful and sustainable HIT change management (Rhee *et al.*, 2017). The structure of a social system or organisation impacts both the performance of the organisation and the acceleration of innovation adoption within the organisation (DeCanio *et al.*, 2000). The speedy adoption of technological innovation against all odds of resistance and barriers is possible if the organisation structure is characterised by a high level of integration, a result of the free flow of communication among individuals, teams and units (Gaspary *et al.*, 2018).

Organisational Culture: For a successful EHR installation, the organisation's culture is critical and is a significant determinant of the rate and frequency of innovation (Topol, 2019). It helps to develop positive interactions between end-users and leaders when the culture is open, supportive and ready for digital change. When an organisation has prior experience with a digital shift, this positive culture is promoted. Nevertheless, not all organisations will have this

experience (Sligo *et al.*, 2017). Other strategies for fostering a positive atmosphere conducive to effective EHR implementation include clinical leaders, for example, benefitting from effective leadership and management, which involves senior leadership demonstrating the implementation's importance by allocating resources (e.g., by purchasing infrastructures and the allocation of new roles) (Gunja *et al.*, 2018). Communicating the project's objective to all end-users in a clear and consistent manner fosters a positive organisational culture that impacts HER implementation (Dornan *et al.*, 2019). In a positive organisational culture that enhances sustainable EHR change management, rewards change with timely feedback (Gunja *et al.*, 2018). The demonstration of effectiveness and favourable outcomes from other sites, as well as the current one, is ideal for promoting the required culture (Quinlan, 2016). The essential organisational culture can be achieved by fostering an atmosphere that encourages collaboration and the sharing of knowledge, information and resources among organisations at all levels of the healthcare system (King's Fund, 2018).

Governance: This is an external factor critical to the successful implementation and sustainability of HIT change management. Governance entails the basic requirements, policies, regulations and legislation that forms the rule of engagement of HIT change management (Goodell *et al.*, 2015). It provides guidelines that should be strictly adhered to and followed when implementing or executing technological changes in the healthcare sector. Governance helps to set out required standards for best practices and promotes the security and confidentiality of patient data in health information networks (Smallwood, 2018). The regulatory body in charge of governance helps to provide the direction and alignment of HIT innovations and adaptation with the nation's healthcare goals and visions and helps to preserve the value systems of the national healthcare system. The functioning and effective governance by a regulatory body help to provide sets of standards and

requirements for vendors or suppliers of HIT or software for EHRs, which enhances interoperability among systems and across diverse healthcare organisations. Well-structured governance (Dong and Keshavjee, 2016) helps to increase and sustain clinical quality and service delivery efficiency. The implementation of an integrated HIT, especially an EHR on a national scale, requires a firm and credible regulatory body that provides due governance for the process from start to finish. The regulations and policies for change management in healthcare for HIT form the basis for compliance that aids in keeping the system and its operations within the boundaries of stipulated ethics (Rouzbahani *et al.*, 2019). Regular audits should be carried out by regulatory bodies to ensure the healthcare sector is not breaching the rules of engagement or being non-compliant, thereby ensuring alignment with due processes and promoting accountability.

Socioeconomic Factors: This is a vital external factor critical to the success and sustainability of change management in an organisation. It is mainly about the external environment (Obonyo and Kerongo, 2015) of the system or organisation within which a change is being implemented. To facilitate a sustainable integrated HIT system in the healthcare sector, there must be a favourable and stable socioeconomic system in place. For instance, the present quagmire of the COVID-19 pandemic constitutes a major challenge to the initiation, implementation or sustainability of an integrated HIT system. The pandemic has caused the need for change in the approach to leading change (Amis and Janz, 2020). The COVID-19 outbreak profoundly affected all industries, including the healthcare sector. Approaches and working styles have changed, and employee engagement has taken on a different form (Ferreras *et al.*, 2020). The pandemic has had a damaging impact on the nation's economy

and led to the accumulation of huge debt for the government. Hence, embarking on a substantive project such as an integrated EHRS in the country will be an almost impossible task, and if initiated in this hostile socioeconomic environment, the chance of its success and sustainability is low. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic (Kirby, 2020) put the healthcare sector mainly the NHS under a huge amount of pressure, a kind that it has never experienced. This stressful circumstance and pressure impacted by the external environment will thoroughly affect the success rate of HIT change management and sustainability, especially in its infancy.

Vendors: The Chief Information Officer and the Chief Clinical Informatics Officer may be in charge of engaging with vendors and developing a trusting relationship that benefits both parties (The King's Fund, 2018). Vendors presenting unrealistic timetables and inadequate chances to adjust EHR technology have been barriers to the productive collaboration between the healthcare organisation and the vendor (Maguire *et al.*, 2018). Having a vendor set firm timelines for the organisation, on the contrary, was considered to be positive by a UK hospital because it assisted them in delivering the EHRS on time (The King's Fund, 2018). There must be sufficient discussion-making and a shared success goal to develop a strong partnership between the organisation and the vendor. The vendor must be willing to share data and change the product (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020), and the vendor must be open to exchanging data and adapting the product. It is also a plus if the vendor has a track record of delivering successful goods and can recognise processes and change their product accordingly. In the procurement stage, decisions about the vendor's degree of assistance and training should be finalized.

Finance: Inadequate money is cited as a major impediment to EHR deployment, particularly among smaller businesses, and based on the scales and complexity levels of organisations, they may face high system integration implementation costs (Kruse *et al.*, 2016). There are significant upfront expenses involved in acquiring the necessary infrastructure, experienced employees and continuous costs to maintain and enhance the system to keep it operational (Gelsuga *et al.*, 2017). According to the literature, there is typically a delay in gaining any return on investment, as well as a loss of productivity during implementation, and it has been reported that half of all large IT projects run 45% over budget (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). Specification scope creep is a common cause of organisations surpassing their budgets. Thus, it is a smart idea to plan for contingency spending. Prior to procurement, a company must evaluate its financial resources, conduct a cost analysis to create a business case and avoid scope creep through extensive planning (Sligo *et al.*, 2017).

3.4 Conclusion

Information technology has immensely contributed to the enhancement and effectiveness of healthcare services and led to service improvement and increases in the speed of service delivery. However, HIT change management and adoption continue to involve bottlenecks. The issue of the sustainability of information technology systems implemented in the healthcare sector remains very challenging, especially with the implementation of an integrated EHRS in the UK. The fatal failure of a national EHRS system in the UK has left the NHS, the government and the management of the trusts shying away from embarking on such an extensive project without a system or strategy to allay their fears and guarantee not only successful implementation but also sustainable change management. In this chapter, a framework for the sustainable change management of IT systems in the healthcare sector has

been provided and comprehensively demonstrated. The systematic adoption of this framework will guild an integrated EHRS, once implemented in the UK, towards the achievement of its goal through its step-by-step phase guide that guarantees success and sustainability.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

Methodology can be referred to as the structured, theoretical or conceptual analysis of the procedures engaged in the study of a particular subject or phenomenon. It is composed of an in-depth analysis of the processes and ideologies of a study or subject field (Osuagwu, 2020). It incorporates quantitative and qualitative processes, stages of engagement, ideal patterns and theoretical models. It can be defined as the general or holistic approach to the whole phases and processes of a research undertaking (Abuhamda *et al.*, 2021). In the application and essence of methodology, it is not furnished to present solutions. Rather, it makes available theoretical structure for identifying and comprehending the procedures, practices and techniques applicable and best suitable for a given study (Chivanga and Monyai, 2020). Hence, research methodology is essentially and primarily about the systematic examination of a research problem (Jilcha, 2019). Simply put, research methodology consists of the techniques used and applied in research studies. It is a means of research guidance and shows how a research study is carried out. It provides adequate tools for research. It aids in the development of scientific observations through critical thinking and analytical procedures of investigation. It can be a daunting challenge to choose the most suitable research methodology for research work (Kieth, 2015). Therefore, it is crucial to ensure there is cohesion between the research approach and the research questions (Adedoyin, 2020). Research methodology enhances the process of research and further deepens knowledge in the field of study being researched. Also, it promotes detailed critical evaluation in research studies, helps in decision-making and increases the credibility of research work, boosting reader confidence in using the research results and applying its findings. A research

methodology is a systematic approach to conducting research work. Contained in this chapter is the investigation and analysis of the methodology applying Sanders *et al.*'s (2019) research onion shown in Figure 4.1, as it relates to the research objectives and questions stipulated in the first chapter of this study.

The first section of this chapter explores research approach and research philosophy, and the remaining part of this chapter details techniques and strategies with research designs. The contents of this chapter are, thus, outlined. Subsection 4.2 examines the research philosophy while the research approaches (i.e., inductive and deductive research) are detailed in Subsection 4.3. Subsections 4.4 and 4.5 enumerate the research strategies and research design, respectively. The methods of data collection, quantitative and qualitative research and research survey are all analysed in Subsection 4.6. Quantitative and qualitative data analysis methods are considered in Subsection 4.7, research quality is detailed in Subsection 4.8 and Subsection 4.9 contains a summary of the whole chapter.

Figure 4.1: The research onion

Source: Saunders *et al.*, 2019.

4.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy refers to the crux of a researcher's perspective of the world and their held beliefs and sentiments about them. It can be defined as the formulation of research characteristics, assumptions and cognitive prowess (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). It can be described as the assumptions and ideologies sustained by a researcher about a research subject, and the kind of research philosophy used in a study is largely a function of the field of knowledge that is being examined (Bianchi, 2021). It is what every researcher engages in whenever research is initiated, regardless of whether it is done consciously (by research experts) or unconsciously (by newbies). If the research involves knowledge development, then research philosophy is involved. It is important for researchers to develop their own awareness and align the understanding of their studies with their philosophical ideologies (Sapkota, 2019). There are three classifications of research philosophies based on philosophical assumptions that are known as paradigms: axiology, epistemology and ontology.

Ontological philosophy is about the character and form of reality and indicates the disparity between the idealism of reality and the view we uphold and sustain about reality with its impact on all our endeavours (Cohen *et al.*, 2018). Ontology is the study of reality's nature, which may be quite conceptual and theoretical. Although a researcher's ontological view may not align with the subject, it still influences the manner in which a researcher engages in studying (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). Its basis is on a paradigm perspective of truth and reality. Its centre of attention is on what exists. Ontological philosophy consists of relativism, critical realism, idealism and materialism (Chege and Otieno 2020).

Epistemological philosophy is about perspectives on knowledge, the things that make up reasonable, admissible and approved knowledge and effective means of communicating such

knowledge (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). Its significance cannot be undermined, even though it can be difficult to comprehend because of its abstract nature. Epistemology can be referred to simply as diverse knowledge held concerning reality. It is the investigation that clearly shows the difference between points of view and plausible rationales (Muhaise *et al.*, 2020). It can be described as a means of study that aims to provide clarity about the prospects of knowledge and its inception, limits, composition, procedures and justice and the means through which knowledge is acquired, established and modified. Mostly, perspectives of epistemology usually stem from ontological perspectives. Epistemology promotes the idea of prioritising processes and techniques in research studies (Zukauskas *et al.*, 2018). In modern times, the philosophy upheld by the climes of the West has been acclaimed to be the most genuine, unblended and unadulterated philosophy and has been proven to be the ideal nature of knowledge in its adoption and propagation (Saulauskas, 2012). Axiology refers to the implication of utility and principles of morality in the processes of a research study. It involves research reactions and the engagement of their personal values as well as those of the people participating in the research work (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). In business and management research studies, there are certain important philosophies that can be applied: positivism, pragmatism, critical realism, postmodernism and interpretivism.

According to Tomb and Pugsley (2020), the founding father whose research work brought positivism to the limelight was Auguste Comte. Positivism is the type of philosophy that suggests that the apprehension of human behaviour should be based on the experiences of experimentation, monitoring and thought processes and should be upheld as the sole authorised method of broadening knowledge and assimilating the nature of mankind (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). The assumption of positivism is that the subsistence of reality is free from human influence and ruled by unchanging laws (Rehman and Alharthi, 2016). It engages the

scientific method with facts that can be measured and monitored. Users of this research philosophy are not compelled to present value, and researchers' belief and value systems may be far-fetched. Its means of analysis are essentially quantitative.

Critical realism is a philosophy that embraces the existence of reality and the fact that reality is strongly influenced by factors such as gender, religion, culture, tribalism and politics and that a social system is formed as a result of the reactions among these factors. According to Saunders *et al.* (2019), critical realism-based research is value-oriented and considers the prejudices of cultural background and world perspectives. Researchers who use critical realism make frantic efforts to ensure that their prejudices and misconceptions are eliminated and that they objectively present their results with fairness and unbiasedness (Hürlimann, 2019). With this philosophy, many ascribe high regard and admiration to knowledge validated by people held in high esteem within a social system, but this idea of esteeming a source of knowledge while disregarding other sources calls for prompt investigation. Pragmatism is the philosophy that encourages the plurality of methods and integration of approaches to tackle issues being researched (Alise and Teddlie, 2010) and a focus on the provision of a solution to challenges, emphases and practices. It upholds the view that true knowledge is such that it enhances productive implementation. Postmodern philosophy focuses on amplifying the ideas and notions of the repressed and ostracised members of a social system by challenging the status quo and generally accepted world views (Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

Interpretivism is the philosophy of interpretivism. It is a counterreaction to the concept of positivism. Interpretivism purports that there is no iota of reality that exists independently of human interference (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). It negates the belief in the existence of a rigid and general means of communicating knowledge. Rather, it promotes multiple and diverse

means of forming reality (Bianchi, 2021). Interpretivism concentrates on narratives and interpretations. It contributes new knowledge and perspective to world realities. Interpretivism-based research is influenced by value. They are often interfered with researchers' sentiments, beliefs and value systems. They usually undergo critical and detailed examinations and engage in qualitative means of data analysis. The most suitable research philosophy identified for this research was interpretivism due to the essence of the research subject, which is mainly EHRs in the healthcare sector. This philosophy will help enlighten and provide more knowledge on HIT, especially the EHRs in the healthcare sector and foster the design and formulation of an unprecedented framework for a sustainable EHR implementation and change management. This will enable the provision and recommendation of implementation guidance for the leadership and management of the healthcare sector and academicians. Also, the choice to use an interpretivist philosophy was influenced by the Researcher's experience and previous studies in the field of business and management. As previously mentioned in Chapter 1, Section 1.0, the Researcher works in a role in within the NHS in which change management forms a critical aspect. Implementing new healthcare practices and technologies requires a careful approach to ensure smooth adoption and minimal disruption to patient care. This experience provides valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities involved in managing change, which is directly applicable to this research on EHR change management. Parallels between the strategies used in workforce change management and the methods employed in facilitating EHR adoption among healthcare professionals are drawn. This provides an important contribution to the methodology of this research.

4.3 Research Approach

The use of theory is often highly significant in a research study. Research works are hugely dependent on theories, and this is often reflected in research design, whether directly or indirectly. However, at the conclusion of a research study and upon the discussion of the research findings, the theory is usually made evident (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). The clarity of a theory at the initial phase of a research grants significant exposure to the essentiality of the research design. The logic (Grover, 2015) behind the selection of a theory is described as the approach to such a study, and this can be an inductive or deductive research approach. The validity of a research study can be enhanced when the approach is well described (Creswell and Plano-Clark 2018), hence the discussion of both inductive and deduction approaches in this part of the study.

The argument that theory is generated inductively leads to the conclusion that researchers can employ both styles of reasoning and can begin at any time (Bryman and Bell, 2018). Some extra inductive efforts may be required before creating a final theory to refine existing theoretical assumptions. This study employs mixed reasoning based on the assumption that deductive and inductive research methodologies may be employed effectively together. This duality is not symmetrical because the inductive approach is more powerful, but it does show a proclivity for deductive reasoning.

The researcher's observations and experiences with EHRSS aided in the understanding of the background for the inductive assumptions that underpin this study. Despite this, the study's deductive component is crucial to acquiring a better understanding of EHRS and establishing the Strategic EHRS Implementation Framework while driving the practice forward. The framework was created deductively on the basis of several theoretical assumptions researched in the literature reviewed in Chapter 2 and the literature gap relevant to existing ERM practices investigated in Chapter 3. To put

it another way, the framework is based on theories and literature. As a result, the researcher concluded that a deductive element should be included in the research design to operate as a validating and moderating check over the inductive technique based solely on observation.

4.3.1 Comparison of deductive and inductive research

Deductive approaches involve the derivation of conclusions from systems of pre-existing facts, data or knowledge. Therefore, the strength and credibility of the conclusion are dependent on the credibility of the set of parameters engaged (Ketokivi and Mantere 2010). The use of a deductive approach to research involves a gradual transition from an initial broad approach to the examination of details and intricate basics (i.e., the derivation of a hypothesis from a theory) (Dawadi, *et al.*, 2021). However, an inductive approach entails transitioning from a specific to a broad subject, for instance, the formulation of theories from basic experimental examination (Timans *et al.*, 2019). In the application of an inductive approach, researchers engage articles, works and journals with inductive background and critically examine them while researchers who use deductive approaches tend to engage published works or articles that are built upon existing and established theories that they have identified for use or testing (Wilkinson and Staley 2019). Inductive research is productive in the presentation of new findings and knowledge that may be disruptive. However, deductive research adds new knowledge and findings, but this knowledge is often not complementary to subsisting concepts and phenomena. In an inductive approach, the product of the research is a theory that is open to testing, challenges and criticism, but in a deductive approach, theory is used to conduct and steer research in the desired direction. The process is shown in Figure 4.2 below.

Figure 4.2: Deductive Approach Process

Source: Bryman and Bell (2018) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

As illustrated above in Figure 4.2, the deductive approach process is initiated with the investigation of an existing theory relevant to the theme of the study. Theory is further processed into hypothesis and subjected to a test of credibility with some data collection to aid the process (Kieth, 2015). Findings are hereby presented. This will either enhance the confirmation of the hypothesis or completely refute it. Afterwards, the theory can be revised as deemed fit by the researcher or other concerned or interested individuals. The reverse sequential application of this process is referred to as the inductive approach.

4.3.2 Integrating deductive and inductive approaches.

Both deductive and inductive approaches are significant. Although each is distinct in itself and may seem contradictory, each plays a vital role in research studies. Both approaches are often applied in research work. The fact that a theory is formulated through inductive means suggests the possibility of the combination of both inductive and inductive approaches. It is important to carry out further

inductive processes to validate and make subsisting phenomena credible (Hutchinson and Barrett, 2019). This research uses a combination of inductive and deductive reasoning because this combination has been described to be an efficient research approach (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). However, in this combination, it is essential that there is no parity in engagement and inductive reasoning is predominant and minimally complemented by the deductive approach (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The business and management background, experience in the use of HIT in the NHS and understanding of the concept of change management of the researcher forms the inductive basis for this study. However, to further broaden insight into EHRS change management and develop the sustainable HIT change management framework shown in Chapter 3, Subsection 3.5, Figure 3.9. The contribution of deductive reasoning cannot be undermined. The framework was developed through deductive reasoning from theories deduced from the literature review and gaps in the literature, hence the decision to include the deductive approach to control and guide the inductive reasoning, which is mainly observation-based.

4.4 Research Strategy

A research strategy can be described as the orientation by which research is conducted (Bryman and Bell, 2018). The strategies used for research have different forms that include, experiment, survey, archival research, case study, ethnography, action research, grounded research and narrative enquiry. An experimental strategy involves the use of variables and understudying the cause-and-effect interaction between them. Change is introduced to an independent variable, and the dependent variable is subjected to keen monitoring to determine whether it is being affected by the introduced change. A survey strategy involves the gathering of information or knowledge from a group of people through their responses to carefully formulated questions or inquiries (Mejia-Perez 2020). This is a common research structure, and with the vast platforms available via information technology, it can be easily and readily made available to numerous participants on different hand-held devices in the

shortest possible time. Survey research can be quantitative, qualitative or a mixture of both. According to Burns (2015), action research is the research strategy used in the investigation and examination of social issues, boosting egalitarian transformation and the enhancement of shared involvement. With this, knowledge is gained and problems are solved. Archival research involves the extraction of information or data from sources such as catalogue records, libraries and manuscripts. The research structure of grounded theory entails the application of a qualitative research method through an inductive reasoning approach for the formulation or establishment of a theory (Brown and Dueñas, 2020). Ethnographic research is used in the study and investigation of the culture of a group of people or society. It has its root in anthropology. This type of research requires researchers to engage in and interact with the theme or subjects of the research for direct understanding and experience (Sharma and Sarkar, 2019). Another research strategy is case study research.

Case study research describes a comprehensive and thorough exploration of a specific organisation, occurrence, social system, circumstance or concept. According to Dimitriou (2019), attempts to define *case study* have often led to the exact opposite of the intended goal (i.e., it further leads to the misunderstanding of what it really means). However, it is important that it is broadly defined in a general sense and not in specificity. This was suggested by Vashishth and Chakraborty (2019). Regardless, the need for a definition of *case study research* is vital because it is the means by which its difference and uniqueness can be understood, appreciated and applied. Hence, a case study can be defined as an empirical inquest that involves meticulously examining a current concept in contextual reality, most importantly when the margin separating the concept and the context is obscure (Yin, 2018). It can be defined as a research strategy used to produce or induce a detailed and exhaustive understanding of convoluted matters in an applicable and relatable manner (De-Xin, 2018). Cases vary in forms and settings. A case can, therefore, be a social system, a company, a person, a phenomenon or a function (Miles *et al.*, 2014). This research strategy has been applied in all fields of

study, including the social sciences, business and management, the healthcare sector and education. It is also acknowledged to be one of the earliest forms of qualitative research (Dimitriou 2019). The use of case study research helps to achieve a high degree of validity, a robust process for the development of new hypotheses and the broadening of knowledge and insight (Hutchinson and Barrett, 2019). It also provides an appreciable and significant level of flexibility to research, regardless of the field of study being researched (Cope, 2015). It is a research strategy that can be used for qualitative and quantitative research to aid in the understanding of complex issues (Han, 2018). Case study research has been criticised as being mainly theoretically relevant with little practical implications regarding knowledge, and it has been argued to be weak in validity and reliability (Mejia-Perez 2020). It is also argued that the applicability and robustness of case study findings can be neither attested nor refuted and, hence, may not be ideal for research (Bahrjdin, 2019). Case study research was selected as the strategy for this research due to the flexibility provided by case study research and the possibility of providing an enormous amount of knowledge both for academicians and top management on achieving sustainable change management. To ascertain its quality, this case study research is subjected to reliability, internal validity, external validity and construct validity tests (Han, 2014).

4.5 Research Design

According to Cresswell and Plano-Clark (2018), research design can be defined as the procedure of gathering, exploring, decoding and reporting data. It can be described as the organisation of the necessities required for data gathering and data analysis in a way that seeks to integrate the purpose of the research with practical application in the field, thereby establishing the relevance of the research study (Akhar, 2016). Research design can also be referred to as the strategic plan and investigative scheme for the exploration and provision of relevant answers to the research questions in a research study (Stroud *et al.*, 2020). In other words, research designs set the tone for the process of gathering the necessary data,

the methods required for the data collection and analysis, and the implication of this process on the provision of detailed and relevant responses to the questions set out in the research (Boru, 2018). It fundamentally aids in the choice of the most suitable framework for a research study. One's approach to research is a very important choice in research design because it is a major determinant of the potency and relevance of the information acquired for the study (Jilcha, 2019). An effective research design is one that provides answers to the research question. Upon the conclusion of a study, if the research questions have not been adequately answered with clarity, then the research design has failed woefully. There are three classifications of research designs, namely, quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods.

4.5.1 Quantitative Research

Quantitative research can be described as a research design and methodology that involves the analysis and evaluation of variables towards the achievement of an outcome in a research study (Apuke, 2017). It entails the analysis and examination of data that are numerical in nature through the application of proven statistical techniques for the purpose of providing requisite answers to the research questions. It can be referred to as the investigation of certain concepts or ideas using data gathering in numeric states and interpreting them through mathematical means (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). It is noteworthy to realise and understand that the core of quantitative research is numerical data. Essentially, it is the quantification of information through data gathering and processing through statistical applications for either upholding knowledge or contesting it (Park *et al.*, 2020). Quantitative research design can be used for both experimental designs and non-experimental designs. An experimental design is a research design used in one subject experiment or behavioural analysis application where an experiment is carried out on a single person or a few groups of people over a period (Vashishth and Chakraborty, 2019). However, in a non-experimental design, researchers primarily engage in comparing two teams or beyond in relation to an occurrence that has taken place.

It can also involve the application of correlational tools to examine and measure the extent of mutuality and correspondence between or among sets of variables (Creswell and Guetterman, 2019).

4.6 Qualitative Research

Qualitative research can be described as research involving case studies or the observation and monitoring of participants, culminating in the illustration and reporting of a phenomenon or concept. It is a research design that is often engaged when the philosophy of research being used is interpretivism (Park *et al.*, 2020). In this form of research, numerical data are not used. Rather, the data engaged are words, and much emphasis is placed on observing worldviews and deciphering phenomena and circumstances to gain insight into the daily lifestyles of individuals (Brown and Dueñas 2020). It focuses on proffering well-furnished insight into the character, experiences, inclination, sentiments and behaviours of humans (Mejia-Perez, 2020). Researchers engaging in qualitative research are often keen on expounding knowledge and gaining enlightenment on the social behaviour of people regarding their worldviews and accumulated experiences. The research approach that is often applied in qualitative research is the inductive approach, whereby the pursuits of researchers concerning a situation or specific subject are aimed at comprehensive investigation and the seeking of understanding (Levitt *et al.*, 2017). Qualitative research can be referred to as an effective research design that is applied in a regular and typical environment, which helps researchers in the enhancement and development of profound insight and germane knowledge through experiences garnered from personal engagement (Cresswell and Baez 2021). In social science and behavioural studies, it is the kind of research study that involves the gathering and use of data that are not numerical in form and subjecting these data to interpretation and evaluation to provide insight into the theme or subject of study (Dodds and Hess, 2021). It explores the

indigenous cognizance and insight of a specific event, the experiences of individuals, definitions and connections and societal affairs and peculiar elements that discount certain sets of individuals (Mohajan, 2018). Qualitative research is the examination and explanation of perceptions or views of individuals about various occurrences, and it encapsulates the thoughts and impressions of individuals in natural settings (Gentles *et al.*, 2015). The research strategies often used with qualitative research designs include narrative research, phenomenology, grounded theory, ethnography and case study. It is also used in historical research, discourse analysis and biography (Stroud *et al.*, 2020). Qualitative research designs have many merits that encourage researchers to apply qualitative methods and enhance their studies. One advantage of this is that it offers numerous amounts of relevant data and information regarding practical issues and individuals. It makes use of tools that aid in and promote problem-solving approaches to life and social issues. These tools include interviews, observations, questions and even notes through which adequate information is acquired from individuals (Mahir *et al.*, 2020). In qualitative research design, theories are generated from gathered data. This grants researchers flexibility (i.e., researchers have the privilege of modifying and adjusting theories where necessary based on their acquired data without interference or engagement of data from other investigators or researchers) (MacKean *et al.*, 2020). It is applauded for its distinctive feature of pictorial and word-based forms of data on which researchers can depend and further engage themselves as effective tools for the provision of comprehensive knowledge and profound understanding (Silverman, 2021). Qualitative research entails the observation and study of human behaviour, such as mindsets, thoughts, affections, conversations and perspectives. This tends to establish a working relationship and some sort of connection between researchers and their participants, thereby leading to genuine participation and authentic information and unrestricted involvement

because participants feel free to share their personal experiences, resulting in robust research results (Dimitriou, 2019). Qualitative research has been criticised for lacking generalisability because it focuses on a set of individuals or a phenomenon. According to Atkins and Wallac (2012), qualitative research can be easily influenced by researchers' emotions and moods, thereby compromising its reliability and credibility. Its replicability has also been heavily criticised due to the lack of the use of scientific methods in its exploration, especially by researchers using the constructivist philosophy (De-Xin, 2018). A detailed comparison between quantitative research and qualitative research is illustrated in Table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1: Comparison of quantitative and qualitative research

	Quantitative research	Qualitative research
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Allows accurate measure of variables ■ Structured & standardised ■ Statistical methods for data analysis ■ Generalisations ■ Objective ■ Measurable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Enhances description/theory development ■ Describes theories and experience ■ Allows deep understanding & better insight ■ Holistic and humanistic ■ Flexible ■ Value placed on participants' views ■ Interpretive ■ Subjective dimensions are explored
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Inflexible ■ Deterministic ■ Disregard of some important factors ■ Excludes subjective aspects of human existence ■ Assumption of an "objective" truth ■ Generation of incomplete understandings ■ Inapplicable to some immeasurable phenomena 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ No hard data, no clear measuring ■ Subjective, 'non-scientific' ■ Deep researcher involvement increases risk of bias ■ Small samples ■ Generalisation limited to similar contexts and conditions

Source: Althonayan (2003)

The design adopted in this research is qualitative research because the philosophy adopted in this study is interpretivism and the research strategy is that of a case study. It was also chosen because of its in-depth analysis, knowledge enhancement, participant involvement and perspectives and flexibility.

4.6 Data Analysis

Data analysis is fundamental to research studies and constitutes an integral part of any research work. It is the process in a study that involves critical examinations and evaluations that strongly impact the outcome of an investigation (Singh and Singh, 2015). Data analysis can be defined as a series of interrelated procedures that is primarily initiated with the aim of processing and digesting gathered data and effectively sorting it to answer the research questions or propose questions in situations in which research questions have not been predetermined (Zawacki-Richter *et al.*, 2021). Analysis in research methodology has been described as the mathematical or majorly statistical application of specific measures with inquests into similar features that are present among sets of data (Kothari, 2013). Data analysis encompasses various sets of operations and processes that aid in the description of research and the establishment of a phenomenon or knowledge through data. It is a generator of empirical relativity through pattern identification (Pandey and Pandey, 2015). Data can be gathered through primary or secondary sources. However, in raw states, these data can be enormous and encumbering, but through analysis, these data are rendered comprehensively succinct with no loss whatsoever (Singh and Singh, 2015). There are two main forms of data analysis that depend on the research design. They are quantitative data analysis and qualitative data analysis. The research design adopted in this research is qualitative in nature, hence the data analysis form used for this research study was qualitative data analysis.

4.6.1 Qualitative Data Analysis

Unlike in the past, qualitative data analysis has gained traction, additional prominence and wide acceptance (Nazmy, 2016). A qualitative research technique can be described as a series of activities that is used when solving the problems identified in a study in their natural settings and not through the extraction of subject themes into a simulated environment (Creswell and Creswell 2018). Qualitative analysis can be defined as a technique of research that is used for the interpretation of non-numerical data through an adequate and effective

procedure of pattern recognition and data deciphering (Stroud *et al.*, 2020). It can also be defined as the means of scaling down and condensing large amounts of qualitative data to identify a central theme and core meaning that is common to all the data gathered. This technique makes the extensive insight and profound comprehension of the subject or concept being studied available through the intuitive perspectives of participants (Akinyode, 2017). Qualitative data analysis is a difficult and convoluted process in a research study that has not been thoroughly explored by investigators, especially in the related published literature. While analysing qualitative data, many researchers are faced with a research trustworthiness challenge when presenting the findings of their research. Furthermore, the complexity of qualitative data analysis is compounded by inadequate comprehensive guides on how to analyse data gathered through interviews (Dodds and Hess, 2021). Qualitative research is significantly subjective, and most importantly, it is classified as interpretative. Investigators who use qualitative research methods are often deeply engaged in tasks and procedures. Their perspectives and affections are usually involved (Park *et al.*, 2020). The gathering of data for qualitative analysis involves data acquisition from numerous and large varieties of sources, all for the purpose of gaining insight and solving the research problem through the engaged participants. The results and findings that are yielded through qualitative means of analysis are free and devoid of mathematical or calculative processes but, rather, essentially through human behaviour and social influences, expressed in words (Al-Ababneh, 2020). The application of qualitative analysis in a research study provides great enlightenment on the theme of the research in its primary and original state of existence. There are numerous advantages to the use of qualitative data analysis. It helps to establish a strong sense of interaction between respondents and the researcher, thereby enhancing the means of communication between them (Akinyode and Khan, 2018). It gives a promising avenue for

the development of listening skills among researchers because this type of data collection involves the researcher's keen attention, meticulous identification of themes and recognition of words as respondents are being interviewed. Qualitative analysis also provides flexibility concerning the location of data collection from participants and gives the opportunity for researchers to read and observe participant reactions and other body signs that are not expressed in words, thereby enhancing the precision and correctness of the data gathered (Cresswell and Clark, 2018)

4.6.2 Qualitative Data Sampling and Saturation

Qualitative data sampling is defined as the process of achieving the objectives of a research study through the gathering of data from selected relevant sources (Gentles *et al.*, 2015). In the quest for relevant data, there are often numerous sources from which data can be collected. However, in a research study, it is not possible to approach all available sources or individuals to extract data. For instance, if the research study is about the healthcare sector in the United Kingdom, then it is not possible to approach all doctors, nurses or clinicians in all hospitals in the United Kingdom for data collection, hence the need for sampling (i.e., to scale down the humongous and inexhaustive source from which data can be gathered). Sampling can, therefore, be referred to as the selection of a portion of a general population for the purpose of research (MacKean *et al.*, 2020). The selection of these suitable groups or pertinent segments of the population is very crucial to the findings and results of the entire investigation. Therefore, effectiveness and accuracy are paramount and should not be undermined in the sampling process. In qualitative data analysis, sampling, as a term in itself, has been strongly contested and challenged as connoting a statistical technique or methodology rather than a critical analytical generalisation that constitutes no statical or numerical implication and, therefore, should be simply referred to as *selection* and not *sampling* (Zawacki-Richter *et al.*, 2021). There are different types of qualitative data sampling: convenience, theoretical, purposive, snowball, deviant case and homogeneous sampling, among others (Elmusharaf, 2016). Purposeful sampling was

selected by the researcher for this research study. Qualitative purposeful sampling can be defined as the process of choosing cases that are highly rich and robust in information for thorough research. Cases that are highly rich in information are those that provide a wealth of knowledge and deep insight into the subject matter being understudied (Patton, 2015). Interviews were used for data collection in this qualitative case study. It is not often straightforward to determine the sample size because this depends on the investigator's philosophical views and technique (Cresswell and Baez, 2021). Therefore, it remains a difficult task to choose a specific interview sample size for a good research study. There are suggestions to use a sample size ranging from 12 to 60 people, with a mean size of 30. This should be a sufficient sample size for a qualitative study involving interviews (Adler and Adler, 2011). A sample size of 50 has also been recommended for the highest level of postgraduate research (i.e., doctoral research) (Cresswell and Baez, 2021). However, due to the difficulty of specifying a particular figure as being the required sample size for this research, the investigator decided to use data saturation to determine the adequate number of respondents required for this research. This ensured the research was thorough, valid and, indeed, qualitative (i.e., of high quality in its findings). Data saturation can be defined as the state in which the accumulation of data from new sources no longer brings further enlightenment and knowledge about the subject being researched (Silverman, 2021). Hence, in the analysis of data in this research, the investigator placed great importance on the efficiency, effectiveness, quality and time required for analysis and not solely on the size of the sample. Data saturation has, therefore, been presented as the main basis for ascertaining the appropriate sample size for a qualitative research study because it will reveal when an adequate sample size has been attained (Creswell and Guetterman 2019). Data saturation provides a yardstick or measure, as well as intensity for the qualitative research being undertaken. Intensity refers to the time taken for an activity to transpire and the frequency of respondent engagement required to gain adequate insight (Timans et al., 2019). Although it is often stipulated that it is impracticable to determine the size of sample required for a qualitative research study beforehand (Gentles et al., 2015), there has been recognition of the importance of having a realistic sample size speculation before conducting

qualitative research, especially when applying for monetary assistance to undertake the research project (Cohen et al., 2018). For qualitative research based on grounded theory, a sample size of 25 is recommended (i.e., satisfactory saturation can be attained through 25 interview sessions with respondents (Charmaz, 2014). A sample size of fewer than 10 participants has been recommended for qualitative studies based on phenomenology if there is significant emphasis placed on intensity, but with less intensity, a sample size that is more than 30 is recommended (Cohen *et al.*, 2018). However, for a single case-study-based qualitative research study, depending on how complex the research subject is and the quality of data acquired from each respondent, the recommended sample size for achieving data saturation falls within the range of 25 to 50 (Yin, 2011). Therefore, the sample size selected by the researcher for this single case study was 25 interviewees. This enabled the researcher to pay close attention to the intensity and richness of data to attain the required data saturation level, therefore strongly aligning with the purposeful sampling method adopted for this study.

6.3 Qualitative Interview Data

Interviews in qualitative research can be described as interactions that are often one-on-one between a researcher and a participant for the purpose of garnering information about a particular subject of study being researched (Mattimoe *et al.*, 2021). Interviewing has been identified as the most prominent tool for amassing data in qualitative research. It is generally accepted and widely used. Hence, it is the tool of choice in this study (Duminda, 2019). Interviews are generally used as a technique for data gathering. They are often used for data accumulation and information sourcing in qualitative research from the perspectives, values and experiences of respondents or interviewees regarding the concept being studied (Linneberg and Korsgaard, 2019). There are different types of research interviews. These are structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews.

Structured interviews are conducted in a rigid and firm form, giving no room for flexibility in any manner. Participants are presented with questions in the exact same way concerning wording and sequence to ensure the comparability of the information acquired from all participants (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). Cautions are often taken to prevent deviation from the questions at hand. It is a formal form of interviewing that involves strict adherence and compliance to an interview schedule. Structured interviews are predominantly used in quantitative research.

Unstructured interviews should be conducted in a free-flowing manner without a predetermined questioning strategy or specifically targeted questions. There are no fine-tuned or detailed guides for the navigation of the interview, and it is often informal in nature. Although the researcher initiates the questions, the interview is often mainly driven by the respondents' responses, and the researcher can then follow through with further relevant questions (Harding, 2018). It is often used in the research of studies in fields that have not been thoroughly explored.

4.6.3 Semi-Structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews may follow specific interview schedules, yet they provide a reasonable level of flexibility in their delivery. Through a questioning process that is open-ended, it gives room for the consideration of responses that were not been envisaged while still ensuring that interview is conducted within the scope of the central theme (Al-Ababneh, 2020). It provides the allowance for the pursuit of questions that have not been predetermined but that come to light during the interview, thereby enhancing the validity and quality of the research. The relevant topics, subjects or matters revealed by participants can be further examined in the interviews. Conducting semi-structured interviews permits the expression of questions in different means that will give proper understanding to the respondents. Semi-structured interviews were conducted by the researcher in this study.

4.6.4 Interview Data Analysis

The analysis of the data in a qualitative study is usually done independent of statistical tools, unlike in quantitative research, which often involves the use of some computer applications, such as SPSS or MATLAB. However, in this research, the interview data were analysed using Excel without any numerical computations. According to Yin (2018), there are diverse tools that can be used to analyse data in qualitative research. The thematic analysis used in this research is identified as one of the analysis tools for interview data.

Thematic analysis was used in this research because it was the most fitting method for engaging in research that entails a quest to observe, understudy and acknowledge certain ideologies, occurrences, concepts, reasonings and practices (Braun and Clark 2012). As is the case in this research, which involves the investigation of change management specifically in the EHRS in the NHS., thematic analysis is structured to highlight and explore consistently reoccurring patterns, interpretations or themes, hence the term *thematic analysis*. Thematic analysis can, therefore, be defined as a qualitative method of analysis that involves the recognition and identification of significantly prevalent concepts or characteristics within a dataset (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017).

In practical engagement, thematic analysis steps are usually interconnected and often necessitate the sustained evaluation and examination of data, giving rise to logical and rigorous inquisition. To allow for accurate and in-depth analysis, it is crucial to ensure the precise description of the interview for each participant through a process of data logging (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). This can be achieved through audio-visual coverage of the interview process and thereafter subjecting the recorded sessions to effective transcription. It is important to seek the confirmation of the participants about their responses and that they

should remain unmodified. This helps enhance the validity of the research in general (Mejia-Perez, 2020). The categorisation of the common themes and ideologies in the transcript can be achieved through coding. Coding can be described as the process of disintegrating and categorising text and accumulated data for the purpose of illustrating and establishing the common themes therein (Creswell and Guetterman, 2019). It essentially focuses on data reduction by grouping transcribed information into reasonable and comprehensive groups through the framework of coding. It can simply be referred to as the allocation of tags to various text segments with various problem sets. Data coding can also be defined as the investigation of the variances and resemblances among collected data (Miles *et al.*, 2014)

4.7 Research Validity and Reliability

Research validity encapsulates the degree to which acquired data provides the information needed for the subject of study being examined or researched (Sürücü and Maşlakçı, 2020). Validity can also be referred to as the estimation of the degree of truth regarding an ideology or deduction from a study. It is paramount that the analysis of data and its preceding collection should immensely diminish prejudice or unwarranted sentiments, thereby further enhancing the reliability of research outcomes (Lopes *et al.*, 2021). It is crucial to use an effective strategy in the establishment of the validity of a research study. This is referred to as a validity strategy. A validity strategy is simply the criteria for a research to be upheld as being valid enough for acceptance or adoption. There are five critical criteria of validity, namely, triangulation (Fusch and Ness, 2017), corpus construction, comprehensive description, surprise and respondent reactions.

Triangulation covers the interconnections that exist between the knowledge or findings deduced from acquired data from all the various sources for the provision of a broader and

deeper insight into the subject matter, thereby enhancing its reliability. It is a prominent criterion in the establishment of the validity of research results (Olson *et al.*, 2016). Corpus construction refers to the sample size used for a research study, whether quantitative or qualitative. When using a qualitative method, the quality of the research can be consolidated through data saturation, fostering the reliability and validity of the results (Hayashi *et al.*, 2019). Comprehensive description makes it possible for non-participants and the general public to have a clear understanding of the study, thereby enhancing smooth familiarisation with the context and enabling transferability (Lopes *et al.*, 2021). This also has a huge impact on the reliability of a research study. Surprise criterion refers to the innovative element of the research study. The research must present new knowledge and unprecedented findings that contribute to the general and existing pool of knowledge in the field being researched. This improves both the validity and reliability of a study. The last criterion identified in a validity strategy is confirmability. This refers to respondents' reactions (i.e., the feedback of participants). Confirmability involves the verification of the agreeability between the responses of participants and the information realised by the investigator after analysis. Furthermore, as described in Table 4.2 below, there are different strategies a researcher can adopt to achieve research validity.

Table 4.2: Strategies for Research Validation

Validation strategies	Adoption in the present research
	<u>Peer review</u> : This research was supervised by academic researchers with extensive industry experience, who reviewed the data and research process (Lincoln and Guba, cited in Creswell & Miller 2000)
Research collaboration	<u>External audit</u> : The researcher consulted an auditor external to the study (with no connection to this research), who examined the process (research steps, decisions, activities) and product (narrative accounts, conclusions) of the study to determine its accuracy
The researcher solicits participants' views of the credibility of the findings and interpretations	The author has published research in international and national sources, and at PhD-related conferences
Rich and thick description	Qualitative data collected in semi-structured interviews supported by the findings of the quantitative research survey
Randomisation	Participation in the quantitative survey in each organisation was determined randomly to ensure that there was no systematic bias in either sample group
Sample sufficiency	Samples were sized appropriately to achieve statistically significant and reliable results. Additionally, they consisted of participants who were in the best position to represent or have knowledge of the research topic
Sequential data collection & analysis	Collecting and analysing data concurrently created a mutual interaction between data and analysis

Source: Creswell and Creswell (2018)

The validation strategy adopted by the researcher in this research is sample sufficiency, as appropriately described in Table 4.2

Reliability can be defined as the measure of the repeatability, consistency or stability of research results or findings (Sürücü and Maşlakçı, 2020). A research study must be reliable and must always stand the chance of yielding the same results when subjected to the same routine of application at random. In qualitative research, it can further be described as the thoroughness and due diligence engaged in the acquisition and analysis of gathered data, the detailed and comprehensive presentation of the findings and the crucial decision-making involved, which hugely enhance the precision and accuracy of the research (Bahariniya *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, as described in Table 4.3 below, there are different strategies a researcher can adopt to achieve research reliability.

Table 4.3: Strategies of research reliability

Reliability strategies	Adoption in the research
Methodological coherence	The researcher confirms the congruence between the research questions and the components of the method (Morse et al, 2002)
Defining consistent sets of questions for research interviews and surveys	The researcher determines a set of measurable questions linked directly to research objectives
Think theoretically	The researcher utilises new ideas emerging from data and reconfirmed in new data; this gives rise to new ideas that, in turn, must be verified in data already collected
Recording and transcribing research interviews	All interviews are recorded to present more reliable evidence and avoid any bias which might happen if the researcher attempted to remember the conversations with the participants

Source: Creswell and Creswell (2018)

The reliability strategy adopted by the researcher in this study was defining consistent sets of questions for the interviews and recording and transcribing each interview, as appropriately described in Table 4.3

4.8 Summary

This chapter contains a detailed and extensive explanation of the means by which this research was carried out. The research philosophy engaged in the research was interpretivism. The research approach applied by the researcher in the study involved the use of the combination of both inductive and deductive reasoning because this has been described as an efficient research approach. The research technique used by the researcher was qualitative in nature, and the primary tool for data collection was interviews with a sample size of 25 people. Data saturation was achieved. The interviews were semi-structured. The collection of primary data was enhanced by sources of data that are secondary in nature which were illustrated in the literature review in Chapter 2. The process used to analyse the interview data is also presented in this chapter. Furthermore, the significance, validity and

reliability of the study were discussed to promote the feasible usefulness of the study through the embedded quality. This provides the bedrock for the new addition to the business and management field, as well as academia, in the new framework—the Proposed Healthcare Implementation Guidance Framework in Figure 3.9 for sustainable HIT change management formulated by the researcher.

CHAPTER FIVE: QUALITATIVE DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

As a sequel to the methodology approach and applications detailed in Chapter 4, the emphasis of Chapter 5 is, therefore, on the examination of the collection of the qualitative data through semi-structured interviews and the analysis of the accumulated data. The qualitative analysis of data significantly entails the identification of common themes, reoccurring phenomena and ideas and the recognition of patterns and unprecedented concepts that enhance existing processes or subject matter (Abuhamda *et al.*, 2021). The major tasks elucidated in this chapter involve data reduction or trimming, recognising and pointing out important interrelations and rendering pensive conclusions essential to the research subject.

Essentially, this chapter aims at capturing the analysis of the collected interview data and using empirical proof to corroborate and substantiate the EHRS implementation framework formulated and presented in Chapter 3, Section 3.5, Figure 3.9. Thematic analysis is the qualitative analytical tool used in this study. The data that was collected through interviews were analysed using thematic analysis, as discussed in Chapter 4.

5.2 Data Collection and Sampling Methods

This section outlines the methodology employed by the Researcher to gather interviewees for the Electronic Health Record System (EHRS) research using a combination of Purposive and Convenience sampling techniques. Due to the NHS Trust's unavailability caused by the overwhelming nature of the COVID-19 pandemic during its peak period, alternative approaches were necessary to ensure data collection and the study's success.

The combination of Purposive and Convenience sampling was chosen as a practical approach given the unique circumstances. Purposive sampling allows for the targeted selection of participants who possess specific characteristics, knowledge, or experiences relevant to the EHRS study, while Convenience sampling helps to ease the challenges associated with participant recruitment during a time of crisis when the NHS Trust was overwhelmed.

Implementation of Purposive Sampling:

- **Identification of Relevant LinkedIn Profiles:** The researcher sought LinkedIn profiles of professionals within the healthcare and health informatics fields. These individuals were identified based on their job titles, qualifications, and work experiences related to EHRS implementation, management, and usage.
- **Contacting Potential Interviewees:** Once the relevant LinkedIn profiles were identified, the Researcher reached out to potential interviewees via LinkedIn's messaging platform. A personalized message explained the purpose of the research, its importance in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the researcher's interest in their expertise.
- **Selection Criteria:** Participants were selected based on their level of expertise in EHRS, their involvement in healthcare settings, and their willingness to share their insights on the EHRS implementation and usage during the pandemic.
- **Follow-Up:** For those who expressed interest in participating, the Researcher conducted further communication to schedule interviews, provide consent forms, and ensure that potential interviewees met the necessary criteria.

In addition to the purposive sampling approach, the Researcher utilized convenience sampling by leveraging on existing professional network and personal connections to identify

potential interviewees. Colleagues and acquaintances with relevant experience and expertise were approached to gauge their interest in participating in the study.

All potential interviewees were provided with detailed information about the research, including its objectives, methods, confidentiality measures, and their rights as participants. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant before the interview. In order to protect participants' privacy and confidentiality, all interviews were conducted anonymously. Pseudonyms or unique identifiers were used during data analysis and reporting to ensure participants could not be identified.

The combination of Purposive and Convenience sampling proved to be an effective and pragmatic approach to gather interviewees for the EHRS research project during the challenging period of the COVID-19 pandemic peak when NHS Trust unavailability was a significant obstacle. The method allowed for the inclusion of diverse perspectives, insights, and experiences, which enriched the overall findings and contributed valuable information to the EHRS research.

5.3 Thematic Analysis of Interview Data

Thematic analysis is an analytical method that has been widely adopted in various fields, such as healthcare, education and sports (Braun *et al.*, 2017). One of the major characteristics of thematic analysis is that it is flexible in its application and can be deployed in diverse frameworks with different research designs and for varying sample sizes and expansive

research questions. Due to this distinguishing attribute of malleability, Clarke and Braun (2013) described thematic analysis as having no affiliation or inherent attachment to any form of research paradigm or perspective. Hence, it has been referred to as being more of a method and not exclusively a methodology. The application of thematic analysis aids in identifying the connections between ideas and juxtaposing these findings with repetitive data. Furthermore, the application of thematic analysis in qualitative research comprises six comprehensive guidelines critical to successful deployment and the generation of credible results (Braun and Clarke, 2019). These steps include familiarisation with data, code generation, exploring and finding themes, theme examination, identifying and defining themes and theme reporting. The essence of these steps is the significance of their design. They were formulated and structured to be iterative or looping and not a rigidly linear approach and application. The researcher can return to the initial step when data is updated or there is a significant theme that calls for consideration with an additional or fresh inquiry is identified (Kiger and Varpio, 2020). In this study, the researcher adeptly adopted thematic analysis in the derivation of common themes in the data acquired through interviews with respondents. This has helped in the investigation of the causes of unsustainable change management for the integrated EHRS in the NHS.

Figure 5.1: A Flowchart for Thematic Analysis

Source: Researcher

The starting point is familiarisation with the data. The process of familiarising oneself with data can be described as an act of intense acclimatisation and conscious absorption of data collected through observations and conversations, such as interviews, whereby comments were made regarding the plausible deficiencies of a predefined concept. Data familiarisation is a fundamental step in thematic analysis that provides the basis for the credibility of a dataset and the outcome of the entire qualitative analysis (Yin, 2018). It is a process that must be approached with the utmost concentration and relentless diligence because it is often time-consuming and enormous. It is imperative for the researcher to pay close attention to details at this stage of data analysis because omissions and errors could be detrimental to the analysis. Great caution must be taken by the researcher at this stage to not be overfamiliar with the phenomenon or research subject because overconfidence or approaching the analysis with preconceived notions may result in missing important findings (Braun and

Clarke, 2019), hence the need for the researcher to keep an open mind use an objective approach and engage in a keen and thorough familiarisation with the collected dataset with required meticulousness to attain the desired accuracy. The process of familiarisation with data involves the frequent and rigorous perusal of datasets captured in notes, jottings, observations and media. It also involves the transcription of audio or audio-visual recordings of interviews with each respondent and repeatedly reading each transcription to achieve the desired level of familiarity (Bree and Gallagher, 2016). In cases in which the research is English-language-based and some of the interviews are conducted with non-English speaking respondents, it is important that such interview sessions are first translated into the English language before transcription is done. Furthermore, this process entails the careful and frequent observation of the body language of respondents by watching recordings to enable an enhanced understanding of the participants' comments and responses. This process often proves to be tedious and quite extensive, but it is important for accurate and credible data analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019).

In this study, the interview sessions were audio-visual recorded with the consent of the participants, and during each interview, ongoing notes were also taken as part of the interview process. At the end of each interview session, the researcher transcribed and verified the transcription with each respondent for confirmation. Also, when each interview session concluded, the researcher further wrote observations that may have been significant in the analysis of data (Mattimoe *et al.*, 2021). The transcription was based on the notes written and the audio-visuals and was rigorously and comprehensively carried out for analysis purposes. The researcher appraises data transcription as a critical process that drives quality research and enhances the detailed vetting of participant responses. The transcription process further bolsters the validity and reliability of the analysis of data by alleviating the

impact of the researcher's values and prejudices in the entire process. Hence, the transcripts of the entire interview session were exhaustively checked and revised to the guaranteed correctness and exactness of the collected interview data. A transcript sample is shown in Appendix 4

Code generation follows data familiarisation. According to Creswell and Baez (2021), an efficient coding process involves the examination of transcribed data and their classification into common themes that depicts the idea or concept being understudied. The code generation stage starts after the researcher has examined and familiarised himself or herself with the dataset and accompanying information, having thought critically about the information encapsulated within which calls for prompt attention (Braun and Clarke, 2021). This stage includes the initiation of code generation from the information and transcribed data. The researcher had to keep returning to the data, especially in the analytical phase of this research. Coding in qualitative research can be referred to as a procedure that involves the thorough introspection of data through thoughts and rumination (Robinson, 2021). The researcher has been able to break down data and direct attention towards certain outstanding data features through coding. It has also helped a great deal in transitioning from raw unprocessed and unrefined data to the discovery of specific themes and meanings embedded in the data. The researcher has recognised and pointed out significant parts of the transcriptions. This text has been labelled to identify the specific themes they represent in the data. The researcher carefully examined each datapoint with keen attention, examining each for any iota of an underlying theme that may be significant to the research (Braun and Clarke, 2021). Measures were taken to avoid code ambiguity and unnecessary layers of coding that may impact the productivity of the code through complexities. Various levelled coding permits the researcher to analyse transcripts at changing levels of specificity with higher

arrange codes giving an outline and point-by-point and lower arrange codes permitting for refinements to be made inside and between cases (Maher *et al.*, 2018).

The next step after code generation is theme searching. This involves spotting themes that resound across the whole dataset that has been collected. The next stage in the thematic analysis of the data in this research study is the reviewing of the identified themes (Braun & Clarke, 2019). This involves refining the themes and checking whether the themes are, indeed, relevant and cover the essence of the research and eradicating any form of duplication or redundancy. Afterwards, the themes were named and defined, and a report was finally produced.

Table 5.1: Demographics of Respondents

RP	Role	Experience (year)	Healthcare organisation	Size of organisation	Location of organisation
1	EPR configuration analyst	1–5	NHS Trust	2,000–5,000	London
2	EHR Transformation Director	15–20	Private Healthcare	1–500	Ide Hill
3	EHR Consultant	10–15	NHS Trust	2,000–5,000	Watford
4	Senior EPR Configuration Analyst	15–20	NHS Trust	2,000–5,000	London
5	EPR Configuration Manager	1–5	NHS Trust	>10,000	London
6	EHR Senior Interface Analyst	5–10	NHS Trust	5,000–10,000	London
7	EPR Application Analyst	1–5	NHS Trust	>10,000	Manchester
8	EHR Clinical System Analyst	1–5	NHS Trust	>10,000	London
9	EHR Implementation Specialist	15–20	NHS Trust	>10,000	Liverpool
10	Healthcare Tech Sales Director	10–15	Private Healthcare	1–500	Manchester
11	EHR Implementation Manager	15–20	NHS Trust	>10,000	Slough
12	EHR Implementation Analyst	5–10	NHS Trust	5,000-10,000	Englefield

13	EHR Transformation Director	10–15	Private Healthcare	1–500	Watford
14	EPR configuration Manager	5–10	NHS Trust	5,000–10,000	London
15	EPR Programme Manager	5–10	NHS Trust	>10,000	London
16	EPR Readiness Director	15–20	NHS Trust	>10,000	London
17	Head EHR Transformation	15–20	NHS Trust	>10,000	London
18	EPR Change Lead	5–10	Private Healthcare	1-500	Leeds
19	EPR Consultant	10–15	NHS Trust	>10,000	London
20	EPR Delivery Manager	15–20	Private Healthcare	1–500	Birmingham
21	EHR Implementation Manager	5–10	NHS Trust	>10,000	London
22	EHR Business Change Lead	5–10	NHS Trust	5,000–10,000	Devon
23	EPR Implementation Manager	10–15	NHS Trust	5,000–10,000	Cambridge
24	Head of EHR Programme	10–15		NHS Trust	>1,000London
25	EHR Project Support Manager	15–20	NHS Trust	5,000–10,000	London

Source: Researcher

Table 5.1 above shows the summary of the description of the demographics of the twenty-five respondents using the information provided by each of them and based on their response to the interview questions, mainly questions 1–4. These questions detail respondents' roles in their organisations, years of experience about the size and type of healthcare organisation they work for.

Figure 5.2: EHR Challenges (based on interviewee responses)

Source: Researcher

As shown in Figure 5.2, over 26.20% of the respondents mentioned that ineffective change management is one of the major barriers to EHRs change management and sustainability. Only 9.8% of the interviewees alluded to the fact that inadequate data security and privacy is a challenge in EHRs. Also, 26.20% of the interviewees claimed that the inefficient interoperability of EHRs is a fundamental challenge that has maligned the productivity and performance of EHRs. Poor system installation was mentioned as an EHR challenge by 3.3% of the interview population.

Figure 5.3: Pie Chart of EHR configuration components

Source: Researcher

Figure 5.3 above shows the frequency distribution of the components critical to the execution and configuration phase of EHR change management based on the interview results. A total of 23.3% of the participants claimed training employees (i.e., end-user clinicians) is important and contributes to the success of EHR implementation. A total of 21% of participants responded that flexibility and local adaptability are essential in the execution phase. A total of 11% of the participants identified interoperability as a critical element in the successful configuration of EHRs. Furthermore, data security infrastructure was highlighted by 17% of the participants as a vital EHR configuration component. 21% of the participants stated that acceptance of use by end-users is the key to the EHR execution phase.

Figure 5.4: Frequency Distribution of EHR Optimisation

Source: Researcher

Figure 5.4 illustrates the frequency distribution of the EHR monitoring phase based on interviewees' responses. 27.40% of the interviewees claimed that feedback is essential to the optimisation of an EHRS and ensuring its sustainability. 19% of the interviewees identified key performance indicator (KPI) as an essential element in monitoring an EHRS and ensuring its sustainability. Also, 19% of the interviewees said that technical support for staff members, especially end-users, will help drive the optimisation and sustainability of the system. Ongoing coaching was mentioned by 12% of the interviewees as an important EHRS optimisation factor.

5.4 Identified Themes

The themes identified and reported in the research data analysis impact the operational procedure involving the development and assimilation of EHRSs into healthcare processes (Creswell and Baez, 2021). The impact of each theme discussed here is genuinely significant

to EHR implementation, but the magnitude of impact each has is dependent on the scale, nature and kind of organisation involved (Grood *et al.*, 2016). The themes include transformational leadership, effective communication, workforce development and support, end-user involvement and system integration.

5.4.1 Theme I: Transformational Leadership

According to Caroline *et al.* (2018), transformational leadership plays an extremely important role in the successful management of an integrated EHRS. Transformational leadership helps set a vision for change in place and the focus required to drive the vision to realise the desired accomplishment. It also enables personnel to get on board and give their required input to ensure the success of the EHRS (Sligo *et al.*, 2017). Transformational leaders give room for and establish avenues for innovation, creativity and the generation of new concepts or revitalization of existing means of doing things (Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019), hence the need for transformational leadership in the implementation of an integrated EHRS for the optimisation of healthcare delivery. This style of leadership is key and ultimately appropriate in EHR change management, boosting a patient-centred, result-oriented system with dedicated and invested employees (Hamed, 2021). This type of leadership is mainly change-oriented, and considering the fact that the implementation of an integrated EHRS involves a comprehensive change approach, it is appropriate to engage transformational leadership in the pursuit of such an initiative. In healthcare settings, transformational leaders are required at the C-suite portfolios and as clinicians champions (Gesulga *et al.*, 2017). Leadership teams are required to work together to accomplish the goals associated with the implementation of an integrated EHRS. These sorts of leaders help drive successful EHR change and change employee perspectives and notions through influence (Ross *et al.*, 2016). This is because some employees are resistant to change, especially when it involves technology. However, through

transformational leadership, these employees can be influenced to realise the need, benefits and usefulness of the integrated EHRS for themselves first and the organisation in general (Alqatawenh, 2018), and this can further enlighten them on the importance of their willingness and acceptance of the success of the project. Respondent 1 (RP 1) alluded to the importance of leadership in the response below:

Respondent 1 observed the following:

In my organisation, transformational leadership played a critical role in the implementation EHR. Recently, my organisation embarked on the initiation of an Integrated Electronic Health Record System with two other NHS Trust in London. The first decision of top management was to employ key transformational leader to spearhead the project and influence the mindset of employees, this helps greatly in setting the tone for effective change management and implementation of EHRS. And it helps in setting the first stones in the management of the project.

Transformational leadership helps promote cognitive stimulation among workforces (Gill and Borycki, 2017). As RP 1 stated, cognitive stimulation is an analytical approach to the examination of processes and how they can be improved. It is the bedrock of innovation (Cresswell and Sheikh, 2013) and creativity, and it propels critical thinking. Cognitive stimulation is, therefore, vital to EHRS change management, which often impacts the day-to-day activities of clinicians and processes within a healthcare organisation. In the management of an integrated EHRS, leaders must ensure the system thrives by encouraging their followers to strive for creativity, improved performance (Saeed and Mughal, 2019), problem-solving approaches and forward-thinking to avoid relapse (Nguyen *et al.*, 2017). The introduction and development of new EHRS in a hospital trust will require the corresponding development of

a new workflow in operations within the hospital to synchronise and accommodate the EHRS being implemented (Adriansyah *et al.*, 2020). This requires critical thinking and cognitive stimulation, and with transformational leaders at the helms of affairs, such processes prove to be seamless. Respondent 1 alluded to the importance of leadership.

5.4.2 Theme II: Effective Communication

Communication can be considered an important tool in the organisation, management and leadership of all groups or teams (Musheke and Phiri, 2021) associated with the EHR change management within a healthcare setting. It is an essential catalyst in the management of expectations, assignment of tasks, dissemination of information and diffusion of knowledge (Merhi, 2015). Communication can be described as the adhesive element that cohesively helps sustain the integration of an entire organisation towards the accomplishment of the desired goal. Employee dedication to the change management of an EHRS can be greatly enhanced through effective communication and help overcome change barriers and provide clarity and answers to employee doubts and fears. One of the factors responsible for the lack of sustainability and failure of EHR change management or initiatives is ineffective communication. Effective communication (Safdari *et al.*, 2015) helps to build and foster trust between the top management and employees, which results in the acceptance of EHR use by clinicians and the sustainability of EHR change management through the transparency of information exchange (Merhi, 2015). It is, therefore, paramount that healthcare organisations ensure the enhancement of effective communication in the deployment of integrated EHR change management. Furthermore, effective communication refers to excellent and constant oral or written information about intended visions and goals. It details the need for EHR change management, the threats and weaknesses that will persist if the initiative is ignored and states the clear objectives of the EHR change management being embarked upon (Pai *et*

al., 2021). Effective communication aids in presenting the means by which the organisation aims to support personnel to achieve the desired success in detail. It also helps in the management of stakeholder expectations and the efficient engagement of vendors, suppliers, patients, clinicians and other stakeholders (Swaminathan *et al.*, 2020). Respondent 12 also establishes this in the following response:

The big one was constant communications amongst the teams so, a project manager sometimes leading a weekly meeting, and that would involve all the stakeholders, the different teams within the organisation and between different analyst teams and then the different conditions. The managers come just to give heads up as to what we've worked on, what expectations are so that way if there are any issues or if we are going off tangent that is captured earlier on in the project rather than later because there have been issues where things have been so, and we had to change it completely because it was a misunderstanding.

Effective communication is crucial during EHR implementation and change management and also plays an essential role in the sustainability and enhancement of the system after it goes live. It is significant throughout the life of an EHR and must be continually sustained. According to Robinson *et al.* (2019), communication can even be improved within a healthcare organisation through a well-engaged EHR (i.e., EHRs can help boost communication among clinicians). Dendere *et al.* (2019) found that enhanced communication is one advantage of EHR. Studies have shown that the smooth authorisation to access patient records and prompt messaging on the EHR has strengthened effective communication among the healthcare professionals within a healthcare organisation or settings (Noblin *et al.*, 2013, O'Malley *et al.*, 2015).

5.4.3 Theme III - Workforce Development and Support

According to Kruse *et al.* (2016) and Ratwani *et al.* (2016), the empowerment of employees through the provision of adequate EHR training and computer literacy education is critical to the implementation and change management of EHRs. Nonetheless, the efficacy and productivity of staff training are largely functions of the proficiency and expertise of the instructors, content and modules selected for training, training techniques and scheduling this process of knowledge transfer and empowerment when the EHR is about to go live (Boonstra *et al.*, 2021). Gill and Borycki (2017) stated that EHR training should not be a one-off occurrence. Rather, it should be continuously catered to new employees and improving the efficiency of EHR use among existing employees (Ratwani *et al.*, 2016). Computer competencies and information technology skills, along with staff individual peculiarities, attributes and quality, immensely influence the success of EHR projects (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2018). As stated in Subsection 3.5.2, HIT failures can be attributed to the incompetency of end-users. However, the root cause of this ineptitude is mainly poor training. The evaluation of the technology awareness and computer competencies of clinicians gives researchers avenues along which to measure and articulate the number of staff that will need fundamental training in the use of computers before receiving general and comprehensive training on EHR use (Salleh *et al.*, 2021). Although the acceptance of the use of the system can be impacted by employee expertise and experience, gender and age, individual attributes like proneness to creativity or change and analytical and problem-solving skills promote successful outcomes for EHRs (Gesulga *et al.*, 2017). Nevertheless, impractical and unworkable technology has been described as one of the major barriers to EHR change management (Sligo *et al.*, 2017). The lack of basic computer skills, such as the skills required

to use keyboards, mouses and the internet affects EHR change management and sustainability (Kariotis and Harris *et al.*, 2019). RP 17 mentioned a similar issue:

Some people are so computer illiterate that they click with their thumb, like in my class I have people that click with their thumb. I understand how tough it is for them for those clinical members of staff, where you're having to push on this very complex system onto them. You know, that's where you have to give a little bit more extra love and support to certain people. I had it just yesterday actually had it yesterday when I was training a couple of consultants, there was a lady, obviously, she was a neurology consultant; she is incredibly intelligent. Yeah so, but you could see the struggle there; what we need to do more of is an IT competency or it sort of literacy training evening before you even do the HR training.

An adequate training support system and modules that involve roleplays and are essentially tailored to equip clinicians for the application of the EHRs and engagement of new workflows are crucial. The communication of the change vision to staff members is not sufficient in itself. It is important for staff members to be shown what is required and expected of them. Hands-on interventions and the practical engagement of the new IT initiative are necessary for employees to gain the required proficiency and credence. To ensure sustainability and competence empowerment in staff, continuous practical engagement with prompt constructive feedback is highly valuable. Inadequate training and lack of basic IT proficiency have been identified in various research studies as prominent hindrances to the implementation and sustainability of EHRs (Khan *et al.*, 2019, Greysen *et al.*, 2020). Medical practitioners have also identified knowledge gaps in the functionalities and use of EHRs as

one of the problems impeding EHR success (Chao *et al.*, 2013). Respondent 5 states the following:

We need to establish the fact that one of the things that hinders end-user participation is inadequate training and support provided during the implementation phase. Proper training and ongoing support are essential to help end-users feel confident and competent in using the EHR. Unfortunately, due to time constraints and limited resources, some staff members received insufficient training, leaving them unprepared to leverage the system to its full potential. As a consequence, they might only use a fraction of the available features, leading to suboptimal outcomes and a failure to fully integrate the EHR into their workflow.

5.4.4 Theme IV - End-user Participation

End-user inclusion and engagement have been pointed out as significant elements in every phase of EHR change management and adoption (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015). It aids in securing the interests of end-users by ensuring the EHR incorporates an uncomplicated operational procedure and caters to the needs of the clinicians who will be engaging it. End-user inclusion further motivates and encourages clinicians to own the system (Sligo *et al.*, 2017) and feel responsible for ensuring its success. It also promotes employee acceptance of use, thereby inhibiting resistance to EHR change management among end-users (Nguyen *et al.*, 2014). It is important for end-users to be represented by all categories of stakeholders in the implementation and change management of an EHR (Boonstra *et al.*, 2021). The representatives of each stakeholder category must be efficient leaders with the required power of influence, experience, expertise and negotiating skills to adequately represent the interests of end-users without undue hesitation and unreasonable compromise (Ross *et al.*,

2016). Clinician participation refers to functional engagement and inclusion of healthcare professionals in the identification of challenges and formulation, organisation, acquisition, development and application of HIT through the clinicians' expertise, proficiency and experience for the establishment of systems that are suitable and befitting (Pannick *et al.*, 2016).

As discussed earlier in Chapter 3.5.1, end-users should be involved in every facet of the EHRS project, including the selection of the system, the design and development of the interface and EHRS software and hardware development to guarantee the system is user-friendly and meets the requirements for daily operations (Hyppönen *et al.*, 2019). Strategies for end-user inclusion should be locally modified and customised, reflecting an equilibrium stance that accommodates end-user interests and needs, EHRS visions and organisational goals. For instance, a situation in which there are contrasting interests between end-users and the organisation may arise. The leadership must, therefore, reach a balance of interests and provide the needed alignment (Martikainen *et al.*, 2020). The implementation and change management of EHRs is not solely technologically dependent; it is also people- and process-oriented. Often, in situations in which the system has failed, the top management approached it as a mainly technical project that only requires an information technology intervention, thereby side-lining end-user involvement (Tariq *et al.*, 2018). Respondent 3 states the following:

In my experience, inadequate end-user participation has indeed proven to be a significant challenge in EHRS implementation. The success of any EHRS project heavily relies on the active involvement and engagement of the end-users, such as healthcare professionals, administrators, and support staff, who directly interact with the system on a daily basis. One of the primary issues we faced was the resistance to change among certain end-users. The

transition from traditional paper-based systems to an electronic platform can be daunting for some individuals, leading to scepticism and reluctance to embrace the new technology. This hesitancy often results in a lack of enthusiasm for learning and adapting to the EHRs, which inevitably impacts the overall adoption and utilization of the system.

In Martikainen *et al.*'s (2020) research study, the prompt and effective communication of the current and perceived challenges to implementers was found to positively impact the participation of end-users in the development of EHRs. The clinician's involvement in the development should involve intimating the experts who will be developing the application with their workflow and operational procedures (Sieja *et al.*, 2019). This will enable the software engineers to design and develop a usable system for the clinicians, which will result in the sustainability of the system after its implementation. According to Tajirian *et al.* (2020), promoting end-user participation is important but still in its infancy in HIT adoption, and promoting and ensuring that it is engaged as it should be remains difficult. The lack or insufficient participation of clinicians is presenting challenges in EHRs implementation. Respondent 16 also mentioned that:

lack of clear communication and collaboration channels between the EHRs implementation team and the end-users exacerbates the problem. End-users might feel left out of the decision-making process, leading to feelings of alienation and a lack of ownership over the new system. Consequently, they may not be adequately motivated to actively participate in the EHRs implementation process. Inadequate end-user participation also has significant implications for data accuracy and integrity. When end-users do not fully engage with the EHRs, there is a higher likelihood of errors, incomplete data entry, and outdated information, compromising the quality of patient care and decision-making.

Figure 5.2: Levels of Clinicians Participation

Source: Maloney (2019) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

5.4.5 Theme V: System Integration

As discussed earlier in Chapter 3 (Subsection 3.5.2), system integration, which is referred to simply as *interoperability*, enables various IT systems to smoothly interact and exchange information explicitly, tacitly and frequently for the purpose of improving healthcare delivery. It provides clinicians with the opportunity to access patient data, regardless of the location of data storage or format of data. System integration affords healthcare practitioners a comprehensive overview of patient medical history and current medical status, hence providing clear insight into a patient's present health condition to aid in accurate diagnosis, informed decision-making and safe outcomes (PAHO 2020).

The primary factor that drives ease of communication and information transfer within an organisation and from one healthcare organisation to another for improved patient-centred service delivery is interoperability (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2018). Various peculiar challenges in each healthcare organisation and across the healthcare sector, unstructured regulatory standards and compliance and discrepancies and irregularities in the format of stored data have made an EHR interoperability development ineffective and non-functional (Ross *et al.*, 2016). It is, therefore, important that a structured regulatory system be formulated and effective

communication across the board of the healthcare organisations be ensured to guarantee the sustainability of EHR interoperability from the initiation of the integrated EHRS project through post-implementation (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). Deficiencies in holistic interoperability have been identified as one of the several major problems encountered in the application of an integrated EHRS. It often leads to the incessant replication of undue healthcare expenses and overwhelming workload stress for healthcare personnel, which is capable of jeopardising safe and quality healthcare for patients (Roman *et al.*, 2017). This is in accordance with Respondent 18 who states that:

inadequate system integration or interoperability is a major challenge that significantly impacts EHRS implementation. Interoperability as we know deals with seamless exchange and sharing of data between different healthcare systems, enabling them to work together cohesively. Unfortunately, in many instances, EHRS systems face difficulties in achieving this level of seamless integration, which can lead to several avoidable issues. The thing is when EHRS systems lack interoperability, it becomes challenging to access comprehensive patient information from multiple sources. Health records, test results, and other critical data may be dispersed across various systems that cannot effectively communicate with each other. This fragmentation hinders healthcare professionals' ability to access a holistic view of a patient's medical history, potentially leading to fragmented care and compromised patient safety.

Furthermore, this presents a persistent challenge for the group of patients suffering from long-standing critical health problems who are dependent on the adequate sharing and communication of patient data through EHRS infrastructures for the enhancement of their healthcare (WHO, 2016). Inadequate and inefficient interoperability is largely inimical to patient healthcare and financially wasteful for healthcare organisations such as the NHS. It

can result in escalated errors in medication prescriptions, increased discrepancies in patient medical records and excessive and needless medical treatment or examination, which can lead to other health complications and problems (Thompson and Graetz, 2019). Respondent 16 mentioned that:

When EHRS cannot effectively communicate with other essential healthcare applications, such as laboratory information systems or radiology systems, it restricts the capabilities and benefits of the EHRS. As a result, healthcare professionals may not be able to access critical data or use advanced features that could enhance patient care and decision-making.

According to Daniel *et al.* (2019), certain key elements are significant to the achievement of effective interoperability. These include the development of a framework for interoperability that includes regulations, standards, policies and implementation guidelines formulated by all major stakeholders involved in the EHRS development. To achieve functional interoperability for a sustainable EHRS, healthcare organisations formulated regulatory standards for interoperability compliance (Adel *et al.*, 2018). Some of these standards include EuroRec, epSOS, GEHR (Begoyan, 2007), CEN/ISO EN13606, openEHR and DICOM (Adel *et al.*, 2021). However, these all have incessant problems, and an overwhelming number of standards has been identified as one of these challenges. Their implementation can be encumbering and arduous (Martínez-Villaseñor *et al.*, 2016). The enhancement of integrated information systems with adequate infrastructures and approach flexibility is one of the key elements that drive interoperability. Patient participation is also a key element of interoperability and involves engaging patients to have access and viable input in their healthcare by making available for them the privilege to determine and consent to the use of the data. The security and confidentiality of patient data must also be ensured (Daniel *et al.*, 2019).

5.5 Conclusion

A majority of the respondents reported the need for sustainable EHRS change management and the growing need for an integrated system for the effective delivery of patient care through HIT optimisation. Respondents found regularly used EHR services valuable for boosting job efficiency after EHR deployment. These time-consuming tasks related to paper-based records were no longer required, resulting in perceived general efficiency gains in workflow and laboratory turnaround time. Interviewees also mentioned increased efficiency as a result of the relatively fast information retrieval in EHRs and reduced documentation time as a result of using EHR templates, for example. The use of templates for EHRs was beneficial and saved time on documentation. The data analysis findings resonate and agree with the theoretical discussions and deliberations of the academic and industry researchers discussed in Chapter 3. The analysis of qualitative data in this chapter demonstrates that aligning EHRS implementation with key factors is paramount to its sustainability through its lifecycle. Each factor is interconnected with the others. For example, the quality of training, as well as the usability of the EHR, will influence end-user abilities and competencies. Therefore, each aspect must be considered in a successful deployment. Future EHR implementations must learn from the achievements and, more significantly, the mistakes that have occurred in the past concerning those aspects. Otherwise, previous mistakes may be replicated and new issues that could have been avoided may arise. Each of the main success criteria is interconnected with the others. The results of the interview data analysis support some of the EHRS challenges outlined in the literature review: interoperability issues, ineffective change management and acceptance of use. Finally, interviewees established increases in the adoption of HIT but highlighted significant room for the improvement and development of integrated systems in the healthcare sector.

CHAPTER SIX: DISCUSSION

6.1 Introduction

This chapter establishes a relationship between this study, academic research and EHRS in the healthcare sector. The goal of the study is to investigate the sustainability of EHRS change management in NHS England and develop an effective framework for a sustainable EHRS to solve the literature gap indicated in Chapter 3, thereby providing industry and academia with realistic implementation guidance. Through the evaluation of the research and its findings, this study connects the strands of academic and business literature offered in Chapter 2. Regarding the research findings and the current body of literature, the researcher discusses major themes in the ERM field.

The remaining sections make up the rest of the chapter. Section 6.2 summarises the discussion as it relates to the literature review, interview analysis and healthcare industry in general. Section 6.3 elucidated the significance of sustainable change management in HIT. Considering the research investigation, Section 6.4 presents the revised framework and explains its validation as the researcher examines the impact of the various organisational aspects on it. Section 6.5 contains practical suggestions for putting the framework into action and Section 6.6 draws conclusions.

6.2 The Change Management of EHRS

As discussed earlier in Chapter 2, health information and data, result management, order input and support and decision support are all clinical services provided by EHRS. Clinical narratives, physician and nursing diagnoses, demographics, laboratory test results, prescription lists and allergies are all examples of health information and data that can be extracted from EHRs (Nordo *et al.*, 2019). It also has a results management component that

digitally manages all types of results, such as laboratory, pathology, and radiology procedure results. Furthermore, interviewees stressed that EHRs provide order entry as well as support functions, particularly in the ordering of pharmaceuticals (Hassenfeldt and Martin 2021). Another wonderful feature of EHRs is the clinical decision support role they play because they incorporate decision support features like computer-assisted diagnosing, alerts and reminders. EHRs enable people involved in patient care to properly communicate with one another and the patient (Reza *et al.*, 2020). Administratively, EHRs streamline and improve processes like appointment scheduling and insurance verification. EHRs also use decision support technologies to identify patients who are eligible for chronic illness care and clinical trial research (Rajaram *et al.*, 2020). Concerning reporting, EHRs are critical in developing standardized language and data formats for both private and public sector reporting (Odekunle 2016).

According to the literature review in Chapter 2, the adoption of EHRs in healthcare delivery has been primarily challenged by greater concern for patient data security and confidentiality (Moats and McFall, 2019). Regulatory bodies in charge of governance are also scrutinizing risk management as they begin to emphasise the importance of governance, risk and compliance, the information security of patients for EHRs deployment and the implementation process (Keshta and Odeh, 2021). Due to these external demands, top management has endeavoured to integrate EHRs into current organisational structures with the goal of achieving effective and sustainable implementation (Ganiga *et al.*, 2020).

Furthermore, one of the primary impediments to EHRs change management and sustainability identified by 26.20% of respondents was inadequate change management. Inadequate data security and privacy are challenges in the implementation of EHRs,

according to 9.8% of the interviewees. Furthermore, 26.20% of the interviewees indicated that ineffective EHR interoperability is a fundamental difficulty that has harmed EHR productivity and performance. EHR use difficulty was recognised as the result of poor system installation by 3.3% of the interviewed population.

The NHS in England is made up of a number of different NHS organisations, some of which have significant autonomy as NHS foundation trusts. Local hospital trusts that provide services to primary care commissioners face some competition as well. Our findings reveal a conflict between government policies that foster decentralization and a policy that provides local NHS settings with centrally acquired, uniform IT systems (Margheri *et al.*, 2020). The formulation of systems obligations into long-term contracts for NHS IT applications revealed an additional policy issue because national instructions for service delivery and reporting by NHS trusts are always changing. Technology also evolves, and long-term contracts might suddenly become obsolete concerning technology (Sittig and Singh, 2021).

Based on the literature review in Chapter 2 and interview analysis in Chapter 5, it is important for the Department of Health to identify discrepancies between supporting NHS internal markets and foundation trusts and the inflexibility of long-term, centrally negotiated contracts that exclude NHS trust end-users (i.e., patients) (Moll and Rexhepi, 2020). For a variety of reasons, secondary care trusts may find it difficult to implement EHRs. However, consistency in leadership from the Department of Health, as well as clarity in communication and vision, may help alleviate some of the current challenges (Boulus-Rødje, 2019). It is also evident that NHS trusts must be able to communicate changing local and national NHS priorities to those working with them to implement EHRs, whether through open lines of communication between the trust and its local service provider or between the trust and the

application supplier (Duan, *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, tying local service provider compensation to the number of sites deploying according to a specified schedule was a tactic for lowering central contract costs that backfired (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). Contract payments linked to more thoughtfully agreed-upon results might limit costs and benefit both NHS trusts and local service providers seeking to deploy.

NHS trusts may be actively urged to use local service provider solutions, but they cannot be forced to do so. Some have negotiated for power over system selection, design, delivery and local configuration (Soman *et al.*, 2020). Local service providers have been negotiating with trusts, suppliers and NHS Connecting for Health to reset contracts on a regular basis. The public debate tends to focus on the IT program's difficult history rather than the desired outcome of EHR use in light of acknowledged policy tensions and program modifications (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). It is beneficial but limiting to consider nationwide implementations of EHRs using broad categorisations, such as middle as compared to top-down approaches (Gorinski, *et al.*, 2019). Other crucial factors, such as what kind of precise EHR is desired, its scale and how much the country is willing to spend for it, remain unresolved in England (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). As a result, it is proposed that policymakers' initial focus should be on how to provide clear and concise solutions and responses to these essential queries.

EHRs are a component of today's healthcare scene and provide numerous benefits. Nonetheless, there is still much resistance to them. The causes for resistance vary, but installation concerns, perceived cost, poor project planning, lack of responsibility and lack of training are just a few of the most prominent issues mentioned in the literature (Rathert *et al.*, 2017). All aspects of healthcare have had opposition, but physician resistance to the new technology has been particularly concerning (Heath and Porter, 2018). As a result, it is critical

to anticipate and handle user resistance to get functional, rather than dysfunctional, results (Heath and Porter, 2018). Although computers may not be a hindrance in and of themselves, some reluctance may stem from the fundamental difference between writing information on a piece of paper and typing it into a computer. Physicians are accustomed to flipping through charts, so doing it online is not as natural (Haluza and Hofer, 2020). According to research, physicians prioritise interpersonal ties in which they speak directly with patients, and technology may conflict with such ties (Gomez *et al.*, 2021). As a result, physicians will act on what is most important to them, which may lead to opposition to new technologies.

EHRs also promote and assist in the management of patient data throughout the healthcare continuum. The nature of the healthcare continuum, on the contrary, has changed. A complex many-to-many information exchange regime is unavoidable when leveraging tools like machine learning and other technology to improve treatment. Traditional trust agreements are used by health organisations to satisfy this sharing need on a case-by-case basis. A trusted third party is essential to communicating information like patient data in today's digital age. As a result, HIT organisations have risen to the fore and are now being utilised to broker exchange agreements between hospitals, clinical domains, regulators, insurers and even patients (Chukwu and Garg, 2020). They claim to be able to deliver fully integrated health systems with real EHRs. Available research continues to point to these systems' incapacity to appropriately address stakeholder needs (De la Vega *et al.*, 2019). The lack of trust in the security and privacy of entrusted patient information is increasing due to unsustainable EHR change management (Chukwu and Garg, 2020).

6.3 Significance of Sustainable (Continuously Maintained) Change Management in HIT

The significance of sustainable change management in health information technology (HIT) cannot be overstated, as it plays a pivotal role in ensuring the ongoing success and effectiveness of healthcare IT systems. The continuous maintenance of change management in HIT offers several crucial benefits:

Optimal System Performance: Healthcare IT systems, including Electronic Health Record Systems (EHRs), are complex and constantly evolving. Sustainable change management ensures that these systems are regularly updated, maintained, and optimized for peak performance. This results in reliable and efficient healthcare operations, leading to improved patient care and safety.

Adaptability to Technological Advancements: Technology in the healthcare industry is rapidly evolving. Sustainable change management allows healthcare organizations to stay up-to-date with the latest advancements and innovations in HIT. By embracing new technologies, healthcare providers can enhance their services, streamline processes, and remain competitive in a dynamic healthcare landscape.

Addressing Emerging Challenges: The healthcare industry is prone to various challenges, including regulatory changes, security threats, and user requirements. Sustainable change management enables organizations to proactively address these challenges by implementing necessary updates, security patches, and user training. This proactive approach helps prevent potential disruptions and ensures continuous system improvement.

Enhanced Data Security and Privacy: Healthcare data is highly sensitive and subject to strict privacy regulations. Sustainable change management incorporates security best practices,

such as regular risk assessments, encryption, and access controls, to protect patient information from unauthorized access and breaches.

User Adoption and Engagement: Ongoing change management fosters a culture of adaptability and user engagement among healthcare staff. Regular training and support during system updates help users become more proficient in utilizing the technology effectively, reducing resistance to change and maximizing the benefits of the HIT system.

Cost-Effectiveness: Regular maintenance and updates, when part of sustainable change management, can prevent major system failures or breakdowns that may result in costly emergency repairs. By investing in continuous maintenance, healthcare organizations can minimize downtime and unexpected expenses, leading to better financial management.

Quality Improvement and Evidence-Based Care: Sustainable change management enables the collection of meaningful data over time, facilitating quality improvement initiatives and evidence-based care. Analysing system data and user feedback helps identify trends and areas for improvement, leading to better clinical outcomes and patient experiences.

Regulatory Compliance: Healthcare IT systems must adhere to a multitude of regulatory requirements, such as HIPAA in the United States, GDPR in the European Union or UK GDPR in United Kingdom. Sustainable change management ensures that the system remains compliant with these regulations, reducing the risk of penalties and legal issues.

In conclusion, sustainable change management in health information technology is critical for ensuring the continuous success, adaptability, and reliability of healthcare IT systems. By proactively addressing challenges, staying up-to-date with technology, and engaging users,

healthcare organizations can unlock the full potential of HIT to deliver high-quality patient care while maintaining data security and compliance with regulations.

6.4 Validation of the Developed EHRS Implementation Framework

This section's major goal is to integrate the empirical study's findings into the theoretical ERM Alignment Framework (Figure 3.9) developed in Chapter 3. The researcher conducted an in-depth gap analysis, which resulted in the validation of essential framework parts. As a result, based on the findings of academic and industrial research, as well as the findings of the empirical investigation, this section provides practical assistance for applying the EHRS Implementation Framework (Figure 3.9). Through the empirical analysis and validation of the theoretical EHRS Implementation Framework, the researcher analysed the theoretical assumptions gathered from the literature.

The structure depicted in Chapter 3, Figure 3.9 was developed using the major findings from academic and industry research contributions (both theoretical and empirical). Its primary goal was to fill a gap in the research (see Chapter 3, Subsection 3.4 and Table 3.2) that demonstrated the need for a strategic framework for long-term change management for largescale EHRS implementation. As a result, the researcher first outlined organisational elements critical to EHRS deployment (Chapter 3) and then empirically proved their importance (Chapter 5). The third step was providing healthcare industry experts and scholars with practical information on how to execute the EHRS implementation framework.

The theoretical framework for EHRS implementation outlined in Chapter 3, Subsection 3.5 was built around three phases: initiation, execution and monitoring. Each phase represents a fundamental component of the holistic implementation process of an EHRS in the context of achieving sustainable change and realising the intended benefits. Changes in the elements of

each of these components, whether strategy, interoperability, technology, system improvement, technical support, data privacy and confidentiality or information security are assumed to have an impact on HIT in the healthcare sector. Organisational structure, communication, leadership and organisational culture are the internal factors identified in the literature review. The external factors identified include governance, socioeconomic factors, finances and third parties (i.e., vendors).

The researcher tried to validate the importance of major aspects that affect the EHRS Implementation Framework in the empirical investigation after laying out the fundamental theoretical factors that underpin it. The Strategic EHRS Framework is depicted in Figure 6.1, and it reflects some key empirical results that influenced the evaluation of the theoretical version of the framework given in Chapter 3, Figure 3.9. It also reveals which organisational aspects have shifted as a result of the empirical study. All major alterations to the theoretical framework (Figure 3.9) are underlined in red. The numbers 1 to 5 represent the steps outlined in Section 6.4 of the framework's instructions for implementation.

According to a comparison of figures 3.9 and 6.1, an additional component of risk management was added to the framework as a result of the data analysis discussed in Chapter 5 so that the implementation of ERM is now seen as consisting of the management of risk throughout the project lifecycle. In other words, at each phase of the implementation process, risk management is required, which is further discussed in subsequent sections. The joint efforts of the chief risk officer, an independent risk management department, risk committees, and EHRS champions are crucial in the sustainable implementation of EHRs, as this new component demonstrates. Building internal support for EHRS and integrating the appropriate personnel in the implementation of the EHRS framework are two of the first steps

in developing an effective risk culture. This component's presence emphasises the significance of robust risk governance in EHRS programs.

Figure 6.1: Strategic EHRS Implementation Sustainability Framework

Source: Researcher

Organisations tended to see health IT as a solution to patient safety issues, ignoring the possibility that it could contribute to safety issues or introduce new sorts of safety risks. When a company installs, expands or upgrades an EHRS, it must ensure the system is functional and that employees are properly trained to utilise it effectively (Salih *et al.*, 2019). Although these concerns have apparent consequences for patient safety, the increased safety risks connected to the adoption and use of health IT, particularly EHRs, were not viewed as requiring concentrated attention in general. As a result, risk management must be ongoing (Alageel and Gulliford, 2019).

The act or practice of dealing with risk, which involves planning for risk, assessing, identifying and analysing risk areas, establishing risk-handling choices, monitoring risks to evaluate how they have changed and documenting the whole risk management program can be referred to as risk management (Fraser *et al.*, 2021). The purpose of risk management is to reduce the likelihood of risk and its consequences. Risk management situations in diverse HIT procedures must be analysed by EHRs implementers to control or prevent risk where and when possible (Pescaroli and Needham-Bennett, 2021).

Root cause analysis, failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA), and the use of risk registries are just a few of the available risk management methods. FMEA is a technique for identifying the location, cause and effects of a probable failure to reduce the risk of failure (Qin *et al.*, 2020). Risk management is required For EHRs so that unwanted events may be ruled out and avoided whenever possible. The goal of risk management is to lower the likelihood of failure (Sredzinski, 2022). A risk management team might employ a variety of techniques to detect hazards. Brainstorming, the Delphi methodology, interviews, root cause analysis, SWOT analysis and experience are all methods for identifying risks. To mitigate the effects of risk variables rated as high to medium, risk management team should pay additional attention to them (Filippetto *et al.*, 2021). Avoiding, transferring, mitigating and accepting a risk are examples of actions. Avoiding risk entails altering one's strategy or process to ensure the risk does not occur. To remedy insufficient training, managers might plan ahead by requesting additional training from vendors and offering additional on-site or online support (Smith and Merritt, 2020).

Purchasing insurance is the most prevalent method of transferring risk. Purchasing supplementary billing insurance, for example, during an EHR implementation project might

mitigate the potential negative effects of billing errors while using the new EHRS (Altuntas, *et al.*, 2021). Another prominent risk-transfer strategy is outsourcing. If the hospital does not have much experience with data conversion during EHR deployment, then it can hire a data conversion specialist to help. If there is not a means of preventing or transferring risk, then risk mitigation is necessary (DuHadway *et al.*, 2019). In the case of system incompatibility, for example, the business can devote greater capital resources to the replacement of outmoded systems. This will necessitate activating the contingency plan for additional resources like labour and cost. Finally, if nothing more can be done, then the company will have no choice but to take the risk (Meechang, *et al.*, 2020).

Organisations' capacity to anticipate and respond to health IT safety concerns may be hampered by traditional departmental silos between risk management, IT and quality and safety management (Hooker *et al.*, 2019). Tools and metrics are urgently needed to enable project teams in hospitals and ambulatory offices to detect, manage and monitor health IT safety concerns (Akbar *et al.*, 2020). The existing structure of the EHR market, combined with a lack of knowledge of the dangers posed by health IT systems, leaves EHR developers and providers with few incentives to participate in the type of collaborative effort required to mitigate health IT security threats (Sujan, 2018).

6.5 Practical Implementation Guidance for the EHRS Sustainability Framework

Based on the examination and analysis of the primary data, this part contains a description of the researcher's proposed practical guidelines for adopting the EHRS Framework (Figure 6-1). According to the results of prior studies, organisations should first assess their current risk management situations, needs and usability before implementing a strategy that will enable them to initiate EHRS change management (Fenelly *et al.*, 2020; Bloom *et al.*, 2021; Walker *et*

al., 2021). As a result, the researcher suggests that managers evaluate certain crucial considerations in the context of their organisations before choosing an implementation strategy:

- What is the current structure of the organisation, and how might an EHRS be incorporated into it?
- What are the advantages and value of implementing EHRS?
- How can senior executives be persuaded to endorse and sponsor EHRS?
- How can the ERM framework be aligned with the organisation's plans, objectives, and goals?
- How can the EHR framework be used to help achieve a sustainable EHRS change management implementation?

The researcher considered the preceding topics to be an important part of EHRSS and, thus, necessary for validating the EHRS Implementation Framework and providing practical implementation guidance. Defining a unique organisational structure is a crucial stage in any EHRS initiative because it enables management to assess the current structure and determine how EHRS can be integrated. Management must comprehend and define the EHRS program's goals and clearly convey them across the organisation, regardless of the organisation's strategic direction. All employees should be aware of the organisation's strategic orientation and comprehend the vision, mission statement and major organisational objectives in connection to their performance objectives. In light of the five actions listed above, the researcher suggests that each of the following implementation processes be considered:

Step 1: Establish the factors critical for sustainable implementation

- a. Internal Factors: Organisational structure, culture, leadership, and communication

- b. External Factors: Governance, socioeconomic factor, finance, and vendors

Step 2: Define the Readiness phase (i.e., the initiation phase)

- c. Change Vision
- d. Strategy
- e. Software design
- f. Stakeholders Involvement

Step 3: Define the configuration stage (i.e., the execution phase)

- g. Data privacy and confidentiality
- h. Interoperability
- i. Technology
- j. Training

Step 3: Define the optimisation of the EHR (i.e., the monitoring process)

- k. System Improvement
- l. Feedback
- m. Technical Support
- n. Motivation and recognition

The following subsections contain guidance on each of the essential implementation steps shown in Figure 6-1.

6.5.1 Step 1: Identify Factors Critical to Sustainable Implementation

It is important for the management to do their due diligence in establishing factors that are critical to a successful and sustainable EHR implementation before launching further into the

commencement of an integrated EHRS. The identification of these critical factors (Janssen *et al.*, 2019) will provide the bedrock upon which the whole project initiative will be built. This serves as a major means of risk management because it will result in a list of the risks that can lead to the fatal failure of the project and help professionals quickly mitigate against such risks (Bajwa *et al.*, 2020). As shown in Figure 6.1, these factors are both internal and external and must be appropriately managed using appropriate measures to ensure an adequate balance is reached to support sustainable development (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). The identification of these factors will grant the management and policymakers the wherewithal to execute evidence-informed resolutions while implementing sustainable EHRSs across the board within the healthcare setting (Barclay *et al.*, 2019). The management must strategically appropriate how these factors would dynamically interact throughout the implementation of an EHRS and influence its success (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020).

When considering the internal factors (i.e., organisational culture, structure, leadership and communication), the senior management overseeing EHR implementation should understand their implications and criticality (Sligo *et al.*, 2017). Although bottom-up, middle-out and top-down organisational structures might have subsisted and been engaged when previous projects were approached, the management should ensure that at the individual organisation level, open-door policies, autonomy, idea generation and buy-ins are encouraged to enhance the acceptance of use, which will lead to sustainability after implementation (Georgiou and Prgomet, 2019). It is also important for the leadership to foster positive and credible relationships with contractors, suppliers and other third parties while designing sustainability plans with measurable outcomes (Moy *et al.*, 2021), suitable implementation steps see the phased model in Figure 6.1) and defining duties for each role involved (Tsegaye and Flowerday, 2020). A deviation from top-down organisational structure, with a designation of

resident leads or exponents and support for effective communication among all involved stakeholders, creating opportunities for continuous improvement and innovation, will aid in the development of a suitable and adaptable culture (Heinze and Heinze, 2020).

Careful consideration must also be given to external factors (i.e., governance, socioeconomic forces, finance and vendors). In preparing to undertake a significant project, such as the implementation of a largescale EHRS that is sustainable, the management must be keen on financial implications concerning budgeting and resourcing (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). Financial constraints are frequently identified as a roadblock, particularly by primary care physicians and people in developing climates (Wang and Gibbs, 2019). A detailed and realistic cost analysis method that involves the consideration of infrastructure, staff, maintenance and continual optimisation should be developed (Biancone *et al.*, 2019). The management can also make provisions for a professional workforce within the organisation with expert knowledge of clinical workflows to reduce vendor reliance and costs (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). Also, compliance with governance measures (i.e., policies, regulations and national standards) must be ensured. A team should be set up to carry out internal audits at each phase of the implementation to ensure strict compliance. A deep understanding of these regulations must be established before the commencement of the project because this will help prevent interoperability issues and bolster patient safety, data privacy and confidentiality (Kanwal *et al.*, 2021).

6.5.2 Step 2: Define the Readiness phase of the EHRS (i.e., Initiation Phase)

Organisational readiness for change is a renowned element that determines the success of organisational changes in general and EHRS implementation in particular (Sligo *et al.*, 2017). It is multidimensional and multi-layered in design, measuring it can also be difficult. According

to Kabukye *et al.* (2020), certain phenomena must be considered for readiness: the change process (i.e., the steps and strategies followed during implementation of the change, e.g., stakeholder involvement), the content of the change (i.e., the specific initiative being implemented), such as the EHRS and its characteristics, is one of the major phenomena and the context of the organisation, which includes the conditions and environment in which employees work (e.g., dynamic). Examples of implementation readiness are core (need/motivational) readiness, technological (infrastructural) readiness, social readiness, engagement readiness and IT learning readiness, among other forms of readiness (Afrizal *et al.*, 2020). The relevance of each of these types of readiness differs depending on the organisation. Poor IT infrastructure and a lack of IT skills, for example, are frequently barriers to EHRS deployment, making technological readiness more pertinent (Afrizal *et al.*, 2020).

According to Weiner *et al.* (2020), organisational readiness can be defined as the psychological and behavioural preparedness of an organisation's personnel. That is, how willing (change commitment) and capable (change efficacy) people are to make and keep a change. Weiner *et al.*'s (2020) holistic view of organisational readiness is based on the idea that EHR deployment entails collective behaviour change in the form of systems redesign, that is, multiple, simultaneous changes in staffing, task flow, decision-making, communication, and reward systems. The aforementioned categories of readiness are antecedents to organisational readiness. Change commitment, and hence the motivation to implement the change, occurs when employees believe they want to implement the change (i.e., they value the change), as opposed to feeling compelled to implement it (i.e., they have no choice and are forced to take the action) (Cho *et al.*, 2021). Staff must be dissatisfied with the existing conditions and appreciate or be convinced of the benefits of the future state to want to make the change. Change efficacy (i.e., when organisation staff members believe in

their abilities to carry out the change action or belief that successful change is possible, e.g., based on similar organisations' success stories) is dependent on the staff's understanding and judgement of the task demands and available resources (McCrorie *et al.*, 2019).

According to Kotter (1996), 50% of significant organisational changes fail due to a lack of preparation. Staff members want to maintain a condition of affairs that gives them a sense of psychological safety, control and identity, and any attempts to alter this status quo are met with resistance (Elharish, 2021). It is necessary to go through an "unfreezing" process in which mindsets are shifted and motivation for change is generated. When organisational preparedness is high, individuals are likely to initiate change, invest great effort, demonstrate high perseverance and display cooperative conduct, resulting in the effective implementation of the proposed change (Kabukye *et al.*, 2020). Early attitudes and behaviours concerning the change, such as negative rumours, participation in the planning and design phases and resistance to change, are all shaped by early perceptions and beliefs about the change (Roos and Nilsson, 2020). To provide a high likelihood of success, it is critical to assess readiness prior to substantial organisational changes, such as EHRS deployment (Gesulga *et al.*, 2017). Conducting a readiness assessment can assist in the identification of action points or concerns that may jeopardise project success, which can be addressed early in the project lifecycle when change management is most effective (Kabukye *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, because it informs the organisation's workers about the impending change and encourages discussion, the readiness assessment process itself can improve readiness.

6.5.3 Step 3: Describe the configuration stage of the EHRS (i.e., execution phase)

After defining the readiness phase dynamics, the researcher suggests that managers endeavour to comprehend and define the configuration of the EHRS by identifying key

elements crucial to system implementation (Step 2). The configuration elements are data privacy and confidentiality, interoperability, technology and training.

The management should first define how they want to ensure patient data privacy and confidentiality are well monitored and managed through adequate information security with appropriate governance and compliance mechanisms in place. As the movement to embrace HIT gains traction, a slew of data security and privacy problems must be addressed. The ability of healthcare organisations to handle cyber-attacks lags substantially behind that of other businesses (Kruse *et al.*, 2017). These businesses may be using old technology and software, and employees are frequently using default passwords (Mansfield-Devine, 2017). A devastating effect of security and privacy vulnerabilities was demonstrated by the WannaCry ransomware event (Martin *et al.*, 2018). Workstations running obsolete Windows software were attacked by Cryptoworms in 2017, limiting access to operating systems that were crucial to daily service delivery within the NHS. In England, 10% of general practitioners' practices and 30% of hospital trusts were significantly affected (UK Department of Health & Social Care, 2018). Aside from surprise assaults, there is also the risk of internal data mismanagement due to human error or a lack of clarity about how the NHS should share data about patients with third parties. This must, therefore, be defined by the senior management during the configuration phase of EHRs implementation. Back in 2018, data about around 150,000 patients was released by NHS Digital for the purpose of research, despite their non-participatory decisions not being honoured due to an error in computer programming code (Sheikh *et al.*, 2021).

The management should ensure that all relevant stakeholders (i.e., patients, policymakers and clinicians) are involved in discussing the management of data privacy and confidentiality.

Patients who want to access their own data should be able to do so through secure systems and policies, which is a legal necessity in and of itself (UK Information Commissioner's Office, 2018). Clear data and cyber security standards, such as frequent software upgrades, data breach handling processes, virtual LAN usage, cloud computing and training staff on recognising and phishing emails, must be strictly adhered to by healthcare organisations to gain and maintain public trust in data privacy and confidentiality management (Kruse *et al.*, 2017). Data protection regulations can be streamlined where possible.

Furthermore, in the configuration phase, the management should integrate interoperability into the EHRS. Interoperability is the ability of two or more systems or units to communicate information and utilise that information. It is a crucial facilitator in increasing the usability of HIT systems (Sheikh *et al.*, 2021). Technical interoperability (i.e., the act of exchanging data between two or more systems) and semantic interoperability (i.e., the measure of establishing that each system can interpret and utilise the information received from the other) are the two issues to consider (Sheikh *et al.*, 2021). It is difficult to achieve interoperability in large healthcare organisations that perform a variety of services at the same time.

Currently, multiple products may be installed within individual hospitals, but a majority of hospitals are missing both technical and semantic interoperability. This has numerous consequences for patient safety and infection control because it creates hurdles to the early detection of nosocomial infections (Benson and Grieve, 2021). For example, during the COVID-19 epidemic, this was a critical issue. Healthcare workers are frequently expected to use a variety of products, which contributes to transcription errors as a result of the increased need to gather and report data (Wachter and Goldsmith, 2018). Contracts frequently fail to

include the necessary standards to permit interoperability across different products, which contributes to this expectation (Sheikh *et al.*, 2021).

Finally, the management should consider strategies for suitable technology and adequate training on the use of such technology in the configuration phase of EHRs implementation.

At this phase, training should also be taking place. Training environments can be established to familiarise users with the new platform as well as some of the upgraded features. This will reduce technophobia. *Technophobia* is defined as an aversion to or fear of HIT for the purposes of this research (Czaja, 2021). Technophobia can also be explained using the TAM, which describes how consumers' attitudes, perceived utility and PEU all influence their willingness to accept a new EHRs (Woody, 2020). These fears may emerge from perceptions that new EHRs or HITs are machine-based systems programmed by IT corporations with no medical knowledge, personal sentiments about their inadequacy in computer skills, perceived expertise, or concerns about negative effects on work procedures and quality (Sidek and Martins, 2017). To combat technophobia, the management must strategize on the provision of adequate training for staff members (Spatara *et al.*, 2019). This stage is critical for maximising communication among all stakeholders so that the next phase can run smoothly. As a result, training is critical to health IT deployment because how people interact with new technology and learn to use it to affect their engagement, motivation and desire to change (Sidek and Martins, 2017). End-users are most likely to regard a new EHRs as unintuitive and unusable when they are not properly trained or have poor training experience, aggravating technophobia early in the configuration phase. Training enables IT developers to get feedback to make patches and updates. Change can cause resistance, which can stifle productivity. This feedback fosters buy-in and minimises resistance (Cho *et al.*, 2021). On the contrary, if end-

user training is positive, timely and successful, then the overall impact of technophobia can be reduced. Leadership must be highly aware of the anxiety that surrounds new HIT. Otherwise, acceptance will be delayed, and productivity will suffer (Woody, 2020).

6.5.4 Step 4: Define the optimisation of the EHRs (i.e., monitoring process)

This section contains a description of the significance of EHRs optimisation through monitoring and enhancement after implementation. According to Jamoom *et al.* (2016), EHRs optimisation is critical in detecting EHR-related advantages among physicians. Optimisation is defined as the process of analysing and improving a system in response to user feedback (Heeney *et al.*, 2021) and is critical to the customisation of a system for continual engagement. The management should quickly respond to the concerns and feedback of end-users (Sequeria *et al.*, 2021). This should be designed as in-depth team-based interventions carried out at particular intervals directed towards training healthcare professionals in the effective engagement of existing EHRs, the remodelling of workflows and the development of new EHR tools, all towards the optimisation of EHRs (Sieja *et al.*, 2019). Physicians' interactions with EHRs can be improved by utilising end-user feedback, motivation from leadership and continuous technical support from the intervention team. The senior management should use the data and analytics accrued from the use of EHRs to monitor EHRs for the purpose of optimising the system on an ongoing basis to achieve sustainability (Taxter *et al.*, 2022). This can be designed in the form of dashboards or indicators that enable the management to spot problems and help healthcare professionals assess their EHRs use performance (Melnick *et al.*, 2021). In a technological era in which the open publication of performance reports is going to be critical, no organisation wants to be left out in the optimisation process and turn out inferior metrics (Rudin *et al.*, 2020). Dashboards should be manually created in health systems with more rudimentary data and analytics features, and

clinicians or members of management should use them (Rostamzadeh *et al.*, 2021). Designing a real-time workflow reporting system for each clinician, with peer review and new routinely generated dashboards in response to clinician requests will help produce sophisticated data and analytics (Dagliati *et al.*, 2021) operations for the monitoring and optimisation of the EHRS and to attain sustainability.

The optimisation of EHRS implementation requires expert, technical, executive and external assistance (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2018). End-users can be assisted with the optimisation of their usage of the EHRS by experts or through peer support (Sequeria *et al.*, 2021) while technical support staff can assist in resolving IT issues (Ross *et al.*, 2016). In hospitals, technical and peer support should be accessible around the clock (Ratwani *et al.*, 2016). Pathways for obtaining assistance during working hours should remain open. Other important sources of assistance should include executive or policy-level officials and professional networks or outside parties (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). It is also important for maintenance assistance for servers and networks to be carried out to mitigate against undue downtime.

6.6 Conclusion

The findings of theoretical (chapters 2 and 3) and empirical studies (Chapter 5) have been brought together in this chapter. Major themes from existing knowledge and research, as well as the many EHR phenomenon in the healthcare sector, were discussed. With effective top management support, EHR can trigger a critical transformation in how healthcare organisations handle important sustainable changes according to this discussion.

The data analysis reported in Chapter 5 backs up the idea that it is important to link EHRS implementation to crucial elements to ensure its long-term viability. Each factor influences specific end-user abilities and competencies. For example, the quality of training, as well as

the usability of the EHR, will influence particular end-user abilities and competencies. Therefore, each aspect must be considered in a successful deployment. This chapter has explored the internal and external factors that affect healthcare organisations in the context of EHRs acquisition and implementation based on the theoretical framework provided in Chapter 3 (Figure 3.9).

The major factors that influence the sustainability of EHRs change management, as covered in Chapter 2, Figure 2.1, are provider engagement, administrative and policy support, lack of infrastructure, legal and digital divides, organisational structure, culture, leadership and communication. Others include governance, finance, vendors and socioeconomic factors. Considering the contributions of the literature covered in Chapter 2 and the findings of the data analysis in Chapter 6, the researcher identified a number of barriers to the sustainable implementation of EHRs. The researcher found that major internal and external organisational elements interact and influence how EHRs are implemented in different healthcare organisations.

The following are some of the most significant obstacles to long-term EHR implementation: poor system compatibility and integration, which hampers both the deployment and usage of EHRs. Physician resistance, lack of trust in EHRs and data privacy and the danger of data vulnerability were identified as important hurdles to the full utilization of EHRs. Lack of faith in the dependability of EHRs and not being convinced about the benefits for patient care were viewed as impediments to EHR implementation by interviewees. Other identified problems included the poor quality of systems, the incompatibility of the system, system and database breakdowns and system inefficiency. Functionality difficulties were cited as impediments to EHR utilisation. Usability elements, such as user-friendly design and interface ease of use

were all acknowledged to be important. The research conclusions and recommendations are discussed in additional depth in the following chapter.

CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Introduction

In this concluding chapter, the researcher points out the contribution of the research and shows how the aims and objectives of the research have been achieved. The researcher also captures the practical guidelines for the implementation of the framework in this chapter. The researcher also demonstrates how the research question has been answered with a detailed response and arrives at a comprehensive conclusion based on the research findings.

Section 7.2 contains the conclusion of this study. Section 7.3 contains a review of the research findings, aims and objectives of the research and research question. Section 7.4 contains a discussion of this study's knowledge contribution to the field and the literature on change management and EHRs. Section 7.5 highlights the research limitations. Future research recommendations are then captured in Section 7.6. In this chapter, the researcher presents the findings, conclusions and practicable recommendations on sustainable EHR change management.

7.2 Conclusions

There is no evidence in the existing literature that there is a comprehensive approach to sustainable change management for EHR implementation in healthcare settings that incorporates key features into an EHR transition approach. The previous discussion of the various findings contains a summary of existing information and knowledge gaps related to EHR deployment. The number of hospitals EHR implementations is increasing, as is the volume of literature on the subject. This systematic analysis of the literature yielded EHR implementation findings. A number of these findings are general conclusions consistent with

the wider literature on change management while others are unique to EHR implementation in the healthcare sector.

The data offered in this research can be seen as a high-level summary of key issues to consider while developing an EHR. EHRs are clearly complicated, and they should be implemented with great care, with special emphasis paid to context, quality and process difficulties, as well as the interconnections between them. As a result, by conducting a comprehensive evaluation of the literature on EHR installation, we achieved our research purpose. The academic contribution of this work is that it provides an overview of the existing literature on EHR implementation in the healthcare sector through the EHR framework developed by the researcher. Scholars interested in this topic can now easily obtain information about sustainable EHR implementation in the healthcare sector, and they can use this research to build on what they already know. The general findings presented as implementation guidance for adopting EHRs in hospitals are contributions for managers.

Furthermore, the national push for EHR adoption is picking up speed, but the focus should now be on its sustainable implementation. It is impossible to overestimate the complexity of EHRs and the healthcare environment. The findings of this study emphasise the importance of strong physician leadership and management assistance during the development and deployment of an EHR. Healthcare professionals should assist in the development of criteria for evaluating and selecting EHRs that are specific to the needs of physicians and other EHR users by examining the information needs of physicians and other EHR users. In general, research on sustainable change management in EHR is still in its infancy.

Based on workflow requirements and user demands, IT practitioners, in collaboration with medical staff leaders, should recommend hardware and software functionalities to

developers. Physicians should be involved in the selection or design of user interfaces to promote ease of use. To enhance initial and long-term EHRS adoption, senior management and IT professionals must continually collaborate with doctors and other users.

7.3 Aims, Objectives and Research Questions

In this section, the research aim, objectives and questions are reviewed to show how they have been realised and answered. The aim of this research is hereby presented:

- To investigate the sustainability of EHRS change management in NHS England and to develop an effective framework for a sustainable EHRS supported by implementation guidance for managers and practitioners.

This aim has been fulfilled. The literature review in this study revealed a variety of corporate and academic contributions that addressed various important aspects of her use in the healthcare sector. This offered a sound theoretical and empirical basis for the formulation of the framework presented in Chapter 3 by enabling the consideration of published ERM studies. The formulation of the EHRS implementation guidance framework (Figure 3.9) fills the literature gap by including the consideration of numerous EHR concepts and factors that have immediate impacts on its strategic development, acceptance and implementation. Furthermore, Figure 6.1 shows the empirical findings and contains prescriptive implementation guidance for the healthcare sector and academic professionals.

The research objectives set out by the researcher are highlighted thus:

5. To evaluate current status of healthcare IT systems in general and specifically EHRS in the NHS

6. To analyse factors (challenges and barriers) affecting the implementation of healthcare IT systems in general and particularly EHRs in the NHS
7. To evaluate the necessary conditions critical to the success of change sustainability of EHRs in the NHS
8. To evaluate the effectiveness of existing frameworks in healthcare IT systems

The subject area was covered in full in the second and third chapters, which included evaluations of subsisting knowledge, concepts, applications and major contributions to research. The components of several EHRs influencing factors, implementation elements and theories were reflected in the construction of the theoretical sustainable EHRs Implementation Framework (see Figure 3.9).

The implementation framework was designed during the study's theoretical phase (i.e., chapters 2 and 3). The framework was developed based on the findings from the data analysis described in Chapter 5, with a focus on highlighting and corroborating major external and internal factors that are critical to ensuring that the implementation of an EHR is sustainable, as well as systematically integrating an EHR with the existing organisational structure. Hence, the theoretical EHRs framework evolved into a practical management and implementation tool for use in the healthcare industry (Figure 6.1).

The research aim and objectives were achieved by tackling the four research questions highlighted in Chapter 1: Section 1.6. This is described in-depth below:

The first listed research question focuses on the present condition of EHRs in the healthcare sector, along with their developmental growth over time, as it relates to sustainable change management.

1. Evaluate the current status of healthcare IT systems, specifically EHRs in the NHS

To answer the first question, which covers the evolution of the EHRs in the United Kingdom over time, the researcher first conducted an examination of the current literature, which is detailed in Chapter 2. The researcher reviewed the evolution of the EHRs from the inception of the adoption of computers in the NHS in 1968. This provided a background to the development of this system.

In recent years, there has been a substantial increase in the use of EHRs in medical practice. EHRs offer a valuable opportunity to improve health surveillance and evaluate service delivery, which has led to advances in public health management and promotion in the UK (Dornan *et al.*, 2019). Most healthcare professionals, according to the findings, use the information available to analyse the patient's overall state, inform clinical decision-making and facilitate shared communication within patient care teams (Vinks *et al.*, 2020). The purchase and implementation of EHRs is a considerable financial investment, but the approach's performance is also dependent on physician willingness to incorporate new technology into their daily operations (Sieck *et al.*, 2020).

Currently, EHRs are being used to collect detailed information on heart disease, smoking and the implementation of preventive treatments (Chu *et al.*, 2020). EHRs have improved the design and sustainability of effective immunization policies by allowing for the tracking and consolidation of immunization programs (Nyanchoga *et al.*, 2021). The current state of EHRs gives most healthcare practitioners convenient access to patient information, and although the usefulness of EHRs in clinical settings should not be understated, the technological needs for health information are constantly changing (Dornan *et al.*, 2019). Existing data collection and analysis systems usually lack coordination and effective interconnection across

departmental and hospital systems, making it difficult to analyse and evaluate patient outcomes, especially in specific demographics or communities (Daliya and Ramesh, 2019). To provide effective and preventive care management, more complex and expansive data gathering on specific populations will be required, which currently exceeds the capabilities of most healthcare organisations (Gupta and Gupta, 2019). Data collection on specific populations is now at a scale that exceeds the capacity of most healthcare institutions to handle (Dornan *et al.*, 2019). Understanding the progress made and the procedures by which EHRs are adapted in various settings in the UK lets healthcare practitioners acquire useful lessons and develop successful systems to enhance public health.

The barriers to EHR implementation were addressed through the second research question:

2. To analyse factors (challenges and barriers) affecting the implementation of healthcare IT systems in general and particularly EHRs in the NHS.

The researcher presented some challenges and barriers that affect EHRs implementation and change management in Chapter 2, Section 2.5. Resource constraints, inadequate training, poor technical support for end-users, literacy level, poor use of IT skills, limited acceptance of use and data privacy are some of the challenges (Chen *et al.*, 2020). Many of these challenges appear to persist over time. The effect of EHR usage on physician burnout is one of the factors. In a recent study, researchers found a link between the use of EHRs and psychological tiredness (Adler-Milstein *et al.*, 2020), as well as a link between poor EHRs usability and stress (Vehko *et al.*, 2019). As presented in Chapter 2, provider participation, administrative and policy support with commitment and a lack of infrastructure are the major barriers to successful EHRs deployment (Endalew, 2020). Other problems with EHRs implementation include privacy, security and legal issues, as well as the digital divide. Furthermore,

functionality issues with EHRs, such as too many sophisticated capabilities and too few needed functions, were highlighted as barriers to their use. The importance of usability components, such as user interface design and navigation, was emphasised. As explained in Chapter 2, the cost of system upgrades and maintenance, insufficient funds, time restrictions, limited access to computers, limited networks (internet) and an insufficient number of user licences were all mentioned as impediments to EHRs installation and acceptance (Greysen *et al.*, 2020). Concerns have also been raised about the legal liability of medical records contained in EHRs/PHRs. A lack of administrative and governmental support, as well as a lack of understanding, were mentioned as factors that could hinder the successful implementation and use of PHRs (Khan *et al.*, 2018).

In the third research question, the researcher sought to discover all essential conditions to develop the implementation framework required in the healthcare sector and academia.

3. What are the necessary conditions critical to the success of change sustainability of EHRs in the NHS?

The researcher examined the factors critical to successful EHRs sustainability in Chapter 3, Subsection 3.5.4, as well as in the presentation of the ERM sustainable implementation framework and implementation guidance in Figure 6.1 and Subsection 6.4.1. The researcher explained that the successful implementation of a long-term HIT system is based on several elements that affect the entire process of the three stages, namely the initiation, execution and monitoring phases. Internal and external variables are divided into four categories: communication, leadership, organisational structure and organisational culture. Governance, socioeconomic issues, financing and vendors are examples of external variables. Communication is a significant internal factor in the successful adoption and maintenance of

HIT change management in all businesses (Neill, 2018). Poor leadership and ineffective management have been recognised as barriers to EHR adoption for the NPfIT. Due to the leadership's lack of attentiveness, there was gross unaccountability and negligence in task and project management (Hansen, 2018). Also, the structure of an organisation can be a tremendous accelerator for the effective adoption of a technological innovation, but it can also destroy the long-term viability of an IT innovation in a company or industry (Dekoulou and Trivellas, 2017). The culture of the organisation is crucial for a successful EHR implementation and is a strong driver of the rate and frequency of innovation (Topol, 2019). Furthermore, governance, socioeconomic factors, vendors and finances are the external factors critical to the success of the change sustainability of EHRs.

The final research question focuses on examining the effectiveness of existing implementation frameworks. The researcher reviewed some of the existing frameworks and their service delivery as it relates to EHRs sustainability.

4. What are the existing frameworks for the implementation and sustainability of healthcare IT systems?

The researcher addressed this question in Chapter 3 by presenting the TAM framework and evaluating Gebre-Mariam and Bygstad's (2019) EMR Implementation Framework. The researcher presented two paramount concepts upon which the TAM model was designed. They include PEU and PU. These two crucial concepts are at the heart of the essence and significance of any new technological innovation in any sector. It is critical that any group of people be enticed to embrace and accept a new technology by appealing to their reasoning regarding its importance and how user-friendly it is (Sprenger and Schwaninger, 2021). There is a crucial relationship between PEU and PU. A high degree of PEU corresponds to a high

degree of the PU of a technology (Muhammad *et al.*, 2019). To put it another way, the more user-friendly a new technology is, the more valuable it is thought to be, and hence, perceived utility is largely determined by PEU. The perceived utility of a new technology changes attitudes and behaviour intentions towards it (Sagnier *et al.*, 2020). This has a significant impact on the utilisation of the new technological breakthrough. The extent to which a person believes a new technological innovation will improve their effectiveness and efficiency is referred to as PU. PEU can be defined as the degree to which a person believes a new technological innovation will be devoid of ambiguity (Al-Rahmi *et al.*, 2019). In examining the existing EHRS Implementation Framework, the researcher presented the EMR implementation framework developed by Gebre-Mariam and Bygstad (2019) which comprises important conditions that must be present to facilitate the successful execution of an electronic record system. Casual, contextual, and intervening factors are among them. Haphazard circumstances are those that have a significant impact on EMR deployment. Restricted access to full patient information, confidentiality issues (Keshta and Odeh, 2021), drug interactions and prescription errors, clinician communication issues, a lack of a robust decision support system and an inefficient follow-up process are all examples of such conditions. Infrastructure, economics and organisational considerations all play roles in contextual conditions. Energy, information and telecommunication systems are essential infrastructures for the adoption of EHRS (Afolalu *et al.*, 2021). Human resource strength, operational method, the work at hand and patient capabilities are all organisational elements. The economic prerequisites are mainly the funds and financial requirements for such a project, including the deployment of such a large system. Individual and organisational factors, cost and technological factors are the intervening conditions. Individual and organisational factors are reflected in end-user attitudes towards the system, staff computer

skills and literacy, particularly clinicians who will be using the EHRS, and management's unwavering support in facilitating training and essential support are critical to the successful implementation of an EHRS (Fennelly *et al.*, 2020). The financial implications of training staff, acquiring equipment, recruiting personnel and providing planned maintenance are all covered by the cost component here. The technological aspect encompasses the system and service quality, as well as the software and hardware needed for EHRS implementation.

7.3.1 Relevance of Literature Gap to Research Question

The identified literature gap which is limited framework and practicable implementation guidance for the successful and sustainable implementation of HIT change management, is relevant to all four research questions. How this gap relates to each research question is shown thus:

1. What is the current status of healthcare IT systems in general and the EHRS in the NHS in particular?

The literature gap is relevant to this question because without a comprehensive framework and implementation guidance for HIT change management, it becomes challenging to assess the current status of healthcare IT systems, including Electronic Health Record Systems (EHRS) in the NHS. The lack of a robust framework may lead to inconsistent implementation practices and hinder the collection of relevant data to evaluate the current state of IT systems effectively.

2. What are the factors (challenges and barriers) that affect the implementation of healthcare IT systems in general and the EHRS in the NHS in particular?

The absence of a well-defined framework and practicable implementation guidance makes it difficult to identify and address the factors, challenges, and barriers affecting the successful implementation of healthcare IT systems, especially EHRs in the NHS. A comprehensive framework would help researchers and stakeholders pinpoint specific issues and challenges that hinder successful implementation and provide actionable solutions to overcome them.

3. What are the necessary conditions for the successful change and sustainability of the EHRs in the NHS?

The literature gap becomes highly relevant to this research question because the absence of a clear framework and practicable implementation guidance hinders the identification of necessary conditions for successful change and sustainability of EHRs in the NHS. It's crucial to have a well-established and widely accepted framework that outlines best practices and conditions required for successful and sustainable implementation to guide policy decisions and organizational efforts effectively.

4. What are the existing frameworks for the implementation and sustainability of healthcare IT systems?

The literature gap itself addresses the limited availability of existing frameworks for the implementation and sustainability of healthcare IT systems, including EHRs. Without such frameworks, researchers and practitioners might struggle to find well-established models to reference and adapt for their specific contexts. Addressing this gap would not only help identify existing frameworks but also allow for their evaluation and improvement, leading to better-informed decision-making in HIT change management.

In order to advance research on these four questions, it is imperative to bridge the literature gap by developing a comprehensive framework and providing practicable implementation guidance for the successful and sustainable implementation of HIT change management. This framework would serve as a valuable resource for researchers, policymakers, and healthcare organizations, enabling them to make informed decisions and effectively address challenges in implementing and sustaining healthcare IT systems, particularly EHRS in the NHS.

7.4 Theoretical and Practical Contributions to Knowledge and Literature

This section contains an outline of the research's major contributions to the related literature and knowledge. This study's first significant contribution to the related body of knowledge is a meticulous examination of various EHR themes and phenomena based on a detailed review of industry reports and academic literature, as well as the researcher's identification of the impact of internal and external factors on sustainable EHR change management and implementation. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, this is one of few healthcare-sector investigations into the organisational characteristics that can sabotage long-term, largescale EHRS adoption while attempting to explain the evolution of EHRS over the last decades. As noted in Chapter 3, this study discovered an EHRS literature gap that, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, has not been experimentally examined to such a substantial degree in past studies. Also, by developing a sustainable EHRS Implementation Framework for the healthcare sector, this research significantly contributes to the literature. In various aspects, this framework is distinctive because it is designed to provide comprehensive knowledge of the typically complex interconnections of internal and external elements that influence each organisation in different ways, all while efficiently managing major risks. The interviews were with 25 senior managers who were well-versed in EHRS concepts, both

theoretically and practically. The researcher observed that established EHRS methods differ among healthcare organisations and typically depend on a highly custom-tailored framework and policies that are compatible with each organisation’s objectives and structure. This study contributes to the general understanding of the role and significance of EHRSs in the healthcare sector. It identifies the key drivers of EHR, as well as its merits and obstacles to its implementation and provides prescriptive advice on how to achieve them. This is based on the theoretical and empirical investigations that were conducted as part of this study.

Furthermore, most of the empirical academic research into EHRS has been limited to quantitative research or certain parts of EHRS. Therefore, the significance of qualitative research’s use in the comprehensive assessment of political, cultural and sociological contexts has been overlooked. Because the researcher sees the EHRS field as immensely varied, a thorough grasp of its nature necessitates familiarity with its historical, organisational and external contexts. As a result, the methodological approach of the current EHRS research includes the use of robust and in-depth primary data collection and analysis methodology.

Table 7.1: Brief summary of research contributions

Contributions	Type	Description	Chapter/Figure
Development of the theoretical EHRS Sustainability Implementation Framework	Theoretical	<p>theoretical EHRS Sustainability Implementation Framework</p> <p>Stages of EHRS Implementation</p> <p>Factors Affecting EHRS Change Sustainability</p>	Chapter 3, Figure 3.9

Validation of the Developed EHRS Implementation Framework	Practical	Strategic EHRS Implementation Sustainability Framework	Chapter 6, Figure 6.1
Practical Guidelines	Practical	Practical Implementation Guidance for the EHRS Sustainability Framework	Chapter 6

Source: Researcher

7.5 Research Limitations

The researcher examined many areas of the related subject matter, the theoretical framework, the research technique, data collection, data analysis and sample selection in this research study. This section contains descriptions of the research limitations, which are based on the researcher's knowledge of the phenomenon being studied and available resources, such as skills, effort, information access and time. Hence, the limitations include the complexity of the EHRS Sustainable Implementation Framework. The researcher realises that due to the convoluted nature and intricacies of EHRs and the varied interplay of manifold aspects of the EHRS Framework shown in Figure 6.1, it may seem challenging to handle at first. The framework, on the contrary, was designed for those who are conversant with the fundamentals of EHR and change management. The limitations may, therefore, only apply to people who are inexperienced with the complexities of EHRs. This constraint can be alleviated through simplification of the framework following its practical use, which can be achieved through future research. The EHRS Sustainable Implementation Framework (Figure 6.1) focuses mainly on the challenges and features of EHRs in the healthcare sector and applies the study findings particularly to EHRS and not HIT in its entirety, thereby limiting the scope of the fieldwork for healthcare organisations.

The interviewees had to have experience in healthcare organisations. To mitigate the impact of this limitation, the researcher recruited top management cadre officials and healthcare professionals with substantial expertise in EHRs for the interviews. The qualitative case study method was used as the research strategy, so there may be bias in how the interviewer and respondents decipher social reality (Bergen and Labonte, 2020). The researcher avoided the flaws of utilising semi-structured interviews alone to collect and analyse data, thus reducing the possibility of bias. Only 25 interviews and 10 interview questions were used in this study. However, the modest sample size is justified by the nature of the HIT in which it was conducted (i.e., EHRs and the pedigree and senior roles of the respondents interviewed). The researcher attempted to improve the quality of this research by assuring the reliability and validity of the findings, as mentioned in Chapter 4, Section 4.7. Various metrics of the phenomenon under inquiry were obtained by combining multiple sources of empirical data. The use of an interview guide and the method of debriefing set the tone for the interviews and allowed the results to be verified. Furthermore, the interview agenda was built on a solid theoretical framework, guaranteeing that relevant data was acquired and bolstering the reliability of the finding. Despite the constraints indicated, the researcher examined key EHR themes and applications connected to its efficient change management and sustainable implementation. The analysis of the data assisted in capturing and validating essential EHR attributes, peculiarities and similarities with other HIT systems. While acknowledging that the study was conducted with a focus on EHRs in the healthcare sector, the researcher claims that the EHR Sustainable Implementation Framework can be applied to other HIT systems considering that the management will take the system's unique characteristics into account and appropriately tailor and adapt the framework.

One of the major limitations of this research was related to the COVID-19 pandemic that thrived over a period of two years (i.e., from 2020 to 2022) and adversely impacted the progress of this research. It was quite challenging to secure interviewees for the research due to lockdown within the country and around the world. Many fitting interviewees were reluctant to participate because they did not want to be close to any individual out of fear of being infected with COVID-19. Some potential interviewees were self-isolating while others were shielding. Healthcare organisations were grossly overwhelmed in attending to COVID-19 patients and had no accommodation for allowing interviews to be conducted with potential interviewees. Physicians (i.e., the end-users of EHRs) were frontline workers helping to attend to the ever-growing number of hospitalised patients. Hence, they were not available for interviews. This caused a major delay in the research and impacted the data collection and analysis of the research. The researcher was able to recruit interviewees by approaching them via LinkedIn. Furthermore, the interviews could not be conducted face-to-face. Rather, they were conducted online through Zoom to encourage participation while still observing government guidelines to covid restrictions.

7.6 Recommendations for Future Research

The current study's findings, which are exploratory in nature, serve as a springboard for additional research into a variety of issues and topics relevant to EHRs. The first recommendation is for the EHRs Sustainable Implementation Framework to be further developed. In the future, researchers should investigate its deployment in other HIT systems, such as the medical practice management systems, e-prescribing software, remote patient monitoring, urgent care applications, medical billing software, personal health records and electronic dental records. This would provide information on how the framework's

implementation varies among diverse HIT system applications in healthcare sectors. It would also be useful in determining how unique organisational characteristics influence the process of integrating the EHRS framework into various internal and external environments. Future research into this technique might be more quantitative in nature with a large sample group to bolster the generalisability of the results. Furthermore, such research may result in a visual and structural simplification of the model. Researchers should continue to seek and introduce new relevant features and contexts to the present framework as the EHR discipline develops. Additional research is required to measure, and quantify, when possible, the value associated with all aspects of EHR, including its potential benefits, problems and limitations so that the flaws can be readily overcome.

Furthermore, patient trust in the EHRS has been eroded due to the disclosure of personal data to unauthorised parties in healthcare applications. As a result, if the privacy of critical health information is compromised, then public trust may be jeopardized. Patients are continuously concerned about the safety and security of their health information, even though the present EHRS is quite viable and convenient. As a result, it is recommended that research be conducted on the creation and implementation of a blockchain-based platform for exchanging EHRs among numerous healthcare organizations while also considering security and privacy regulations for patient data. The blockchain would be the central component of a platform that enables patients to serve as data administrators. Because of the decentralization and transaction transparency properties of blockchains, the total protection private of patient information cannot be guaranteed. In the EHRS, a blockchain transaction is the process through which patient data is updated, produced, destroyed or transferred among the nodes of a connected network. This platform allows for the easy

identification of a specific node that visits the provider and the frequency of visits, allowing for the acquisition of confidential patient data such as names, diseases and current addresses. Additionally, challenges such as correctly organizing acquired data and determining the links within a blockchain network should be further researched. A framework for executing private and confidential interoperability using blockchain technology to protect patient data privacy in EHR-based blockchain transactions, keeping the data private and enabling anyone to validate the transaction without publicly revealing any data.

7.7 Implications for Developing Countries

Electronic Health Record Systems (EHRS) have revolutionized healthcare delivery worldwide, and their implementation holds great promise for developing countries such as Nigeria and South Africa. However, these nations face unique challenges in adopting and integrating EHRS into their healthcare systems. This section explores the implications of EHRS implementation in Nigeria and South Africa with relevant recommendation, considering the opportunities and hurdles they encounter in leveraging this technology to improve healthcare outcomes.

EHRS implementation in developing countries can lead to improved healthcare accessibility and quality. In both Nigeria and South Africa, the use of EHRS can bridge geographic gaps by providing remote access to patient records and specialist consultations. This enhanced accessibility can significantly improve healthcare delivery, particularly in rural and underserved areas where access to quality care is limited.

EHRS implementation facilitates the efficient management of vast amounts of healthcare data. In countries like Nigeria and South Africa, where paper-based records have been prevalent, transitioning to electronic systems can streamline data storage, retrieval, and analysis. As a result, healthcare providers can make more informed and data-driven decisions, leading to better patient outcomes and resource allocation.

EHRIS can bolster public health monitoring and research efforts in developing countries. Real-time data capture enables health authorities to track disease outbreaks, monitor vaccination coverage, and identify health trends promptly. This data-driven approach empowers policymakers to design targeted public health interventions and allocate resources effectively, ultimately advancing population health.

Despite the potential benefits, EHRIS implementation in developing countries faces significant financial constraints and infrastructure challenges. Limited funding and competing priorities may hamper the full-scale adoption of EHRIS in healthcare facilities. Moreover, inadequate IT infrastructure and intermittent internet connectivity can hinder the smooth functioning of electronic systems, demanding innovative solutions tailored to local contexts.

Developing countries need to address data privacy and security concerns associated with EHRIS implementation. Strengthening data protection laws, establishing robust cybersecurity measures, and raising awareness among healthcare professionals about the importance of safeguarding patient data are essential steps to mitigate these risks.

Achieving interoperability between different EHRIS platforms and medical devices remains a critical challenge in developing countries. The lack of standardized health information exchange protocols can hinder seamless data sharing among various healthcare facilities. Collaboration with international organizations and adherence to global interoperability standards can help address this issue.

EHRIS implementation in developing countries such as Nigeria and South Africa holds immense potential to transform healthcare delivery and improve population health. While the adoption of EHRIS can enhance healthcare accessibility, data management, and decision-making, challenges related to financial constraints, infrastructure, data privacy, and interoperability must be addressed. Collaborative efforts from governments, healthcare institutions, and international organizations are essential to overcome these hurdles and harness the full benefits of EHRIS technology in improving healthcare outcomes for the people of Nigeria and South Africa.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix A

Ethics Approval Letter

25/02/2021

Dear Olusola Daniel Oladiran,

Your application 13912: TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE CHANGE MANAGEMENT IN HEALTH INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (HIT): THE CASE OF UK NHS ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD SYSTEM (EHRS), submission 13336, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr. D Turner

Appendix B

Interview Consent Form

Research project title: Towards Sustainable Change Management in Health Information Technology
(HIT): The Case of UK Electronic Health Record System (EHRS)

Research investigator: Olusola Daniel Oladiran

Research Participants name:

The interview will take 15 minutes. We don't anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to stop the interview or withdraw from the research at any time.

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of the above research project. Ethical procedures for academic research undertaken from UK institutions require that interviewees explicitly agree to being interviewed and how the information contained in their interview will be used. This consent form is necessary for us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following:

- the interview will be recorded and a transcript will be produced
- you will be sent the transcript and given the opportunity to correct any factual errors
- the transcript of the interview will be analysed by Olusola Daniel Oladiran as research investigator
- access to the interview transcript will be limited to Olusola Daniel Oladiran and academic colleagues and researchers with whom he might collaborate as part of the research process
- any summary interview content, or direct quotations from the interview, that are made available through academic publication or other academic outlets will be anonymized so that you cannot be identified, and care will be taken to ensure that other information in the interview that could identify yourself is not revealed
- the actual recording will be (kept or destroyed state what will happen)
- any variation of the conditions above will only occur with your further explicit approval

All or part of the content of your interview may be used;

- In academic papers, policy papers or news articles

- On our website and in other media that we may produce such as spoken presentations
- On other feedback events
- In an archive of the project as noted above

By signing this form I agree that;

1. I am voluntarily taking part in this project. I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time;
2. The transcribed interview or extracts from it may be used as described above;
3. I have read the Information sheet;
4. I don't expect to receive any benefit or payment for my participation;
5. I can request a copy of the transcript of my interview and may make edits I feel necessary to ensure the effectiveness of any agreement made about confidentiality;
6. I have been able to ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.

Printed Name

Participants Signature

Date

Researchers Signature

Date

Contact Information

This research has been reviewed and approved by the Edinburgh University Research Ethics Board. If you have any further questions or concerns about this study, please contact:

Name of researcher Olusola Daniel Oladiran

Tel: [REDACTED]

E-mail: [REDACTED]

You can also contact Olusola's supervisor:

Name Prof. Abraham Althonayan

Tel: [REDACTED]

E-mail: [REDACTED]

What if I have concerns about this research? If you are worried about this research, or if you are concerned about how it is being conducted, you can contact the Chair of the Business and Creative Industries SEC Dr. Daniel Turner (██████████).

Appendix C

Participant Information Sheet

1. Research Project Title

Towards Sustainable Change Management in Health Information Technology (HIT): The Case of UK NHS Electronic Health Record System (EHRS)

2. Invitation

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide to do so, it is important you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you wish to take part or not. Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the project's purpose?

This research project aims to investigate the implementation and sustainability of change management in health care IT systems; and to develop an effective framework for sustainable HIT systems supported by implementation guidance for managers and practitioners.

4. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because as project manager, Director of HIT, Change Manager or person in a similar role, you will have knowledge about HIT change management and its attendant challenges.

5. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether to take part or not. If you do decide to take part you will be able to keep a copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement to the online consent form. You can still withdraw at any time. You do not have to give a reason.

6. What do I have to do?

You will be required to participate in interview session virtually online for a period of 30mins. There are no other commitments or lifestyle restrictions associated with participating.

7. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress will be the same as any experienced in everyday life.

8. What are the possible benefits of taking part? Whilst there are no immediate benefits for those people participating in the project, it is hoped that this work will have a beneficial impact on how change in HIT systems is managed. Results will be shared with participants to inform their professional work.

9. What happens if the research study stops earlier than expected?

Should the research stop earlier than planned and you are affected in any way we will tell you and explain why.

10. Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

All the information that we collect about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. Your institution will also not be identified or identifiable. Any data collected about you in the interview will be stored online protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies.

11. Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

Yes, during the interview session you will be recorded audio visually via Zoom platform solely for the purpose of this interview to aid analysis of data acquired during interview.

12. What type of information will be sought from me and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

In the interview, the researcher will ask you about your opinions and current practices in relation to EHRS. Your views and experience are just what the project is interested in exploring.

13. What will happen to the results of the research project?

Results of the research will be published. You will not be identified in any report or publication. Your institution will not be identified in any report or publication. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please kindly indicate.

14. Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This project has been ethically approved by School of Business and Creative Industries ethics review procedure of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS).

15. Contacts for further information

School of Business & Creative Industries BClethics@uws.ac.uk

Chair of University Ethics Committee: Professor Moira Lewitt, [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this research.

Appendix C

Research Interview Questions

1. What is your current role in your organisation?
2. What type of healthcare organisation do you work for? You can choose more than one options
 - a. Community or Integrated healthcare
 - b. Residential social care
 - c. Community social care
 - d. Miscellaneous healthcare (e.g paramedics)
 - e. Others (specify)
3. What is the size of your organisation based on the number of employees?
 - a. 1-500
 - b. 500-2000
 - c. 2000-5000
 - d. 5000-10000
 - e. >10000
4. How many years have you worked in HIT change management or EHR Management?
 - a. 1-5years
 - b. 5-10years
 - c. 10-15years
 - d. 15-20years
 - e. Others (specify)
5. Which stage of HIT Implementation have you been involved in? You can choose more than one option
 - a. Initiation stage
 - b. Execution stage
 - c. Monitoring stage
 - d. Others (specify)
6. What are the challenges affecting the implementation of HIT systems especially EHR in your organisation? You can choose more than one option
 - a. Ineffective change management
 - b. Lack of data security and privacy
 - c. Interoperability issue
 - d. Inadequate staff training
 - e. Poor system installation
 - f. Others (specify)
7. What fundamental actions were undertaken at the initiation phase of EHR in your organisation? You can choose more than one option

- a. Change Vision
 - b. Need for Change
 - c. Strategy
 - d. Stakeholders involvement
 - e. Realistic timeline
 - f. Procurement
 - g. Others (Specify)
8. In the execution of EHRS, what were the key components that guaranteed successful execution of the system? You can choose more than one option
- a. Flexibility and local adaptability
 - b. Interoperability
 - c. Data security infrastructure
 - d. Training
 - e. Acceptance of Use
 - f. Others (specify)
9. How is the current EHRS in your organisation monitored to ensure sustainability? You can choose more than one option
- a. Key Performance Indicator (KPI)
 - b. System improvement
 - c. Technical support
 - d. Feedback
 - e. Ongoing coaching
 - f. Others (specify)
10. What are the necessary conditions critical to the success of change sustainability of Electronic Health Record Systems (EHRS) in the NHS? You can choose more than one option
- a. Communication, Culture, Finance
 - b. Leadership, Governance (policy), Project Management, Socioeconomic Factor
 - c. Performance management, organisational structure, accountability
 - d. All the above
 - e. Others (specify)